

ALTEX

Proceedings

EUSAAT 2024

The European Congress on 3Rs

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EUSAAT

*European Society for
Alternatives to Animal Testing*

The European 3Rs Society

- ▶ NAMs and NGRA implementation in industry
- ▶ Inflammation & Infection models
- ▶ Animal Methods Bias
- ▶ Methods for Toxicology
- ▶ Animal-free human based cell culture
- ▶ 3R Research Funding in Europe
- ▶ The Value of Transition Approaches in Animal Free Scientific Research
- ▶ Stem cell models
- ▶ Culture of Care: Enhancing Communication among Stakeholders for 3Rs Progress
- ▶ Cancer models
- ▶ Novel in silico tools
- ▶ 3Rs Implementation: Progress and Barriers
- ▶ 3Rs: ethical conceptual considerations and harmonisation
- ▶ Outer Biological Barriers
- ▶ Refinement
- ▶ Lung models
- ▶ Policy / networking
- ▶ 3Rs Implementation: Providing frameworks and tools
- ▶ Emerging technologies I & II
- ▶ Musculoskeletal In vitro models
- ▶ Reduction: Planning and Reporting
- ▶ Inner organ models
- ▶ Education about 3Rs

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Dear friends and colleagues,

On behalf of EUSAAT, the European Society for Alternatives to Animal Testing, we welcome you to the 24th European 3Rs Congress and the 21th EUSAAT Congress in Linz/Austria from September 18-20, 2024.

Since 1991 the “Linz Congress” has become the main event in the field of 3Rs science in Europe. We are excited to welcome you in person in Linz to celebrate the 3Rs and explore avenues for improvement and innovation of animal testing. Among the many registrations of friends and colleagues, we particularly value the upcoming reports of our international partners from Japan (JSAAE – Japanese Society for Alternatives to Animal Experiments) and China (CCARE) on their recent developments in the 3Rs field.

As usual, EUSAAT 2024 hosts oral and poster presentations to facilitate discussions and exchange ideas to promote the most advanced non-animal methods in the life sciences. The Scientific Committee has put together a stimulating and appealing program on the most exciting subjects that are currently the focus of 3Rs research in Europe and worldwide.

The **main program focus is on Replacement methods as the most critical pillar of 3Rs research**, with sessions on animal-free human cell cultures, and novel technologies for skin, lung and cardiac toxicity, liver and intestine, cancer research, ecotoxicology, developmental neurotoxicity (DNT), novel *in silico* tools, stem cell models, biological barrier models, inflammation and infection studies, and NAM and NGRA implementation.

As with previous events, the EUSAAT Congress 2024 also constitutes a platform for the other two pillars, **Reduction, and Refinement**, including sessions and topics such as culture of care, reduction: planning and reporting, refinement, and on the value of transition approaches in animal-free scientific research.

We are more than happy to welcome many members from the **COST Action IMPROVE (CA21139)**, which was founded two years ago. The COST Action IMPROVE established a European network to **refine, harmonize, and promote data, documents, and 3Rs concepts in order to improve the quality of biomedical science**. To support the mission, we will host together with the COST Action a 3R centers workshop prior to the conference based on our successful initiatives throughout the past conferences.

We are very pleased that distinguished colleagues have followed our call to Linz as keynote speakers to enrich our program with various perspectives and exciting insights on recent achievements and scientific progress. Aside from excellent Austrian cuisine, the Gala dinner will host the Award for the best ALTEX article in 2023, and we will celebrate our young scientists travel awardees.

Another highlight of this year's conference is the series of YOU events integrated throughout the EUSAAT 2024 program. These events are aimed at young and early-career scientists working or planning to work in the 3Rs field. Our goal is to facilitate dialogue between young scientists and their established mentors, opening up professional networking opportunities and providing a free and open atmosphere for exchanging scientific ideas and career perspectives in the 3Rs field. EUSAAT continues to support early career scientists with the "Young Scientists Travel Awards (YSTA)" with the help of the SET Foundation's generous funding. The YSTA program provides 20 young scientists with the opportunity to share their ideas on implementing the 3Rs in education and using novel test systems to reduce animal suffering and overall numbers in research. EPAA, *ecopa*, and PCRM sponsor five additional travel grants, and ATLA supports our youngest with Young Investigator Awards for best conference presentations.

The EUSAAT Board is pleased to announce that the sponsoring of the EUSAAT congresses is continuously increasing. The generous financial support of our sponsors can keep the scientific standard high and the congress fees low. This central EUSAAT ideology attracts young scientists from Europe and beyond. Thus, on behalf of the participants, the EUSAAT Board, and the Scientific Committee, we thank our sponsors. Also, we thank Sonja von Aulock, editor and CEO of ALTEX Edition, for her support to again promote our conference abstracts via publication in *ALTEX Proceedings*.

Finally, we want to thank our colleagues on the EUSAAT Board, the Scientific Committee, and the Co-Organizers for their continuous support in planning this year's EUSAAT Congress.

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1

JNK is activated in an EGFR-induced *Drosophila* lung tumor model and promotes cancer progression

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Mutations in the EGFR gene are among the most important drivers of lung tumor development, but the success of personalized therapies is still limited due to the development of resistance. The role of JNK in lung cancers harboring EGFR gene mutations is not fully understood. We specifically expressed constitutively active EGFR (Egfr^{CA}) in the *Drosophila* airway system and performed a comprehensive phenotypic analysis. Ectopic expression of Egfr^{CA} induced tumor-like growth of larval tracheal stem cells. We found that overexpression of Egfr^{CA} in larval trachea activated three downstream signaling pathways: MAPK, PI3K/Akt and JAK/STAT

signaling pathways, respectively. We blocked each of the three signaling pathways and found that in this Egfr^{CA} ectopic expression-induced lung cancer model, the MAPK pathway was mainly involved in proliferation, PI3K/Akt in maintaining cell survival, and JAK/STAT in metastasis. We next found that JNK activated in the Egfr^{CA}-induced tumor model and blocking JNK rescued tumor-like proliferation and significantly reduced Egfr^{CA} activation of MAPK, PI3K, and JAK/STAT pathways, while also rescuing Egfr^{CA}-induced animal death. Pharmacological tests found that a synergistic effect of subtherapeutic doses of afatinib in combination with JNK inhibitors; reduction of the drug toxicity of PI3K inhibitors in combination with JNK inhibitors. Taken together, we developed a *Drosophila* lung cancer model with tumor-like growth of tracheal stem cells and used the *Drosophila* model study to identify JNK as a key regulator of EGFR-induced lung cancer progression, providing a promising therapeutic option for treating lung cancer patients with EGFR gene mutations and JNK overexpression.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

4

Systematic analysis of gut bacterial carcinogen biotransformation and its functional consequences

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Organic carcinogens, in particular DNA-reactive compounds, contribute to the irreversible initiation step of tumorigenesis through introduction of genomic instability. Although carcinogen bioactivation and detoxification by human enzymes has been extensively studied, carcinogen biotransformation by human-associated bacteria, the microbiota, has not yet been systematically investigated. We tested the biotransformation of 68 mutagenic carcinogens by

34 bacterial species representative for the upper and lower human gastrointestinal tract and found that the majority of tested carcinogens undergo bacterial metabolism. To assess the functional consequences of microbial carcinogen metabolism, we established a pipeline to couple gut bacterial carcinogen biotransformation assays with Ames mutagenicity testing and liver biotransformation experiments. This revealed bidirectional crosstalk between gut microbiota and host carcinogen metabolism, which we validated in gnotobiotic mouse models. Overall, the systematic assessment of gut microbiota carcinogen biotransformation and its interplay with host metabolism highlights the gut microbiome as an important modulator of exposome-induced tumorigenesis.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

5

Engineering of a tissue-mimetic biochip model of the human synovial membrane for osteoarthritis research using non-animal-derived protocols and materials

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To truly advance pharmaceutical development in osteoarthritis (OA), patient-derived and animal-product-free tissue models are needed to overcome the current limitations of all organ-on-a-chip and other 3D cell culture systems.

In this study an animal-product-free protocol to model osteoarthritic synovia is introduced and tested that utilizes primary human OA-patient synoviocyte cultures (e.g., bio-waste) adapted to

non-animal products such as human fibrin (TISSEEL hydrogel) and human platelet lysate (ELAREM™). The elimination of commonly used animal-derived matrix components and proteins (e.g., Matrigel, FBS, etc.) for *in vitro* tissue generations is considered essential to overcome unphysiological cell-matrix structure-function relationships in human disease modeling.

Results of our study show that the animal-product-free OA-synovial tissue-mimetic organoid's architectures do respond in a physiological manner to varying hydrogel stiffnesses where softer matrices induce pathophysiological traits. A demonstration of the clinical relevance of the established animal-product-free and patient-centered osteoarthritic synovial tissue model is the obtained significant Yap1 overexpression under varying inflammatory environments, thus pointing at synovial hyperplasia based on cell stimulation and pro-inflammatory progression.

Overall, our animal-product-free 3D cell culture approach not only aligns with ethical considerations of refining, reducing and replacing animal testing, but also offers a closer approximation to the structure-function relationship of actual OA patient synovia.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

6

Quantitative AOP modeling of mucus hypersecretion using 3D cells for comparative risk estimation of tobacco products

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Adverse outcome pathway (AOP) serves as a simplified representation of intricate biological cascades culminating in adverse outcomes. While primarily utilized in toxicological assessments, the AOP framework holds potential for extending its applicability to disease-related risk assessments. We have developed an AOP-based *in vitro* assessment method targeting mucus hypersecretion in the airway, a hallmark symptom of respiratory diseases, through repeated exposure to cigarette smoke. Additionally, we have devised a Bayesian network (BN)-based analysis approach enabling probabilistic quantitative AOP (qAOP) assessments. To reflect interin-

dividual variability, 3D bronchial epithelial cells from six donors were utilized. Subsequently, means and standard deviations from each donor were employed for resampling within the BN modeling framework to compensate for the sparsity of the original *in vitro* dataset. In this study, we performed risk assessments for our heated tobacco product (DT3.0a), based on the previously developed method for cigarettes and compared their respective risks of inducing mucus hypersecretion. Results revealed that DT3.0a elicited less pronounced effects on the AOP, including mucus hypersecretion, across all donors. Conversely, cigarette smoke exposure yielded varied responses, possibly indicative of individual differences, although most donors exhibited increased mucin secretion over time. The BN model, leveraging these *in vitro* datasets, indicated DT3.0a aerosol exposure predominantly showed negligible or lower probabilities of adverse outcome onset than cigarette smoke exposure. Our presentation will further explore the linkage between *in vitro* and real-world exposure scenarios, as well as the BN-based qAOP results and their implications for respiratory system in humans.

Conflict of interest

This work involved DT3.0a (PloomX, manufactured by Japan Tobacco Inc.). All authors are employees of Japan Tobacco Inc. All experimental work was funded by Japan Tobacco Inc.

Presentation: Poster

7

How good communication can advance a good culture of care

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Establishing a good “culture of care” is a fundamental requirement if legal, ethical and animal welfare obligations, along with wider responsibilities towards employees and the public, are to be met.

Almost all aspects of what is needed to achieve and maintain a good culture of care can be linked back in some way to systems and effectiveness of communication – both within establishments, and with wider stakeholders.

For example, corporate expectations of standards of science, ethics and animal welfare should be clearly set out by management and understood by all personnel, and good performance should be appropriately supported and recognised; effective processes should be in place to facilitate the flow of information about the 3Rs into and around the establishment; forums for raising ideas for, and dis-

ussion of, continuous improvement in practices should be in place; and a clear system for reporting and acting upon concerns should be known to all.

Similarly, to meet societal expectations for openness and transparency, establishments should provide balanced and meaningful information to the public and interested stakeholders, including on how animals are used, what they experience, and the steps taken to avoid their use and minimise impacts on their well-being.

This presentation will reflect on how good communication can enable the fullest implementation of the 3Rs and open discussion of ethical issues. It will also provide practical ideas to help fulfil commitments to quality science, good animal welfare, and responsibilities to personnel and the public [1].

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Conflict of interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

8

Enhancing Atlantic sturgeon stem cell culture: Assessing serum reduction and growth factor substitution effects

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Sturgeons are known for their economic significance in caviar production, but they are also important in evolutionary research and their crucial role in aquatic ecosystems. The Atlantic sturgeon (*Acipenser oxyrinchus*) is currently exploited in the aquaculture industry but in nature classified as “vulnerable” by the IUCN (International Union for Conservation of Nature) Red List [1].

Sturgeon cell cultures serve as important tools for studying the biology, toxicology, and virology of sturgeons, while also offering alternatives to *in vivo* studies. Nevertheless, traditional cell culture cultivation relies heavily on Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS), known for its inter-batch variability and ethical concerns in production. In recent years, great efforts have been made to reduce and substitute the use of serum, but for fish cell cultures the knowledge is still limited compared to mammalian cell cultures, leading to greater difficulties in finding alternatives for their cultivation.

To address this, we have evaluated the impact of serum reduction (from 10% to 5% and 2%) and substitution with growth factors (FGF-Basic, LIF, IL-13, and IFN- γ added to 2% medium) on the proliferation of an Atlantic sturgeon cell line (AOXlar7y) [2-4]. Our results indicate the AOXlar7y cell line’s resilience to serum reduction, suggesting promising prospects for eliminating serum usage in the future. However, the incorporation of growth factors yielded unexpected results making further investigation necessary. This research contributes to advancing sustainable and ethical practices in sturgeon cell culture and underscores the importance of conservation efforts for this vulnerable species.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

9

Keeping an eye on the move: Tracking cell migration with optical imaging in 3D

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Cell migration is crucial in various biological processes, yet traditional cell culture methods often fail to accurately replicate migration mechanisms. This study aimed to develop a bioengineered platform for non-invasive monitoring of cell migration, with a specific focus on creating a more reliable and easier-to-use tool, while also reducing animal usage in drug development.

A 3D system was created utilizing a silk scaffold, complemented by the introduction of dynamic flow mode facilitated by an HPLC pump, ensuring constant media flow for nutrients and oxygen supply. Optimization of cell culture duration and shear stress levels of the dynamic platform enhanced the system's efficiency. 4T1 breast cancer cells were labelled with Near Infrared Fluorescent (NIR) markers for real-time monitoring via *in vivo* imaging system (IVIS). Spheroids, including co-culture with fibroblast variants, were created to mimic the tumor microenvironment, with plans to introduce to the optimized platform. Various antimigrastatic agents were assessed via traditional 2D and 3D setups, compared against the self-designed bioreactor system.

After validating the cell seeding efficacy, we demonstrated that our system could sustain viable cells for over 10 days. We showed that continuous and efficient nutrient supply along with waste removal enhanced cell viability, providing a unique and physiologically relevant platform for 3D cell culture. Cell migration was flow-rate dependent in a longitudinal direction and significant inhibition by antimigrastatic agent effects could be observed via IVIS.

In summary, our engineered dynamic 3D platform shows potential as an advanced, user-friendly, and cost-effective tool for investigating cellular migration and cancer invasion.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

10

The power of animal welfare body networks to promote best practices

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At the 2022 Federation of European Laboratory Animal Science Associations (FELASA) congress, a plenary session discussed how national Animal Welfare Body (AWB) networks can improve promotion of a good Culture of Care by sharing initiatives and best practices. Several countries have set up AWB networks, enabling AWBs to share good practice with respect to establishing effective processes and fulfilling all of their tasks. This has helped many AWBs to improve animal welfare, the implementation of the 3Rs, the quality of the science and staff well-being. Despite these benefits, organized AWB networks are not yet common practice. Following on from the FELASA congress, a group has been estab-

lished with the aim of encouraging and developing more national AWB networks.

The ultimate objective of the network is an overarching European Network of National Networks for AWBs⁷ (ENAWB), to help ensure good practice for achieving the following:

- All AWBs successfully meeting the requirements of Directive 2010/63/EU.
- AWBs supporting one another, learning from one another and sharing experiences on how AWB tasks are successfully delivered.
- Sharing of practices and ideas on operational matters, regarding national AWB networks.
- Discussion of AWB operational issues and challenges, and how these can be addressed.
- Sharing of training materials for AWBs.
- Enabling AWBs to address the 3Rs more effectively.

The talk will present the network's activities to date, proposals for its further development and plans for future initiatives.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

11

Evaluation of chemically defined cell culture media with the cellasys #8 assay

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The development of fetal bovine serum (FBS)-free media is crucial to ensure consistent, reproducible, and translatable results and safe products [1,2]. For these reasons, researchers are trying to transit from serum-based cell culture media (CCM) to chemically defined CCM without FBS. To do so, weaning experiments are usually carried out to evaluate new serum-free CCM formulations. Here, cells are gradually switched from a serum-based CCM to a serum-free alternative. However, such experiments take weeks to months, resulting in labor-intensive and, hence, time-consuming tasks. In the presented work, we demonstrate the application of the cellasys #8 assay [3] for the evaluation of chemically defined CCM for Caco-2 and L929 cell lines. The cellasys #8 assay is a multiparametric and label-free method based on microphysiometry [4]. It runs for 24 hours and measures effects of treatment as well as recovery of substances toward the cellular model.

Three cellasys #8 assays were performed for each cell line. Chemically defined CCM under investigation were 1) DME, 2) DME/Ham's-F12, and 3) DME/Ham's-F12/ITS [5]. To evaluate the CCM, treatment and recovery of the cells were calculated for metabolism and morphology. For Caco-2 the metabolic data identifies 2) and 3) as suitable, whereas the morphological data identifies only 3) as a usable CCM. For L929 metabolic as well as morphologic data identify 3) as a good chemically defined CCM.

The data demonstrates that the cellasys #8 assay can successfully identify chemically-defined CCM formulations at increased speed and reduced costs.

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Conflict of interest

Joachim Wiest is shareholder and CEO of cellasys know-how.

Presentation: Oral

12

Establishment of three-dimensional infection and cancer tissue models for the validation of laser-based diagnostic medical devices

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Background: Head and neck cancer has a poor prognosis as it is often detected at a late stage due to a lack of sensitive screening procedures. A correlation between bacterial compositions of the oral microbiome and cancer initiation is thought [1]. Within the BMBF-funded project “TIRAMISU” [2] a non-invasive endoscopic method should be developed to enable early diagnosis of microbial infections and carcinomas in humans.

Methods: Aim of the project is the integration of laser-based FLIM and Raman technology. The validation of these diagnostic tools will be performed using preclinical studies on human three-dimensional (3D) tissue models instead of the established highly stressful C57BL/6J (black 6) mouse model, in which 4NQO ingestion induces oral carcinogenesis.

Results: We developed various 3D cancer and infection tissue models. All tissue models are based on a decellularized porcine intestine (SISmuc) [3]. The immunocompetent tissue model represents a co-culture of primary fibroblasts and THP-1 derived

macrophages. For the establishment of the infection model an implant mesh is cultivated with a biofilm of *Staphylococcus spec.* and *Pseudomonas spec.* and integrated into the immunocompetent tissue model [4]. Cancer models were produced by the integration of tumor spheroids from a pharyngeal cancer cell line FADU.

Conclusion: The new diagnostic endoscope including FLIM and RAMAN technology will be validated in blinded studies with the above-described tissue models and against the established mouse model C57BL/6J. These results could be a reliable validation method for the approval of medical devices and thus be a replacement for animal studies.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

13

Appreciation is key: Improving the 3Rs by optimizing communication with young researchers

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According to a survey by the German Research Center for Higher Education and Scientific Studies (DZHW), more than half of the scientists surveyed seriously considered leaving academia [1]. The reasons have to do with factors such as the Scientific Temporary Contract Law in some countries (e.g., Germany and Italy), the high workload, the pressure to publish, the lack of resources, and the lack of communication with supervisors and colleagues. This disengagement is exacerbated in the case of researchers working with animals, who face additional stress factors such as the unavoidable fact of experimenting and killing animals, stigmatization, and strenuous work to fulfill regulatory tasks for approval of animal experiments. A relevant stakeholder in this debate is the young researchers, who conduct most animal experiments in academia and industry and to whom the adequate understanding and application of the 3Rs and the development of new alternative methods are incumbent. In this oral presentation, I will discuss some perceptions

of young researchers regarding internal communication, stressors, and stress-coping mechanisms when working with animal experiments, according to information gained from a previous workshop [2]. Subsequently, I will reflect on the importance of setting expectations in any communication approach, the impact of cultural differences when communicating, and the environmental setting for working on emotional competencies within animal research and the 3Rs. I will end the talk by mentioning examples of how supervisors and young minds can improve communication and mutual appreciation.

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Conflict of interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

16

Microenvironmental acidification by pneumococcal sugar consumption fosters barrier disruption and immune suppression in the human alveolus

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Streptococcus pneumoniae (*S.p.*) is the most common causative agent of community-acquired pneumonia. Accordingly, many animal experiments related to *S.p.*, particularly in mice, are conducted. A key pathogenic mechanism that exacerbates severity of disease is the disruption of the alveolar-capillary barrier. However, the specific virulence mechanisms responsible for this in the human lung are not yet fully understood.

In this study, we infected living human lung tissue with *S.p.* and observed a significant degradation of the central junctional proteins occludin and VE-cadherin, indicating barrier disruption. Surprisingly, neither pneumolysin, bacterial hydrogen peroxide nor pro-inflammatory activation were sufficient to cause this junctional degradation. Instead, pneumococcal infection led to a significant decrease of pH (approximately 6), resulting in acidification of the alveolar microenvironment, which was linked to junctional degradation. Stabilizing the pH at physiological levels during infection reversed this effect, even in a therapeutic-like approach.

Further analysis of bacterial metabolites and RNA sequencing revealed sugar consumption and subsequent lactate production were the major factors contributing to bacterially induced alveolar acidification, which also hindered the release of critical immune factors.

Our findings highlight bacterial metabolite-induced acidification as an independent virulence mechanism for barrier disruption and inflammatory dysregulation in pneumonia. Thus, our data suggest that strictly monitoring and buffering alveolar pH during infections caused by fermentative bacteria could serve as an adjunctive therapeutic strategy for sustaining barrier integrity and immune response. Human 3D culture models can provide new clinically relevant insights into the widespread disease pneumonia while also serving as an alternative to animal testing.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

17

A platform for *in vivo* label-free tissue histology to reduce the use of animals in biomaterial tests

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Tissue histopathology, relying on H&E staining of thin tissue slices, is the standard method for assessing immune reactions to implanted biomaterials. It's time-consuming, expensive, and unsuitable for longitudinal studies. Non-linear excitation microscopy provides a label-free, *in vivo* option. We designed and validated an implantable micro-structured device for assessing immune reactions to biomaterial implants using this technique. The device, resembling a matrix of regular 3D lattices, is fabricated using two-photon laser polymerization [1], it can be implanted in animal models and directly observed using non-linear excitation microscopy. By comparing histological and microscopy images, we create a cell atlas correlating histological observations with label-free images. Initial tests on the

chorioallantoic membrane of embryonated chicken eggs are then compared with early results in mice. The non-linear excitation images are then converted in the staining typically used for histological analysis by means of dedicated deep neural networks and can be used to quantify the number of cells recruited in the tissue reconstituted in the microstructures and identify granulocytes on label-free images within and outside the microstructures [2]. Collagen and microvessels are detected using second-harmonic generation and autofluorescence imaging. The analysis suggests that the tissue response to implanted microstructures resembles typical healing after injury. Similar microstructures, integrated with biomaterial, could enable *in vivo* test of the biomaterial using label-free non-linear excitation microscopy on a reduced number of animals.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 964481.

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Conflict of interest

None

Presentation: Oral

18

Culture of care: Where are the resources I need to improve conditions at my workplace?

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Great efforts are being made internationally to help staff improve their workplace conditions – both to benefit their own welfare, health and safety, and that of the animals. The phrase “culture of care” has been coined to indicate a demonstrable commitment, throughout the establishment, to improving animal welfare, scientific quality, care of staff and transparency for all stakeholders, including the public. An important element of this culture is that it goes beyond simply complying with the law.

Norecopa hosts the website of the International Culture of Care Network [1]. The site includes links to a large number of resources that can be used to increase culture of care [2]. The countries currently participating on the Network can be visualized on Norecopa’s interactive global map of 3R resources [3].

This presentation will give an overview of the various types of available resources.

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Conflict of interest

Curator of the website of the International Culture of Care Network.

Presentation: Oral

19

Quality, fast, cheap: Choose two. Practical advice on how to conduct better science

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As discussions about the current “reproducibility crisis” continue, and the extent to which animal studies can be replaced or avoided is hotly debated, a need remains for detailed, practical advice on how to plan those studies which, at the outset, appear to involve the use of animals.

It is my firm belief that the path to better science involves a series of events, starting with better planning and ending in better reporting. Having managed research animal facilities for 30 years, it is also my impression that much of the input into the debate about animal research comes from scientists who know more about the “mathematics” of experimental design in their special fields than

the factors within a facility which affect validity, animal welfare, and health & safety. Close collaboration between facility staff and the research team, from day 1 of planning, is therefore essential. Ethical and legal evaluation of a proposed study necessitate collaboration with additional players: funders, ethical committees, regulators and journals.

A “publish or perish” atmosphere in which many scientists appear to work, creates the temptation to work fast and publish fast, using existing protocols and without adequate discussion as to whether they can be refined or rejected. This is worsened by the apparent lack of species- and situation-specific guidelines. It is rarely possible to conduct good quality, cheap research fast – one of these three parameters will be sacrificed.

This presentation will give early career researchers an overview of resources, building upon the work done by Norecopa and others.

Conflict of interest

The author is Secretary of Norecopa and manages the Norecopa website.

Presentation: Oral

20

A new animal-product-free, defined, and universal cell culture medium: Easy to use, do-it-yourself and beneficial for 2D and 3D culturing of normal and cancer cells

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Cell culturing methods are increasingly used to reduce and replace the use of live animals in biomedical research and chemical toxicity testing. Although live animals are avoided when using cell-culturing methods, they often contain animal-derived components, most commonly fetal bovine serum (FBS). FBS is added to cell culture media among other supplements to support cell attachment/spreading and proliferation. The safety, batch-to-batch variation and ethical problems with FBS [1] are widely acknowledged and therefore worldwide efforts are ongoing to produce FBS free media.

Here, we present the composition of a new defined medium [2,3] with human proteins either recombinant or derived from human tissues: Oredsson Universal Replacement (OUR) Medium.

OUR medium supports long term routine culturing of normal and cancer cells. Additionally, it can be used for cell banking and cryopreservation. We show growth curves and dose response curves of cells grown in two and three dimensions as well as applications such as cell migration. Cell morphology was studied in real time by phase contrast and phase holographic microscopy time-lapse imaging. OUR medium is successfully used with human normal and cancer-associated fibroblasts, human keratinocytes, several human breast and pancreatic cancer cell lines, human colon cancer CaCo-2 cells as well as several other normal and cancer cells [3].

In conclusion, we present the composition of OUR defined medium without animal-derived products that can be used for routine culturing and in experimental settings for normal and cancer cells, i.e., OUR medium provides a leap towards a universal animal product-free cell culture medium.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Have the non-technical summaries of animal experiments in Europe improved? An update

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Following a review of the Directive 2010/63/EU on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes in the European Union (EU), non-technical project summaries (NTS) of all approved projects must be published in a central database using a standard template [1]. Our initial review of the NTS reported in ALTEX in 2018 had found the NTS to be deficient in their accessibility and quality, notably the adverse effects section where the harms to the animals are meant to be described [2]. Here we repeat our review to see if these legislative changes have improved the accessibility and quality of the NTS.

As before we focused on the NTS from the United Kingdom (UK) and Germany; even though the UK has left the EU it is using the same template. We found significant improvement in the report-

ing of five of the six elements we identified as essential to the predicted harms section. However, there was no significant improvement in the reporting of adverse effects. Only 41% of German NTS and 48% of UK NTS are fully reporting this important element of the predicted harms section [3].

Unless the NTS improve further, their utility as a tool for sharing of good practices in the 3Rs or to support evidence-based policy making will remain limited. In our view, researchers need support in describing the impact of their research on the animals and to assist here we include a checklist for competent authorities and a list of suggested terminology for standard administration and sampling procedures [3].

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Implementation of an *in vitro* angiogenesis assay to study mechanisms of vascular invasion during endochondral ossification

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Vascularization via sprouting angiogenesis is crucial in bone development and fracture repair, occurring through endochondral ossification. Newly formed vessels invade the initially formed cartilage template to promote mineralization and transition to bone. Despite its importance, the precise mechanisms underlying vascular invasion remain elusive. Hypertrophic chondrocytes, which produce vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), are implicated in driving vascularization. Conversely, suppression of vascular invasion has been linked to enhanced chondrogenesis and delayed bone formation and healing. To elucidate these mechanisms, we developed an *in vitro* three-dimensional co-culture system combining GFP-labeled human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs) and human bone marrow stromal cells (hMSCs) [1]. Here we exemplify the integration of this model in two basic research projects focusing

on (i) the functional significance of the chemokine CXCL12, also known as stromal-derived factor 1 (SDF-1), in YAP/TAZ-mediated angiogenesis [2] and (ii) the effect of the matricellular growth factor Cyr61 during vascularized fracture repair [3]. In short, depletion of YAP/TAZ from hMSCs impaired tubular network formation, while supplementation with recombinant CXCL12 rescued this phenotype, providing crucial evidence for a functional link during bone development. In addition, Cyr61 treatment significantly enhanced tubular network formation, suggesting its role in vascular morphogenesis and a potential strategy for future therapeutic approaches. Thus, our model provides insights into the complex interplay between endothelial cells and stromal cells during vascular invasion in bone development and repair. Understanding these mechanisms could inform novel therapeutic strategies for enhancing bone regeneration and fracture healing.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

23

Repeated injection of sustained-release buprenorphine for pain management in mouse femoral fracture models

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Ethical and scientific reasons demand optimized pain regimens in animal experiments to avoid any preventable stress or discomfort. Buprenorphine is a highly potent analgesic opioid with common application in a wide range of pre-clinical studies. Buprenorphine has a short pharmacokinetic half-life, requiring injection every 4-8 h [1]. Depot formulations of Buprenorphine for laboratory animals are commercially available in the USA providing sustained analgesia without the need for frequent, repeated injections. However, several studies have shown restricted duration of action with effective serum concentrations over a maximum of 24 to 48 h [2]. As a result, re-administration might be necessary if clinical signs indicate insufficient pain amelioration in the animals. Here, we investi-

gated whether the administration of a repeated dose of sustained-release Buprenorphine (SR-Bup) could ensure a continuous and sufficient analgesia over 72 h in a mouse femoral fracture model using the most frequently used intramedullary pin fixation. We monitored (i) general parameters of wellbeing, e.g., body weight and clinical score, and (ii) walking behavior as model-specific pain parameter. We also observed a previously unreported reaction to repeated injection of SR-Bup, which we evaluated by additional experimental and histological analyses. The availability of evidence-based and optimized analgesic regimes for post-surgical pain treatment in laboratory animals is imperative for preclinical studies on bone fracture repair to ensure scientific quality and translational potential as well as to increase animal welfare by actively supporting the implementation of the 3R principle (refinement).

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

24

Reducing our reliance on animals through advanced technologies: Today and tomorrow

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The success of preclinical pipelines relies on the ability of the models used to predict the safety and efficacy of drug candidates in patients. Advanced technologies such as complex multimodal imaging, OMICs, New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) and AI/ML have the potential to complement traditional *in vivo* and *in vitro* models, maximizing data insight from each study, refine models and accelerate decision making. This presentation will outline examples where such complementarity where advanced technology helps improve the predictivity of preclinical work, bridge the cross-species translational gap, and reduce our reliance on animal use.

Imaging technologies have become a key aspect of the pharmaceutical research & development process to understand the complexity of biological events happening within tissue. The growth of spatial-omics is giving access to transcriptomic, proteomic and metabolomic data in a single tissue. At AstraZeneca, we're integrating those data with gold standard histological methods to generate a holistic understanding of drug action using Mass Spectrometry Imaging (MSI) and Imaging Mass Cytometry (IMC). The integration of both technologies is playing a pivotal role in providing pharmacokinetics, pharmacodynamics, safety and target engagement (TE) information, crucial for decision making.

NAMs are human-derived *in vitro* or *in silico* models developed to act as primary proxies for human biology. Examples of complex, self-organizing cellular models use such as organoids or micro-physiological systems (MPS) will be outlined to illustrate ways by which improved productivity helps implement the 3Rs and reduce our reliance on animal use.

Conflict of interest

The author is employed by AstraZeneca and holds shares at AstraZeneca.

Presentation: Oral

25

Towards porcine enteroid cultures for rotavirus studies

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Enteroids are 3D, polarized, *in vitro* models composed of multiple intestinal cell types that resemble the architecture and functionality of the native small intestine [1]. Among several research applications, they have been used to study enteric pathogens [2-4]. However, a practical issue with the 3D model is the access of the pathogen to the apical cell surface that faces the lumen of the enteroid.

To overcome this issue, we derived a 2D culture from the 3D model, that exposes the apical surface. Both 3D and 2D cultures efficiently grow in Mouse IntestiCult Medium™ supplemented with ROCK, TGF- β , p38 MAPK and sirtuin inhibitors. Immunofluorescence staining and RT-qPCR demonstrated that both 3D and 2D enteroids contain stem cells, enterocytes, enteroendocrine, goblet and Paneth cells. In addition, 3D enteroids, in complete medium, maintain the expression of all cell markers after 20 passages. Nevertheless, the depletion of specific supplements in 3D culture induces

changes in cell composition. 2D cultures need an addition of animal serum to be viable and grow efficiently. However, under these conditions, 2D enteroids contain fewer stem and epithelial cells than 3D. Finally, we tested the infectivity of a porcine rotavirus strain in 2D culture. RT-qPCR showed an increase of the virus titer after 24 h post-infection, confirming the successful replication of this strain.

In conclusion, we have established the conditions for the generation of 2 differentiated and polarized enteroid cultures that resemble the *in vivo* intestinal environment. These models will be used in future studies on the pathogenesis of porcine rotaviruses.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

26

Even beyond animal testing – Possibilities for an overall assessment of animal well-being

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Background: In laboratory animal science stressors are initially considered as the sum of all factors leading to deviations in the well-being of animals. Various severity assessments have been created for a large number of individual manipulations. However, when multiple harmful interventions or stressors occur simultaneously, the cumulative overall severity often leads to significant underestimation.

Methods: A comprehensive analysis was conducted on 20 legally mandated records of animal experiments from the years 2015-2023. This analysis involved daily examination of the effects of each experiment on the respective animals or groups of animals. The aim

was to identify significant stressors across various research domains.

Results: In order to visualize these cumulative occurring stressors, a scoring system was developed to estimate the overall stress loads within the context of an animal experiment. The developed scoring system is based on four different aspects, namely the definition of the (1) highest individual stress load, the assessment of (2) parallel and (3) serial individual stress loads and the consideration of a (4) baseline load. From these four different aspects, a cumulative overall stress load can then be determined through point allocation even daily or at previously identified highly critical control points.

Discussion: This scoring system is highly effective in objectively depicting cumulative stress load and covert burden. It is crucial that it is optimized for the respective situation and that care is taken to ensure that the point allocation is coherent and tailored to the specific testing project or situation.

Conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest.

Presentation: Oral

27

Establishing a lentiviral reporter platform for screening 3D human lung organoids: A proof-of-concept approach

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Over the last decade, research efforts towards developing sustainable human models have been undertaken to increase the likelihood of success of new drugs taken into clinical trial phase, while circumventing animal experimentation.

In line with this goal, we developed a lentiviral reporter system to tackle differentiation, mucus production, senescence and drug screening in human-derived organoids. We designed fluorescently-labelled lentiviruses targeting gene promoters related to ciliation and mucus production, which were used to transduce apical-

out organoids. Whilst developing, organoids were stimulated with cytokines, bacterial proteins and inhibitors, to test the reproducibility of the lentiviral system to accurately mimic cell and tissue physiology.

Our results reveal an increase in the promoter gene expression of markers for ciliated cells and mucus producing cells over time. Stimulation with IL-13 significantly impairs ciliated gene expression, while pre-treatment with JAK-STAT inhibitors rescues this phenotype. Flagellin and IL-1 β significantly increase the expression of genes related to mucus production, while NTHi infection stimulates IL-8 expression which, in turn, is alleviated by treatment with a bacterial natural compound.

We believe that our system represents a robust tool to for high-throughput screening of drugs and novel compounds in lung organoids. Additionally, the versatility of lentiviral manipulation means that our model might have broader applications beyond the human lung and can be established for other organs and disease models.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

28

Advancement of human osteoarthritic cartilage-on-a-chip models by integration of glucose and lactate biosensors for monitoring of disease-related shifts in cell metabolism

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Microphysiological cartilage models provide excellent opportunities for animal-free modelling of joint pathologies, including osteoarthritis. They are currently limited by their inability to facilitate real-time measurements of disease progression markers. Here, we present glucose and lactate biosensors integrated in a human cartilage-on-a-chip system for *in situ* detection of disease-related shifts in chondrocyte metabolism. We optimized glucose and lactate oxidase-based third generation biosensors to ensure signal stability and wide dynamic range, validated their signal against com-

mercial luminescence-based assays, confirmed signal specificity, reversibility, and repeatability and excluded signal interference by cell culture media components. We measured target analyte levels in healthy cartilage organoids and those inflamed by treatment with IL-1 β and TNF- α to mimic the osteoarthritic cartilage environment. The chip-integrated biosensors detected decreased glucose (2.2-fold signal decrease) and increased lactate (8.9-fold signal increase) levels in cell-laden organoids, compared to cell-free controls, showing feasibility of *in situ* metabolic monitoring with the proposed system. Long-term measurements indicated enhanced glucose-to-lactate metabolism in chemically inflamed compared to untreated cartilage-on-a-chip. This was confirmed by measuring 1.7-fold decreased glucose and 5.1-fold increased lactate content in cell culture supernatants after 2 weeks of culture and 1.5-fold glucose decrease and 1.9-fold lactate increase in cell culture supernatants from inflamed *versus* non-inflamed tissues. In conclusion, this study demonstrates proof-of-concept of glucose and lactate biosensors integrated in disease-relevant microphysiological cartilage models that enable real-time monitoring of inflammatory processes. Integration of biosensors in tissue-mimetic *in vitro* models will advance lab-on-a-chip technologies and contribute to gaining a clearer time-resolved understanding of physiological and pathological processes.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

29

Establishing a culture of care environment through knowledge exchange – A project to increase mutual understanding leading to better results in health and research

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Mental health and compassion fatigue (CF) are significant concerns in animal facilities (AF), particularly affecting non-research personnel such as animal caretaking professionals (ACP). Studies show that 9 out of 10 ACPs experience CF during their careers, intensified by the increasing digitalization of work environments. This often results in work orders being issued without direct com-

munication with caretakers. Our project aimed to identify the drivers of CF and explore solutions for integration into daily operations within AFs.

We conducted surveys and organized events to understand the challenges faced by various workgroups across different AF levels. The surveys revealed that ACPs desire acknowledgment of their expertise, more detailed information on experiments and breeding schemes, enhanced feedback, and improved communication about research outcomes. A workshop was held to discuss CF issues and identify the psychological strains affecting AF workers, highlighting that the lack of interaction, intensified by digital processes, significantly contributes to CF. Particularly stressful for ACPs are large animal sacrifice orders from researchers.

Acknowledging these challenges, we initiated a pilot program addressing CF for new users of the mouse facility. This aimed to decrease large sacrifice orders and reduce the number of surplus animals. Our findings suggest a growing disconnect between AF users and operators, exacerbated by digital barriers. Moving forward, we plan to facilitate regular in-person meetings involving all AF stakeholders to better address these issues and improve overall conditions in animal facilities.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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3D human vascular-on-a-chip: Method development for the biological assessment of endothelial dysfunction and monocytes migration

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Background and objectives: To date, atherosclerosis has typically been investigated using animal models due to the complex etiology of atherogenesis. Nowadays, advancements in *in vitro* culturing techniques enable us to investigate more complex biological interactions under biomimetic conditions. In this study, we established a method for evaluating monocyte migration, a key event in atherosclerosis, using a Vascular-on-a-Chip (VoC) model that mimics the human vascular microenvironment and takes into consideration immune system interactions.

Material and methods: Test samples were prepared by exposing M1 macrophages, differentiated from THP-1 cells, to lipopolysaccharide (LPS) and particle phase extracts of 1R6F reference cigarette smoke for 1 hour, followed by incubation in fresh medium for 3 hours. VoC were prepared by cultivating human coronary artery endothelial cells (HCAECs) in OrganoPlate 3-lane 40[®] (MIMETAS B.V.). VoC were exposed to test samples for 24 hours. Trans-epithelial electrical resistance (TEER), monocyte adhesion to HCAECs and monocyte migration into extra cellular matrix were measured.

Result and discussion: The VoC model presented here allows assessment of the effects of pro-inflammatory substances, acting through immune cells, on TEER, monocyte adhesion and migration, which are all important biological processes in atherogenesis. TEER, monocyte adhesion, and migration showed good correlations, regardless of exposed substances, and results were in line with *in vivo* data. There is still scope to improve the inter-experiment variability of the model, especially for tobacco product-derived exposures. We believe this VoC method could be a useful additional tool to analyze contributions of pro-inflammatory immune response in atherogenesis *in vitro*.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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In vitro patient-derived tumor models – Innovative 3D bioprinted long-term tissue cultures to test drug sensitivity

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Developing tumor models, including patient-derived ones, is essential for basic research and personalized therapies. Regarding the limitations, these patient-derived cultures and animal experiments are only used in a few exceptional cases for research applications. Additionally, standardization would be necessary in applying 3D bioprinted tests before starting their wide-range use. Accordingly, we aim to develop 3D bioprinting technology in personalized or preclinical drug selection. In our work, various treatments have been analyzed using traditional 2D, 3D cultures, newly created 3D bioprinted and *in vivo* models derived from breast cancer cell line and patient-derived human ovarian carcinomas.

We optimized the cell isolation protocol from 4T1 allograft and patients' samples. The freshly isolated tumor cells containing alginate-based bioink were used in 3D bioprinting to study the long-term development of cancer tissue-like structures *in vitro*. Moreover, drug sensitivity and protein expression profiles of the different cultures and *in vivo* growing cells were also compared.

Based on characteristic morphology and drug response, 3D bioprinted cultures had the highest similarity to the original *in vivo* growing tumors versus any other patient-derived models. Moreover, the 3D bioprinted tumors could mimic the drug response better than the traditional SCID xenograft model.

This research demonstrates the potential of 3D bioprinted models in drug screening, providing more efficient *in vitro* drug testing in future tumor models, especially for personalized applications. Based on our results, integrating 3D bioprinted models into drug testing could significantly reduce the number of animal experiments and improve drug pre-screening before clinical trials.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Presentation: Poster

33

Lockbox enrichment – Manipulative and cognitive activities for laboratory mice

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Conventional housing conditions often do not allow laboratory mice to fully express their behavioral repertoire, including manipulative and cognitive behaviors, because of a lack of complexity and diversity of stimuli. Therefore, we developed mechanical puzzles, so-called lockboxes, which are filled with food rewards and presented to the mice in their home cage.

The effects of the lockbox enrichment (LE) on the phenotype and the affective state of mice were investigated and compared with conventional housing conditions (CH) and super environmental enrichment (SEE). Young adult female C57BL/6JCrI mice were examined before and after a 2-month phase during which they had access to group-specific enrichment.

The study results suggested that LE reduced trait anxiety compared to CH. Neither CH, SEE nor LE influenced state anxiety and physiological variables such as body weight, resting metabolic rate, stress hormone metabolites concentrations, and adrenal gland weights. LE improved the sequential problem-solving ability compared to SEE when novel lockboxes were presented to the animals. While the relative variability increased over time for most variables regardless of housing conditions, it decreased for some variables, especially after LE. No evidence of toxicopathological effects of the LE material (Polylactic acid for 3D printing) was found.

In summary, LE improved the affective state and the ability of mice to solve sequential problems without affecting other variables. Neither LE nor SEE increased relative variability compared to CH.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

35

SMAFIRA – Finding the needle in a haystack

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Searching literature databases for alternatives to animal experiments is a very time-consuming work. In Europe, such a literature search is the prerequisite for conducting animal experiments. For biomedical research PubMed® is the most prominent database as it is freely available and comprises more than 37 million citations. For the specific search for alternative methods in PubMed® MeSH terms like “animal testing alternatives” can be used, but often do not entail sufficient results [1].

Thus, we have developed SMAFIRA, a freely accessible online tool to simplify the screening of (un-)curated abstracts in PubMed®. SMAFIRA employs state-of-the-art computer linguistic methods based on machine learning [2]. The tool aims to alleviate the search for possible alternative methods of a specific reference document describing best the animal method to be replaced. The search uses

the similar articles that PubMed® publishes for the specific reference document. These similar articles are re-ranked by SMAFIRA according to their relevance for the research question. Abstracts and methods mentioned therein are assigned to different categories such as *in vivo*, *organs* or *primary cells*. The result of a SMAFIRA search is a hit list of up to 200 manuscripts that represent a possible alternative method to the reference document.

The tool is designed to essentially reduce the time required to screen the biomedical literature for candidate alternative methods. However, it does not exempt scientists from checking the citations if their research question in mind can be evaluated with one of the proposed alternative methods.

SMAFIRA is accessible at <https://smafira.bf3r.de>.

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Conflict of interest

The authors have not interests to declare.

Presentation: Oral

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From flat to 3D bioprinted cell cultures: Revolutionizing breast cancer studies

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The FDA and EMA's shared goal of phasing out animal testing urges a need for alternative methodologies in pharmaceutical pre-clinical research. *In vitro* models are increasingly favored, with 3D models gaining importance due to their precision and reproducibility, aiming to increase efficiency and reduce animal testing [1,2]. 3D bioprinted tissue-mimetic structures (TMSs) possess unique attributes requiring validation of analytical techniques. Our study aims to validate cell proliferation assays on TMSs, confirm tissue formation, and compare metabolic features and mTOR inhibitor sensitivity to 2D cultures.

Utilizing a 3D bioprinter (BioScaffolder 3.2), we established printing protocols for fluorescent T47D human breast cancer cells. Cell proliferation assays (Alamar Blue, Sulforhodamine B), sample preparation methods for analytical techniques (immunohistochemistry, Western Blot) were developed and validated. mTOR inhibitor

sensitivity and metabolic characterization studies were conducted using the former validated methods.

TMSs were maintained for 21 days, with tissue formation evident by day 7, confirmed through various assays and pathohistological analysis. Altered mTOR-pathway protein expression (elevated S6, mTOR, Rictor; reduced pS6, pAkt) and decreased mTOR activity (pS6/S6 and pAkt/Akt ratios) were observed in TMSs compared to 2D cultures. mTOR inhibitor sensitivity (rapamycin; ipatasertib) decreased in TMSs, correlating with the altered mTOR activity.

Our study underscores how tissue culture conditions influence metabolic characteristics, impacting *in vitro* study outcomes. Developing *in vitro* test systems that closely mimic *in situ* reactions is crucial for enhancing drug preselection and the success rates of clinical trials while saving time and reducing animal experiment requirements.

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Conflict of interest

All authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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Toward an expansive interpretation of the 3Rs across areas of animal use

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More than six decades since Russell and Burch formulated the 3Rs, the principles of replacement, reduction, and refinement have become mainstream guidelines for animal research, particularly in the areas of toxicology and biomedical science [1,2]. While there exists a growing literature of critique on the 3Rs, these principles may still offer the best avenue toward organizing good practices, if applied systematically and coherently [3]. They also represent a promising model for other domains of animal use, most importantly animal-based food production [4]. The 3Rs could be a suitable beacon for converging dynamics among public health, animal welfare, and environmental sustainability. However, in the efforts toward an expansive interpretation of the 3Rs, it is essential to address two major obstacles. On the one hand, taking the 3Rs beyond the area of animal research requires abandoning an “originalist” interpretation focused on technocratic application. On the other hand, regional differences in legislation and organization may pose specific impediments on the application of the 3Rs (e.g., comparing East Asia versus Europe) [5]. Both of these challenges with the 3Rs may

cause tension among different groups of stakeholders, which must be charted and analyzed carefully in order to foster cooperation. Here, we offer an initial analysis, aiming to identify potential issues or points of contention that could cause conflict among researchers, educators, policymakers, and the general public. The key goal should be to target the dynamical range of where interests overlap, so that the progressive expansion with the 3Rs leaves no one behind.

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Presentation: Oral

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Culture of care at Novo Nordisk, a pharmaceutical company – Caring for animals and people

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All establishments working with laboratory animals have a culture related to this work, but most are not aware of the elements of this culture before they start working with the concept of Culture of Care (CoC). When this work is started, it is likely to raise an awareness and a wish to be more active in the development, communication and implementation of their own, and unique culture.

At Novo Nordisk, our work with mapping and defining our culture has led us to the understanding that our approach to CoC is what we proactively choose to do when we put legislative requirements into action. We closely look into the intentions of the legal

requirements and from that, we choose the solutions which have the best match with the intentions. In other words, we go above and beyond the minimum requirements of legislation.

The CoC also includes the staff working with the animals, as they are the ones providing care to and showing empathy with the animals. They are also the ones to suggest refinements of scientific procedures, housing, caring, and enrichment in order to improve animal welfare.

Our purpose of working with CoC is to better enable us to reach our goals in relation to the welfare of the animals and of the people working with them. We will give examples (<https://norecopa.no/media/rfzjetbc/what-does-coc-look-like-at-novo-nordisk-a3-final-08-05-2023.pdf>) of CoC in the different phases of a study and how communication tools for improving animal welfare and 3Rs are implemented and why this is so important.

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The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Non-aversive handling of research animals at Novo Nordisk

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When working with research animals, it is common for these to undergo various husbandry and scientific procedures, such as weighing, blood sampling, drug administration, anesthesia, and analgesia. While some of these procedures themselves can cause discomfort, the act of handling, restraining or immobilizing the animals to perform the procedures can often cause more anxiety than the scientific procedures themselves.

At Novo Nordisk, we have implemented a program to socialize, habituate and train our animals to participate in these procedures, ensuring that they are comfortable, as little stressed as possible and cooperative; in other words, we try to work *with* the animals. We continuously strive to improve our non-aversive handling methods, such as using VAPs for multiple blood sampling, non-invasive analgesia, gentle fixation and allowing the animals to move freely out of their cages during cleaning.

During the presentation, we will demonstrate a wide range of non-aversive handling techniques throughout the animals' lifecycle, from everyday care to scientific procedures and euthanasia.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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In vitro ion-channel dependent neurotoxicity evaluation using a series of ion-channel stable overexpression cells

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The ion channel is a key membrane protein and is related to multiple diseases such as pain, itch, and neurotoxicity. While there is no standard *in vivo* and *in vitro* testing methods for ion-channel dependent toxicity testing. To overcome this issue, it is a possible approach to establish a series of ion-channel stable overexpression cells and develop certain biomarkers to evaluate ion-channel dependent toxicity.

Biodegeneration plastic is widely used in the catering industry and other related industries. Indeed, it is beneficial for the overall environment, while the migratable substances like toluene diisocyanate and tin organic compounds already showed irritation, immune inhibition, and central nervous system toxicity. Studies have confirmed that the main reason for these adverse effects are highly active ion channel.

Therefore, we constructed a cellular model with stable expression of a series of ion channels including the sodium ion channel (SCN9A, SCN10A), the calcium ion channel (TRPV1, TRPV4, TRPA1, TRPM8), the potassium ion channel (KCNB1). We carried out a combined test of ion channel toxicity (mainly focused on cell viability) against isocyanate compounds and organotin substances that may be present in degraded plastics to confirm if these chemicals are ion channel selectively. Based on these results, we further establish a high-throughput ion channel toxicity screening model including cell viability testing and ion channel activity testing, by which to screen whether the testing items showed ion-channel dependent toxicity.

Study funding: National Key R&D Program of China (2022YFF0606703).

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Presentation: Poster

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***In vitro* tissue culture-based efficacy testing method for cosmetics**

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Nowadays, a number of alternative methods have been included in the *Safety and Technical Standards for Cosmetics 2015*. In addition, a number of OECD-validated alternative methods are being synchronized for research, validation and transformation in China. In modern alternative methods, the application of integrated alternative testing approach with adverse outcome pathway evaluation techniques, stem cell evaluation techniques, histological analysis and evaluation techniques, and tissue engineering evaluation tech-

niques have made the alternative methods more diversified and in line with the overall physiological and pathological processes of human body.

Based on the tissue engineering evaluation technology, Guangzhou Chn-alternative Biotechnology Co. Ltd. established a model of isolated hair follicle to evaluate hair growth promotion efficacy of haircare cosmetics and related cosmetic ingredients, in which the apparent morphology (length of hair growth) and hair growth factor VEGF were used as the indicators of the efficacy of hair growth promotion. Numerous experiments have verified that the model has been validated in a number of experiments to be extremely beneficial for the development of alternative methods of hair growth promotion.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Optimizing endpoints for crystalline quartz silica exposure in a lung co-culture model

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In addressing the challenge of aligning *in vitro* lung models with *in vivo* responses, researchers increasingly use *in vitro* to *in vivo* extrapolation (IVIVE) to identify valid endpoints. This approach aims to ensure that selected endpoints accurately reflect the *in vivo* outcomes and meet the necessary criteria for assessment in both *in vitro* and *in vivo* models. In this study, we conduct a comparative

analysis of *in vitro* and *in vivo* pulmonary models for inhalation toxicity after exposure to crystalline quartz silica particles (DQ₁₂). Starting from acute, 24-hour exposure employed *in vitro*, we extended the investigation of inflammatory endpoints to 7 days of exposure to match the timeline employed in the *in vivo* model suggested by the OECD Test 413 for inhalation toxicity testing. We utilized an *in vitro* co-culture model consisting of the human bronchial cell line Calu-3 and human monocyte-derived macrophages exposed to DQ₁₂ particles. We did not observe enhanced cytotoxicity 7 days after exposure. However, we observed increased IL-1 β , IL-6, and IL-8 release, measured on both protein and gene levels. The results were compared to those of the *in vivo* rat model. We identified a significant correlation in interleukin IL-8 and IL-1 β gene expression across both systems. Our study showcases the validity of *in vitro* models to assess inflammation and the importance of using longer exposure durations in assessing lung inflammation upon exposure to particles. These findings suggest the potential to replicate certain aspects of *in vivo* responses and reduce the necessity for animal testing.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Novel microfluidic prostate-cancer model: A tool to a study microRNA secretion and their potential as diagnostic biomarkers

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Prostate cancer (PCa) research often relies on cell lines lacking crucial physiological features. Microphysiological systems (MPS) offer a promising solution by replicating cancer microenvironments more accurately. This study aimed to construct an MPS model using conventional PCa cell lines (LNCaP and PC3) and assess their behavior under dynamic culture conditions. The TissUse Humimic platform was used to model the 3D PCa environment with microfluidic culture. Both LNCaP and PC3 cells were cultured in conventional and 3D environments, under static and dynamic condi-

tions. Agar-collagen hydrogels were optimized to support PCa cell secretions and tolerate cyclic perfusion in the MPS model. Evaluation criteria included cell morphology, prostate-specific antigen secretion (PSA), and expression of key prostate markers and microRNAs. In 3D and MPS cultures, LNCaP cells formed spheroids and upregulated cytokeratins and adhesion proteins. They also exhibited sustained PSA secretion in the MPS. PC3 cells showed limited structural development in 3D and MPS cultures, with differential PSA expression. MicroRNA expression analysis revealed upregulation of certain microRNAs in LNCaP-MPS (miR-4417, miR-3687), indicating dynamic culture induced significant phenotypic changes. Conversely, PC3 cells maintained consistent microRNA expression across conditions. Extracellular expression of certain microRNAs decreased in both cell lines under MPS conditions. These findings reveal that MPS can mimic PCa pathophysiology and highlight the sensitivity of microRNA to external stimuli, demonstrating the utility of PCa-MPS in studying microRNA secretion, an underexplored aspect with potential for discovering diagnostic biomarkers.

Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Investigating the systemic distribution of implant wear products *in ovo* using the hen's egg as a model

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The use of endoprosthesis in arthroplasty is a common method to restore mobility and quality of life. Components of orthopaedic implants frequently use alloys that contain Cobalt (Co), Chromium (Cr) and Molybdenum (Mo). Due to corrosion and abrasive wear, micro- and nanoscale particles as well as Co ions are released [1]. While the local distribution of wear products and resulting tissue reactions are well described, little is known about their systemic distribution and possible effects [2]. Animal models are considered the gold standard in implant material testing, yet the discussion about alternatives to established models is ongoing due to scientific and ethical reasons [3,4]. The Hen's egg might pose a suitable alternative and is also recommended by the EU Reference Laboratory for alternatives to animal testing (URL ECVAM) [5]. In the present study we investigated the systemic distribution of Co ions within chicken embryos as a model for vertebrate organisms. In

a first step, the model was established in terms of exposure route and injection procedure. Next, the distribution of Co within organs and tissues of the embryo was investigated by Inductively Coupled Plasma – Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS) and spatially resolved synchrotron-based X-Ray fluorescence (SR- μ XRF). It was found that cobalt accumulates in specific organs of the chicken embryo including the central nervous system (CNS), heart and liver. Our data indicate specific distribution of systemic available Co ions. Accumulation into the heart and CNS have been confirmed and are of high relevance for clinical practice.

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Presentation: Poster

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Investigating pathological mechanical strain in ligament disease

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Inflammatory conditions like desmopathy can severely impact the anterior cruciate ligament, contributing to fibrosis and arthritis. A major challenge has been the lack of representative 2D *in vitro* models mimicking inflammatory processes and dynamic mechanical strain, crucial for ligament homeostasis. Physiological levels of strain have been shown to exert anti-inflammatory effects, while excessive strain can promote inflammation. Adhering to the 3Rs (replacement, reduction and refinement) of animal research, this study aims to create a more realistic dynamic *in vitro* environment by combining a flexcell culture system with primary

human ligamentocytes for studying inflammatory ligament diseases. Primary ligamentocytes from 4 patients (ages 59-81) were cultured in DMEM with human platelet lysate (hPL), IL-1 β (1 ng/mL) to induce inflammation, or TGF- β 3 for immunomodulation. Cells were strained at 0.5Hz for 48 hours at 10% (normal) and 21% (supra) elongation, then imaged and analyzed by RT-qPCR. Cells oriented along the force axis under strain. Without treatment, 21% strain increased COL1A1 and IL6 expression. With IL-1 β , any strain markedly decreased COL3A1. Interestingly, PIEZO1 expression increased substantially with 10% and 21% strain compared to static controls in inflammatory conditions. PIEZO1 also increased with 21% strain in TGF- β 3 and combined IL-1 β +TGF- β 3 cultures versus normal strain. In conclusion, the findings underscore the pivotal role of the mechanoreceptor PIEZO1 in regulating cellular responses to mechanical overstrain in ligamentocytes, emphasizing the importance of incorporating dynamic strain into *in vitro* models of inflammatory ligament diseases.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation:Poster

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Innovative therapy of influenza and respiratory infections caused by viruses through the use of siRNAs (short interfering RNAs)

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Influenza A viruses are a potential danger to human health due to viral recombination phenomena and the frequent appearance of pandemic biotypes. The aim of this study is to propose new molecules that can be an alternative to vaccination plans and, in this perspective, RNA interference (RNAi) play a key role: this regulation mechanism of gene expression is addressed by small dsRNA molecules triggered by the administration of exogenous siRNAs. In this work, a siRNA pool was generated in *Escherichia coli* using the filed carrier pBAD-6xHis-p19-NP. The operating principle of the vector is linked to the ability to produce the NP gene target and the p19 protein, capable of sequestering siRNAs: after the expression of both transcriptional units, endogenous ribonuclease III cuts the NP-related sequence into small dsRNA fragments, which are sequestered by the p19 protein and purified. The cell line used for

the transfection was Madin Darby Canine Kidney (MDCK, code BS CL 64). Transfection was performed by the reverse-transfection protocol, using Lipofectamine 2000 (Life Technologies) and BLOCK-iT™ Fluorescent Oligo (ThermoFisher Scientific) as a positive transfection control. The influenza biotype used for the viral infection was: A/swine/Italy/1513-1/1998 H1N1 (VIR RE RSCIC 187). The resistance of the transfected cells to infection with increasing dilutions of the viral biotype was evaluated by observing the CPE and the results were compared with real-time PCR assays to detect the presence of non-degraded virus. The results showed a positive effect of siRNA treatment and a significant effect of siRNAs on viral replication.

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The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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Regulatory advances in China alternative toxicology methods

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The recent regulatory developments in China have significantly altered the landscape of toxicological research, with a particular emphasis on the adoption and development of alternative methods to animal testing. The Regulation of Supervision and Administration of Cosmetics has improved the mechanisms for risk monitoring of cosmetics, establishing a robust framework for safety assessments that prioritizes consumer health and proactive risk management. Furthermore, the Regulation actively promotes scientific innovation, in particular in the development of new cosmetic materials

and the use of *in vitro* testing methods. It supports the transition to non-animal testing methods by integrating advanced computational models and biological assays that meet international cruelty-free standards and address both efficacy and safety. Prior to this regulation, the Shanghai Society of Toxicology has made considerable efforts to promote the use of alternative methods. These efforts have included the organization of numerous toxicology public interest forums, which have attracted over 5,000 participants and 100 companies in total. Additionally, the society has played a pivotal role in the organization of numerous standards projects for alternative methods, multi-center validation and the publication and release of related standards, thereby making a significant contribution to the application of alternative methods in the cosmetic industry. It is encouraging to observe that, as a result of collective efforts, regulatory authorities are also becoming more receptive to the use of alternative methods in China.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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An *in vitro* method for anti-hair loss efficacy testing

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Androgenetic alopecia is the most prevalent form of hair loss observed in clinical practice, with a high prevalence rate and a tendency to manifest in younger individuals, resulting in significant disruption to patients' lives and psychological distress. Minoxidil and finasteride are the principal pharmaceutical agents employed in the clinical management of androgenetic alopecia. Nevertheless, the use of these drugs is not without adverse effects, including itching, irritant dermatitis and sexual dysfunction.

The cells selected for the experiment were human dermal hair papilla cells (DPCs) and human hair follicle stem cells (HFSCs). The MTT assay was employed to ascertain the viability of the cells

in different administration states and to identify the optimal concentration for administration.

The cells were seeded in 6-well plates at a specified density in order to establish a model of male decidualisation induced by dihydrotestosterone as a stimulant. The negative control group was established using maintenance medium, the model group was modelled using dihydrotestosterone, the positive control group was modelled with dihydrotestosterone followed by the administration of minoxidil or finasteride, and the test article was modelled with different dihydrotestosterone concentrations using the addition of samples to be tested.

Following administration, the levels of β -galactosidase and ROS, which are indicative of the process of ageing, were quantified in accordance with the instructions provided in the kit. The expression levels of IL-6, FGF7, FGF10, PDGFA, PDGFR- β , VEGF and ALP were quantified by RT-qPCR, while the expression levels of p16, p21, p53 and Bax were determined by Western blotting.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation:Poster

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An *in vitro* method for anti-glycation efficacy in cosmetics

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The causes of skin ageing can be classified as endogenous or exogenous. Exogenous causes are mainly related to ultraviolet radiation, whereas endogenous causes are unavoidable physiological changes that occur over time. Recent studies have shown that endogenous ageing is closely related to the glycation reaction in the skin. Glycation is a non-enzymatic reaction between nucleic acids, proteins and lipids and sugars, resulting in the production of stable and irreversible products known as advanced glycosylation end prod-

ucts. AGEs bind to the receptor of advanced glycation end products (RAGE), activating nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate (NADPH) to generate oxygen free radicals (ROS). This leads to changes in the structure and function of the skin, manifesting as a decrease in the proliferative capacity of cells, thinning of the skin and a decrease in skin elasticity. Carboxymethyl lysine (CML) is a structural form of AGEs. The lower the content of CML, the more significant the anti-glycation effect of the sample.

In this experiment, normal human dermal fibroblasts (NHDF) were treated with methylglyoxal (MGO) for glycation modelling. The anti-glycation effect of the samples to be tested was assessed by immunofluorescence assay to detect the fluorescence intensity of CML.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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Monocyte activation test (MAT) as potential assay for quality control of veterinary autogenous vaccines: Preliminary data

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Veterinary vaccines play an important role in control/prevention of animal diseases, furthermore, autogenous vaccines (AVs) are an efficient tool against antibiotic resistance. AVs, as all injectable products, undergo quality controls (QCs) to ensure safety/efficacy.

The acceptance of the 3Rs principle (replacement, reduction, refinement) is leading to the application of *in vitro* methods in several investigations. Monocyte activation test (MAT) is an alternative to animal-based methods and allows the detection of both endotoxic/non-endotoxic pyrogens in injectable pharmaceutical products and can be performed on immortalized murine monocyte-macrophage cell line and/or cryopreserved PBMCs. The inflammatory process can be assessed through IL-6 cytokine release. Among the pro-inflammatory interleukins, this biomarker has been found to be statis-

tically significant [1]. In this work we described the first application of MAT for AVs as a QC test.

Raw 264.7 murine macrophage cells were incubated with Gram-positive/viral vaccines at two dilutions. After 24 hours, culture supernatants were tested with IL-6 ELISA kit (Sigma-Aldrich) to assess the cytokine concentration released.

All vaccines dilutions showed the increased of IL-6 levels ranging from 0.119 pg/mL for Ovine Mastitis diluted at 1:250 to 146.8 pg/mL for Lattococcosis 1:250, compared to the not stimulated control.

These preliminary results, together with those previously obtained with *in vitro* MTS assay [2] are necessary to relate the *in vitro* results to lab animals evidence. The final perspective is the standardization of protocols and the application of validated alternative test.

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Conflict of interest

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Presentation: Poster

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Coculture of Jurkat and THP-1 cell lines as a model for the evaluation of immunosuppressive properties of chemicals

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The immunosuppressive effects of chemicals, including environmental pollutants, are traditionally assessed by *in vivo* tests on rodents or by a whole blood cytokine release assay (WBCRA). In the latter, blood from donors is activated *ex vivo* and the cytokines, mainly released by monocytes and lymphocytes, are subsequently measured. With the aim of developing an *in vitro* method to assess immunosuppressive effects without *ex vivo* blood or animals, we have established a coculture of cell lines resembling lymphocytes and monocytes (Jurkat and THP-1). The viability of the coculture was confirmed and its optimal activation was achieved by a 24-hour

stimulation with a cocktail of 10 ng/mL lipopolysaccharide, 1 μ M ionomycin and 50 nM phorbol-myristate-acetate. To assess the effects of chemicals, the coculture was pretreated with compounds for two hours prior to stimulation, after which IL-8, TNF α and IL-2 in the coculture supernatants were measured by ELISA.

Initially, a series of immunosuppressants with different mechanisms of action were tested and the released cytokines were measured. The decrease in IL-8 provided the most reliable results and was therefore selected as a marker for immunosuppression. The threshold for a positive assessment was set at < 30% of IL-8 compared to the vehicle control.

Using this model, we have so far been able to demonstrate the immunosuppressive effects of glucocorticoids and inhibitors of mTOR, calcineurin phosphatases, MPO and NF- κ B signaling pathways. In addition, the investigation of various environmentally occurring bisphenols and PFAS showed that some of them act as potent immunosuppressants.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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Targeting mitochondrial defects in a 3D-bioprinted LCHADD/VLCADD model

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Background: 3D bioprinting technologies are revolutionizing tissue engineering, especially in studying metabolic processes using patient-derived cells. Long-chain-3-hydroxy-acyl-CoA-dehydrogenase-deficiency (LCHADD) and Very-long-chain-acyl-CoA-dehydrogenase-deficiency (VLCADD) are rare disorders of the oxidation of long-chain fatty acids (LC-FA). Therapy mainly involves a diet restricted in LC-FA, supplement substitution, and fasting avoidance. Innovative strategies are needed to reduce mortality and improve quality of life.

Methods: The study examines mitochondrial rearrangement in β -oxidation-defective fibroblasts by exposing them to various rescuers in 2D. Mitochondrial morphology was analyzed using live cell fluorescence microscopy and quantified by counting the number of branches and dots. To mimic tissue physiology, a 3D-bioprinted, vascularized tissue model with healthy and patient-derived fibroblasts was developed.

Findings: Analysis of mitochondrial morphology in patient fibroblasts revealed significant alterations of mitochondrial morphology, reduced oxidative phosphorylation, but increased glycolysis and significantly increased intracellular ROS levels caused by NOX2. NOX2 inhibitors and other rescuers led to mitochondrial network refusion. 3D-bioprinted tissue surrogates showed impaired vessel formation in the presence of patient fibroblasts.

Interpretation: Our findings will improve the understanding and therapy of LCHADD/VLCADD, as there are no direct therapies for elevated ROS levels and mitochondrial dysfunction. 3D-bioprinted patient tissue models will be used for testing novel treatment modalities and tissue response during physiologic stress.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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The effect of clicker training on the acute physiological stress response in C57BL/6J mice

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The objective of this study is to investigate the effect of clicker training and laboratory procedures on the acute physiological stress response caused by injection stress and short periods of restraint stress in female C57BL/6J mice. Using indices of stress such as elevated levels of corticosterone and immune parameters. Experimental procedures such as blood sampling, injections, or restraint cause stress to the animals. Acute stress decreases blood leukocyte subpopulations. Even responses within the normal adaptive range

could influence experimental outcomes. Previous research determined an impact of gentle handling on the well-being of laboratory mice. Our aim is to develop a clicker training protocol to prepare the animals to laboratory routines to minimize acute stress.

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Presentation: Poster

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Induced pluripotent stem cell (iPSC)-derived hepatocyte-like cells: An essential tool for disease modelling and toxicity tests

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Functional hepatocytes are essential for assessing drug and toxin metabolism and to test novel drugs for hepatic diseases. The current gold standards are animal models or isolated human primary hepatocytes (PHH). Both systems are not only associated with significant ethical concerns but are limited in their ability to predict toxicity and drug activity either because of species differences or because of culture-induced dedifferentiation. To overcome these limitations, hepatocyte-like cells (HLCs) generated *in vitro* from human induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) are a promising novel tool.

Using urine derived renal progenitor cells (UdRPCs) as a source, we can collect material from patients of all ages and diseases, which allows us to model not only common conditions such as non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) but also rare diseases like alpha-1-antitrypsin deficiency (AATD). Our novel improved HLC differentiation protocol enhances expression of the essential hepatic transcription factor farnesoid X receptor (FXR) by employing forskolin in the final differentiation step [1]. Basal cytochrome P450 (CYP) 3A4 activity is increased by 5-fold and can be induced 1.5-fold further with rifampicin. Similarly, the addition of forskolin increases CYP2D6 activity up to 6-fold. HLCs derived with this novel protocol reproduce the essential hallmarks of NAFLD and AATD, namely lipid droplet incorporation and accumulation of polymeric alpha-1-antitrypsin (AAT). They show beneficial responses to drugs such as vildagliptin for NAFLD and carbamazepine (CBZ), SAHA, kifunensine (KIF), or cysteamine (CYS) for AATD and have the potential to be employed in toxicity assays to reduce animal experiments in this field.

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Presentation: Oral

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Development of a microfluidic perfusion bioreactor that enables culture of multiple 3D bone models under mechanical loading

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While *in vitro* cell-culture techniques have proven to be extremely valuable in the context of bone biology and disease, these methods neglect important physiochemical parameters such as mechanical forces and oxygen saturation, both crucial for proper cell function [1,2]. In this regard, microphysiological bioreactors, also referred to as organ-on-a-chip, provide a suitable solution since they allow control over tissue-specific parameters [3]. These model systems do not mimic an organ or tissue in its entire complexity but rather include aspects thereof that are most relevant for the research question addressed. In the context of bone, organ-on-a-chip technology can be utilized to investigate the biocompatibility of implant materials and explore physiological and pathological processes. For example, a commercial system has been employed to reproduce the accumulation of Chromium, that can originate from endoprosthesis wear, into peri-implant bone trabeculae [4]. In another study a cus-

tomized platform was used that allows for monitoring and control of tissue parameters specific for bone, thus providing valuable insights into the interplay of mechanical loading and oxygen saturation in regard to bone formation [5]. Building on past experience with these systems, this project aims to develop a microphysiological bioreactor system which allows for the application of mechanical forces that are adequate for loading matured bone. The overall goal is to create a microphysiological system that allows for the culture of 3D bone models under relevant physiological conditions, while keeping demands on infrastructure and training as low as possible.

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The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Non-invasive monitoring of three-dimensional tumor spheroids using electrical impedance spectroscopy

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In the scope of the 3R principle, this project aims to develop a bio-electronic platform as a preclinical test system for animal-free and non-invasive personalized cancer therapies. Three-dimensional (3D) cell cultures are an important tool for reduction of animal experimentation and mimicking tissues *in-vivo*.

To enable a non-invasive technique to observe tumor behavior, Electrical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) can be employed. EIS may be performed by Two Electrode-Technique (2-ET), where both electrodes are used for excitation and recording purposes, or by Four Electrode-Technique (4-ET), where the two outer electrodes are used for current excitation, and the two inner electrodes record the resulting signal [1]. Here, we successfully used both techniques

to monitor tumor spheroids adhesion and evaluate the therapeutic interventions.

3D Tumor Spheroids (3D-TS; diameter $\sim 300 \mu\text{m}$) made of human colon cancer cells were cultured on a Microelectrode Array (MEA; pitch: $70 \mu\text{m}$). Control and drug treatment experiments ($N_{\text{control}} = 14$, $N_{\text{drug}} = 10$) were conducted using EIS to observe 3D-TS changes. Measurements were performed at three different time spots after interfacing the 3D-TS with the MEA.

EIS allows for reliable, noninvasive identification of adherent spheroids. The identification was confirmed using optical microscopy. With both techniques (2-ET and 4-ET), we obtained significantly higher impedance amplitudes for electrodes underneath the tumor spheroids than for bare electrodes. During the drug treatment, EIS revealed a decrease in the impedance over time compared to the control groups. In the future, this method may be used to interface and record tumor spheroids on flexible MEAs and perform T-cell immunotherapy.

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The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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In-depth proteomic profiles of hiPSC-derived early retinal organoids

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Neurodegenerative diseases of the retina, such as glaucoma, diabetic retinopathy, and age-related macular degeneration involve retinal cell death. Neuroprotection is an important goal for preventing and treating neurodegeneration. To this aim having reliable experimental models of retinal neuronal injury represent an important tool for developing novel therapeutic strategies and assessing the efficacy and adverse effects of symptomatic treatments.

Increasing evidence suggests human induced pluripotent stem cells (hiPSCs)-derived three-dimensional organoids as one of the most promising sources of human retinal cells for disease modeling and cell therapy [1,2]. Here we report an in-depth proteomic analysis of retinal organoids (ROs) on the 21st, 28th, and 35th day of the retinal differentiation protocol to define the most appropri-

ate timing to isolate the retinal ganglion cells (RGCs) [3]. Thus, RGCs were purified from differentiated RO-derived cells on the 28th and 35th day using selection based on CD90-positivity with a low-pressure FACS sorting method. Their phenotype was further investigated by specific markers evaluated with qPCR, mass spectrometry, and western blotting data [4]. However, mass spectrometry revealed other retina-associated phenotypes in the CD90-positive cells, including astrocytes, Müller Glia, oligodendrocytes, and photoreceptors. To conclude, the selection based solely on CD90 expression is insufficient to isolate highly enriched RGCs. Nevertheless, these other cells may be the key to the development and survival of RGCs themselves. Further investigation is needed to standardize the methodology used.

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Presentation: Poster

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Governance for ensuring replacement at Novo Nordisk, a global pharmaceutical company

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Novo Nordisk is a global pharmaceutical company with *in-vivo* research sites in China, Denmark, and the US, focusing on research areas such as diabetes, obesity, and related comorbidities like cardiovascular, liver, and kidney diseases. The company has set an internal goal to significantly reduce the use of research animals used per project, aligning with external expectations from politicians, NGOs, and society to replace animal research where scientifically feasible.

To achieve this, Novo Nordisk has established an internal governance structure for early project phases, aiming at challenging the scientific justifications for new projects. This includes addressing the question: “Can this project be conducted without the use of laboratory animals?” The governance process includes evaluating and scoring the project’s human disease relevance, utilizing bioinformatics, cohort lookup, human genetics and clinical data. To ensure a disease-relevant readout in a credible human *ex vivo/in vitro* model system there is specific emphasis on ascertaining if non-animal methods can be deployed.

The application of this governance structure is driving compliance with legal requirements for Replacement by reducing the number of projects involving laboratory animals to a minimal fraction.

The presentation will also address how a similar governance structure can be implemented throughout the entire preclinical research organization.

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The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Transforming culture: Culture of care in animal research focusing communication

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Background: A majority of current debates in animal research focus to a large extent on the significance and implementation of the 3R principle according to Russell and Burch. In this context, the concept of the Culture of Care has come into focus in recent years. Culture of Care describes a transformation of existing routines and procedures that are characterised towards dialogical processes of negotiation and reconceptualization at all levels involved.

Methods: The aim of this qualitative survey research was to analyse people's perceptions and understanding of Culture of Care. Using explorative expert interviews, aspects of a Culture of care in different groups (management level, scientific level, supervisory level, care level) were analyzed. A total of 14 experts in animal-based research were interviewed at four levels: Management, science, supervisory and care level. All interviews conducted were transcribed and analysed with the help of Grounded Theory.

Results: The results of the qualitative interviews show a differentiated picture. Overall, communication is described good. A differentiated look shows a higher diversity. Blocked communication or just informing communication processes in meetings are described. Especially the management level describes the necessity of open communication.

Conclusions: The present survey approached the understanding of the culture of care among experts in the field of animal-based research with a focus on communication. The results offer the possibility to address CoC as a process to change 3R education within the lab animal training. Another aspect of improve communication is coaching and supervision within individual institutions.

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Presentation: Oral

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Investigation of complex *in vitro* models using shotgun proteomics for the prediction of human-relevant data for anti-inflammatory drugs

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As a replacement for animal testing, novel cell culture models offer a promising opportunity for the assessment of safety and efficacy of drugs. Of particular interest in this context are co-culture models, which consist of several cell types and thus can make a precise prediction for human-relevant data. However, these models have often

not been fully characterized yet. Proteomic profiling of different cell culture models can help to elucidate the functional interaction and lead to an optimization of the models. Since macrophages in particular play an important role in the defense against pathogens in inflammation, monocyte-derived macrophages (MDM) can be used for co-culture models [1]. The basis of this work is a proteome study of LPS-stimulated MDM and MDM treated with anti-inflammatory drugs. Based on these results, investigations of a co-culture model of MDM and Caco-2 cells will be carried out, which can be used to test drugs against chronic inflammatory bowel diseases. Ultimately, with the help of a reliable and valid model, animal testing should be minimized in the future.

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Presentation: Poster

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Quadruple culture of primary human osteoblasts, osteocytes, osteoclasts and endothelial cells – An advanced 3D *in vitro* bone model

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With an ageing population worldwide, research into bone metabolism and novel therapies for damaged and diseased bone is essential. We have developed a 3D *in vitro* human bone model comprising the main bone cell species – osteoblasts, osteoclasts and osteocytes as well as endothelial cells, isolated from primary human tissue.

Osteoblasts were isolated from human femoral heads. Osteocytes were differentiated from osteoblasts in collagen gels and osteoclasts were differentiated from peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMC). Human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVEC) were seeded on top of osteoblasts. Quadruple cultures as transwell insert

constructs were conducted for 14 days, allowing simultaneous differentiation and separate analysis of osteocytes and osteoclasts as well as tube formation of HUVECs.

Morphology, gene expression and enzyme activities of the bone cell species like ALP for osteoblasts, TRAP for osteoclasts as well as CD31 for endothelial cells were detected, proving the successful differentiation of all involved cell species.

The external addition of cytokines such as macrophage colony-stimulating factor (MCSF) and receptor activator of nuclear factor- κ B ligand (RANKL) for the differentiation of multinucleated osteoclasts from PBMC is not necessary in the quadruple culture. Therefore, the model represents a physiologically relevant culture system and may help to study and understand the complex crosstalk between bone cells, their precursors and endothelial cells during remodelling and vascularisation of bone tissue. Moreover, it enables preclinical testing of bioactive factors, biomaterial extracts or drugs on the differentiation and behaviour of bone cells and endothelial cells, for translation into clinical practice without animal testing.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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HepG2 spheroids: A new testing approach for the determination of adverse effects of chemicals

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In accordance with the 3R (replacement, reduction, refinement) strategy proposed by EU REACH legislation, significant advances have been made in the development of alternative *in vitro* models to minimize *in vivo* animal testing. In genetic toxicology, a shift towards *in vitro* alternatives has emerged with the development of cell models based on hepatocellular carcinoma cell lines (e.g., HepG2, HepaRG). However, under traditional 2D culture conditions, these cells have limited predictive value for *in vivo* behavior. Conversely,

3D models (spheroids) exhibit enhanced liver-specific functions, higher stability, and prolonged cell viability. We aimed to develop a new approach for testing adverse outcomes caused by chemicals, based on HepG2 spheroids grown under static conditions. Three-day old spheroids were exposed to a carcinogen griseofulvin (GF; 2, 20, 200 μ M) for 24 and 96-hours and then evaluated for cell viability (MTS), cell cycle distribution (Hoechst 33258), proliferation (Ki67), DNA double strand break (gH2AX) induction and mitotic cell formation (pH3+), coupled with toxicogenomic analyses. Results showed that GF did not affect cell viability, but arrested cells in the G2/M phase. Proliferation increased after 24 h exposure however it decreased dose-dependently after 96 h. An increase in gH2AX-positive cells was observed after 24 h, and mitotic cell formation after 24 h and 96 h. Toxicogenomic data align with flow cytometry findings. To conclude, this study demonstrates the utility of HepG2 spheroid model in assessing the (geno)toxic effects of chemicals and is a step forward in applying the 3R strategy.

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Presentation: Poster

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Advanced allogeneic porous scaffolds for personalized xeno-free cell culture and tissue engineering

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Human platelet lysates (PL) play a well-known role in cell function and tissue repair. We recently reported a bioactive PL-derivative precursor (PLMA) that can be cured upon light exposure to form hydrogels with tunable mechanical properties able to support human-derived cells culture [1-3].

Animal-derived serum is widely used as supplement in cell culture, nevertheless, its use raises many safety, scientific, and ethical concerns [1,4]. Following a humanized and completely xeno-free strategy, we propose PL-sponges as a support for 3D cell culture in animal serum-free conditions [5].

To do so, a PLMA solution with photoinitiator was prepared and hydrogels were formed by light irradiation. Human protein-based sponges were then produced by freeze-drying and their structural and mechanical properties were studied. Biological performance of the scaffolds was assessed by culturing human adipose derived stem cells (hASCs) in medium with and without FBS supplementa-

tion. Viability tests showed that hASCs exhibit high cell viability when cultured in FBS-free medium. DNA quantification and MTS results revealed the ability of hASCs to proliferate and stay viable for 14 days even in the absence of FBS. Protein release assays results demonstrate the controlled release of proteins and growth factors involved in cell function.

Our results showed that PLMA sponges are a promising platform for 3D cell culture, offering the possibility to culture cells avoiding the use of animal-derived supplements. It is also a platform that could have an autologous origin, being adequate to produce personalized matrices with no risk of cross-reactivity, immune reaction, or disease transmission.

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Presentation: Oral

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3D printed *in vitro* bone models

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Three-dimensional *in vitro* bone models comprising human bone cells and their precursors, as well as endothelial cells are valuable approaches to analyze the interaction of bone with bioactive substances like growth factors, drugs and bioactive metal ions. Those models can help to reduce animal testing in the early stages of biomaterial development. A versatile method for the generation of spatially arranged tissue models is bioprinting. We are aiming to develop 3D bioprinted *in vitro* bone models inspired by the osteon structure of bone tissue. Especially the involvement of osteocytes into such *in vitro* models is challenging due to the limited avail-

ability of primary osteocytes. We therefore first investigated the differentiation of bioprinted osteoblasts in different alginate-based bioinks. Successful osteocytic differentiation was demonstrated both microscopically proving typical osteocyte morphology as well as by gene expression analysis of osteocytic markers like sclerostin and dentin matrix protein 1. Osteocytic differentiation of bioprinted osteoblasts was stimulated with low serum concentrations and by supplementation with bone morphogenic protein 2. This is the fundament to establish functional 3D printed *in vitro* bone models by incorporating osteoblasts, osteoclasts and endothelial cells. Different bioprinting approaches like coaxial bioprinting as well as printing of combined structures of hydrogels and calcium phosphate bone cements will be applied in future to generate functional bioprinted *in vitro* bone models.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Developing integrated approaches to testing and assessment for acute fish toxicity

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In various regulatory frameworks, the acute fish toxicity test is a standard data requirement, although promising alternative methods are available. These include the fish cytotoxicity test (OECD TG 249) and the acute fish embryo toxicity test (FET, OECD TG 236). There has been agreement that the FET can be used within weight-of-evidence approaches to address the acute fish toxicity data requirement under the European Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation, and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) regulation [1].

As a basis for the preparation of weight-of-evidence approaches to acute fish toxicity, Austria and the International Council on Animal Protection in OECD Programmes are leading a project to de-

velop a guidance document for Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA). The IATAs structure and guide the combination of computational tools, mechanistic information from the molecular and cellular levels, fish embryos and information from species of lower trophic levels. The draft guidance document provides a framework for data generation using TGs 236 and 249 depending on the chemical applicability domains of these assays.

Given a lower sensitivity of TGs 236 and 249 for neurotoxicants, acute fish LC₅₀ and acute daphnid EC₅₀ values available in the EnviroTox Database were compared. The analysis indicates that fish rarely represent the most sensitive trophic level among chemicals with neurotoxic modes of action.

The acute fish toxicity IATA guidance document will allow the use of alternative approaches for estimating the lowest EC₅₀ or LC₅₀ from algae, daphnids, and fish as a surrogate for all aquatic organisms, according to the CLP regulation.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Comparative proteomic characterization of serum-free cultivated HepG2 cells reveals upregulated drug metabolism and increased oxidative stress protection

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In vitro tissue, cell and organ culture is considered a major alternative for animal experimentation [1-3]. However, animal-derived components are commonly used to proliferate and/or differentiate cells in culture, causing both scientific and ethical concerns. One of the most controversial animal components in *in vitro* cell culture is fetal bovine serum (FBS), a cell culture supplement obtained from unborn calf fetuses as a byproduct of the meat industry [4]. In a previous study, the HepG2 cell line was adapted to serum-free conditions and cells (grown with or without FBS) were compared in different toxicity assays, focusing on viability, mitochondrial toxicity, oxidative stress, and intracellular drug response. While serum-free cultivated cells showed generally a slightly higher sensitivity in cytotoxicity assays, cells were less prone to experience oxidative stress.

To further understand these differences and investigate potential alterations of the proteomic landscape, a comparative proteomic study was conducted using cells cultured under FBS containing conditions and with different serum-free media. A particular focus was set on drug-metabolizing enzymes, antioxidative enzymes, and Nrf2 regulated proteins. Pathways related to drug response and oxidative stress protection (including glutathione redox reactions I, xenobiotic metabolism PXR signaling, Phase I – functionalization of compounds, Phase II – conjugation of compounds) were significantly upregulated in serum-free cultivated cells. These findings support previously generated *in vitro* data indicating a slightly higher sensitivity of HepG2 cells towards cytotoxic compounds and improved oxidative stress protection.

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Conflict of interest

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Presentation: Poster

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Differences between potential skin and respiratory sensitizers tested by non-animal methods

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After repeated contact with skin or respiratory system, a substance with sensitizing potential elicits sensitization. Recently, a battery of non-animal methods for assessment of skin sensitization potential has been adopted as OECD guidelines, however, no defined approaches for evaluation of respiratory sensitization potential have been developed yet. The suggested Adverse Outcome Pathways for respiratory and skin sensitization share some of the molecular events and mechanisms of action [1]. This pilot study was focused on investigation of differences and similarities between skin and respiratory sensitizers, which might lead to the definition of relevant endpoints and testing strategies. A group of known positive and negative respiratory sensitizers was tested by 2 alternative methods validated for skin sensitization, namely *in chemico* method DPRA (OECD TG 442C) and *in vitro* method LuSens (OECD TG

442D). According to the published results and to our experimental outcome, DPRA seems to be a promising method for the evaluation of the first key event (haptentation) for both skin and respiratory sensitization and might distinguish between respiratory and skin sensitizers in reaction with lysine or cysteine peptides, while the negative respiratory sensitizers reacted only with cysteine [2]. As expected, results from LuSens (keratinocyte activation) did not correspond with respiratory results. This study will further aim at other possible endpoints and key events in the process of sensitization, e.g., h-CLAT or cytokine evaluation using 3D airway epithelial models.

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Bioprinting of vascularized cancer model for drug testing

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Bioprinting allows the generation of tissue models with sophisticated 3D structures. We used the technology to create vascularized cancer models for developing cancer drugs in a human system. The initial lung cancer model was produced by digital light processing and harbored a curved channel and was connected to a peristaltic pump. Dynamic culture was found to be superior to static conditions with respect to cell viability and drug sensitivity [1]. In a subsequent model, the cancerous core was included in a microenvironment of hepatic cells simulating metastases in the liver [2]. The construct was generated by extrusion bioprinting without the need

of sacrificial material, a technology we named sacrificial-free direct ink writing (SF-DIW). The model contained a branched channel which was lined with endothelial cells. The vascular system was perfused by micro pumps which were integrated into the lid of the multiwell plate, thereby minimizing the required volume of medium. Various tumor types were introduced into the model demonstrating the general applicability of the set up. Finally, a cytostatic prodrug, ifosfamide was investigated, which was activated by hepatic cytochrome P450 enzymes following their induction by rifampicin. Drug treatment resulted in substantial and significant reduction of the tumor spheroid growth. The model can thus be used as a human alternative to cancer animal models which are known to have limited predictability to the human patient.

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Presentation: Oral

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Modeling and analysis of standard-of-care vs experimental, oncogene-specific therapeutic protocols in human digestive system cancer organoids

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Overview: Digestive system cancers (pancreatic, colon, and gastric cancers) remain a significant clinical challenge. By using patient-derived cancer organoids and patient-derived cancer-associated fibroblasts, we applied drug sensitivity and organoid assembly assays, testing new therapeutic protocols developed in our laboratory and comparing them to standard-of-care chemotherapy in the context of tumour microenvironment. The organoid model allowed us to monitor how different parameters of the 3D culture respond to the used protocols.

Methods: Patient-derived colon, pancreatic and gastric cancer organoids and cancer-associated fibroblasts. Organoid Drug Sensitiv-

ity Assay with the addition of tumour microenvironment. Organoid Assembly Assay based on Spinning Disc Microscopy. ImageJ with TrackMate and GraphPad Prism software used for analysis.

Results: The efficiency of experimental therapeutic protocols matched or surpassed standard chemotherapeutic protocols in killing cancer organoids characterized by either TP53 mutations, KRAS mutations, or MYC activation. Organoid assembly assay allowed to distinguish effects on cell migration in a 3D environment and formation of organoids in time.

Conclusion: Heterogeneous colon, pancreatic, and gastric cancer organoid models confirm the high efficacy of novel pre-clinical targeted drug combinations earlier developed using 2D cancer cell line cultures [1-3]. Organoid assembly assay allows us to analyze and distinguish how cell migration and cell group formation towards organoids may be differentially affected by anti-cancer drug treatment and direct oncogene targeting.

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Presentation: Poster

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Venezuelan equine encephalitis virus (VEEV) infection during early brain development impairs neuronal migration in hiPSC-derived neurospheres

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The Venezuelan equine encephalitis virus (VEEV) is a highly contagious alphavirus with a mortality rate of up to 1% of cases, causing severe encephalitis in around 14% of cases. Fetal or early childhood VEEV infection can lead to (fetal) death in up to 10% of

the cases and causes neurological conditions in up to 35% of cases, including long-term neurological sequelae in surviving children.

Our aim was to establish a predictive human *in vitro* brain development model using human induced pluripotent stem cell (hiPSC)-derived neurospheres to understand the infection's course, explain fetal brain sensitivity, predict potential long-term neuronal damage in the CNS, and identify therapeutic targets. Neurospheres, expressing neural progenitor cells, neurons and glial cells, replicate fundamental brain developmental processes.

VEEV infection parameters (dose and time) were optimized to be non-cytotoxic and viral particles were found in both, neuronal and glial cells. Preliminary results suggest an impairment of migration distance and area, which is currently under deeper analysis in a migration assay. The observed phenotype is supported by multi-OM-ICs analyses (transcriptome, proteome, secretome) which resulted in identification of several targets involved in motility, projection and migration of neural cells.

Evidence suggests VEEV infection may impair neural migration in fetal human brain modeling neurospheres. This model could shed light on the specific vulnerabilities of the fetal brain to VEEV and aid in the development of therapeutic interventions. Further research is warranted to elucidate the mechanisms underlying VEEV-induced neural damage and to explore potential avenues for treatment and prevention.

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The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Utilising experimental NAMs to assess genomic instability in liver models

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Animal-based research is under increasing pressure due to its sustainability, test model ethics, and relevance to human health hazard assessment. Ultimately, faster, and more advanced *in vitro* models in conjunction with an enriched toolbox of new-approach methodologies (NAMs) may fundamentally transform the regulatory testing framework. The human hepatocellular carcinoma (HepG2) cell line cultured in a 3D format demonstrates liver-like functionality and metabolic activity. This research tested the efficacy of the *in vitro* alkaline comet assay using HepG2 spheroids cultured in ultra-low attachment (ULA) plates.

HepG2 cells were seeded into ultra-low attachment (ULA) plates (2500 cells/well) and cultured for 48 hours. The spheroids were chemically treated for 24-hours with methyl methane sulfonate and ethyl methane sulfonate (MMS and EMS, respectively) followed by the comet assay to measure DNA strand breaks (SBs). For the comet assay the average %Tail DNA median in 150 cells was calculated using the Comet IV software ($n = 3$). Statistically significant ($p \leq 0.05$) SBs were observed following MMS and EMS exposure inducing $> 40\%$ and $> 30\%$ %Tail DNA.

The ULA plates improved the efficiency of culturing HepG2 spheroids for genotoxicity testing using the comet assay. The next phase of testing will incorporate the *in vitro* mammalian cell micronucleus test to assess fixed DNA damage in the HepG2 spheroids which will undergo a co-exposure of test compound with culture media containing 6 mg/mL of cytochalasin B. This research has been funded by the European Commission through the United Kingdom Research and Innovation.

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Presentation: Poster

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Recommendations for scientific fish husbandry

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Studies on fish species are for various reasons of high importance. This often includes the necessity to keep live fish specimens for investigations. Administrative bodies and legislation are often overstrained by the high diversity of species and life histories as well as their physiology represented by more than 36,600 fish species worldwide. Experts urgently need to support administration in their

decisions and researchers in their proposals and set-ups to work with live fish. Therefore, we started the series “Recommendations for scientific fish husbandry” in the Journal Bulletin of Fish Biology [1]. The aim of this series is to provide guidelines for the housing, feeding, breeding and rearing of specific fish species or groups with similar biology, taking into account their specific needs and animal welfare. In addition, this poster serves to illustrate the high number of fish used for research purposes as well as to present the structure for future articles within this series. We hope to encourage researchers working with fish to write articles about their experience as part of this series.

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The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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Human stem cell-derived neurospheres as a model to characterize the impact of *Listeria monocytogenes* infection on early brain development

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Zoonotic infections during pregnancy can lead to infection of the central nervous system (CNS) in surviving offspring. Neurodevelopmental disorders have been described as long-term consequences of pre- and perinatal CNS infections; however the underlying mechanisms are not well understood.

We use human induced pluripotent stem cell (iPSC)-derived neurospheres to mimic the human developing brain and want to test their suitability as a model to study the consequences of fetal CNS

infections. The neurospheres comprise neural stem cells (NSCs) that differentiate into various neural and glial subtypes, including mature neural cell populations. First studies are focusing on infection with *Listeria monocytogenes*, a bacterial pathogen that is known to cause lasting neurological impairments in infected offspring. By ingesting contaminated food, pregnant women transfer the bacteria to their offspring primarily via the bloodstream.

We hypothesize that infection induces primary NSC depletion and accelerated maturation of surviving NSCs, leading to impaired differentiation, aberrant migration, and altered network activity.

In a first step, sufficient numbers of consistent neurospheres had to be generated that are currently characterized via RT-qPCR and immunocytochemistry. The findings will be presented at the conference. Further, cryopreservation protocols to directly freeze neurospheres using two different cryopreservation media were applied, to allow transfer to biosafety level facilities for infection experiments. Preliminary results indicate the recovery post-cryopreservation does not differ between the freezing media. However, the long-term cell survival rates do not show satisfactory results yet, necessitating the optimization of the protocol. Next, initial infection experiments aim to identify an appropriate infection dose.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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Advancing ethical and reproducible stem cell culture: Alternatives to chemically undefined animal-derived matrices in *in vitro* toxicology testing

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Toxicological testing is crucial in safeguarding human health and the environment from potential hazards of chemicals or drugs. Traditionally, animal testing has been the predominant method for these evaluations. However, there are *in vitro* alternatives, for example the use of human induced pluripotent stem cells (hiPSCs) for predictive, animal-free toxicity testing. Regulatory standards demand predictive and reproducible results. Guidance on good stem cell culture practice [1] promotes the use of xeno-free, and chemically defined components, but mainly focuses on culture media. However, the importance of culture substrates, such as Matrigel or other components of the extracellular matrix (ECM) is overlooked.

Matrigel is not only chemically undefined, but further produces hidden animal use in putative animal-free *in vitro* techniques.

Comparing different substrates consisting of the most abundant ECM components, like fibronectin or vitronectin, we aim to find a defined, xeno-free alternative for hiPSC maintenance. We study attachment, growth and morphology of hiPSCs (IMR90-4). In our hands, two recombinantly engineered variants of fibronectin-containing ECM structures seem to be promising. [2] Their long-term use in hiPSC culture is currently under evaluation. Using RT-qPCR, immunofluorescence staining and flow cytometry, we monitor gene and protein expression of markers of all three germ layers and of pluripotency markers. Further experiments will focus on neuronal differentiation protocols to advance the development of fully chemically defined, animal-free assays. This study is intended to show that alternatives to chemically undefined and animal-derived coatings, like the still excessively used Matrigel, exist and might be a promising alternative in toxicology tests.

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Presentation: Poster

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Body-on-a-chip technologies towards neurotoxic monitoring and environmental safety/CBRN applications

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Organophosphates, such as Malathion, are pervasive components in pesticides and chemical weapons like Sarin. Prolonged exposure to these compounds can result in severe neurological disorders. There is an urgent need for enhanced methods to assess environmental neurotoxicity without endangering human or animal lives. This study aims to develop a portable multi-organ microfluidic platform equipped with *in situ* biosensors for in-field deployment and real-time acute toxicity evaluation.

In this platform, we conducted characterizations of micropumps, including assessments of varying pressures, actuation frequencies,

and sizes, along with an analysis of material deformation (PDMS) and liquid flow dynamics.

Additionally, our study involved an investigation into the responses of tissue-specific cell lines when exposed to organ-specific toxins within both 2D and 3D environments. Specifically, we exposed liver cells (HepG2) to Paracetamol and kidney cells (Hek293) to Gentamicin, documenting their toxicity across different toxicant concentrations. We also examined the behavior of cell micromasses in an organ-on-a-chip platform when exposed to the IC50 concentration of the toxicants.

We additionally explored the reactions of midbrain organoids to varying concentrations of an Acetylcholinesterase inhibitor and Malathion.

Analysis of cell response to toxicants was done using either absorbance or luminescence assays.

We believe that this platform will lead to improvements in the area of *in vitro* toxicology and environmental monitoring, replacing current animal model standards.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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Exploring neuron-mediated chronic pain: Insights from *in vitro* modelling for pharmacology and toxicology

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Chronic pain affects a significant portion of the global population. Current therapy methods mainly rely on animal-based tests, which can be ethically concerning and may not accurately reflect human responses. To address this, our project aims to develop two predictive human cell-based *in vitro* models to quantify neuron-mediated chronic pain.

In the first part, human induced pluripotent stem cell (hiPSC)-derived sensory neurons are utilized to create a luciferase-based exocytosis assay, tracking the exocytosis of Substance P and Calcitonin gene-related peptide, key neuropeptides in chronic pain, via depolarising buffers. We anticipate a correlation between emitted light resulting from a POMC-tagged luciferase and neuropeptide release, both from large dense core vesicles, compared with ELISA data [1].

Secondly, an innervated skin model with hiPSC-derived sensory neurons and Schwann cells, as well as keratinocytes stimulated to produce Neurite Growth Factor (NGF), along with supporting fibroblasts, will be established. Neurite outgrowth via confocal microscopy and gene expression of pain receptors, ion channels and proinflammatory genes linked to chronic pain will be assessed.

Proof-of-concept studies will evaluate pharmacological and toxicological responses, including induced neuropeptide release by TRP agonists or inhibition of release by Botulinum Neurotoxin, neurite outgrowth and modulation of gene expression induced by TRP agonists and inhibited by NGF neutralizing antibodies.

Current work includes the establishment of the exocytosis assay in sensory neurons and optimization of assay conditions.

By modelling molecular signalling pathways of chronic pain in human cells, unnecessary animal experiments can be minimized, facilitating the development of effective and safe human therapeutics.

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Conflict of interest

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Presentation: Poster

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3D bioprinting of humanized xeno-free liver models

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Significant efforts are being made to develop new approach methods (NAMs) to replace animal experiments. However, most of the reported NAMs, including 3D bioprinted cell culture models, involve the use of animal-derived components. The present study aims to develop bioprinted liver models that are completely devoid of animal components. As proof-of-concept, a xeno-free liver model was developed based on HuH-7 cells [1]. Cells were adapted to a chemically defined medium (CDM) using both direct and sequen-

tial approaches. Furthermore, three different chemically defined freezing media were prepared and optimized for the cryopreservation of adapted cells. Additionally, a xeno-free bioink was formulated based on sodium alginate, human collagen (I), and nutrient supplements to avoid the use of animal components in bioprinting. The resulting xeno-free bioprinted liver models demonstrated high cell viability and metabolic activity, comparable to that of the Matrigel-based liver model. To assess the applicability of this xeno-free model, it was used to test the hepatotoxicity of okadaic acid, and results were compared to conventional 2D cell culture. To further improve the model, the established CDM was optimized to grow additional cell lines, including HepaRG (hepatic), LX-2 (hepatic stellate), and HUVEC (endothelial) cells. The co-culture xeno-free model can thus be used as a potential alternative to animal testing for high-throughput hepatotoxicity evaluation.

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Presentation: Oral

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Reviewer guidelines and trainings to mitigate animal methods bias

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Funders and publishers are acutely aware of the potential for bias in their processes, and the detrimental effect this can have on the quality of the scientific knowledge base [1]. In this presentation, the current landscape of reviewer guidelines and bias mitigation trainings will be provided, and we will explore how they could be adapted to include animal methods bias [2]. Current bias mitigation tools include guidelines and trainings for editors or peer reviewers, such as a Peer-Review *In vitro* Appraisal Tool (PRIVAT), which was recently developed by the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration to aid in the comprehensive, useful, and transparent peer review of *in vitro* studies [3]. Widespread implementation of these and other such tools need buy-in from major publishing and funding stake-

holders, which requires acceptance of the possible existence and deleterious effect of animal methods bias. In many cases however there are simple actions that can be taken, and the most efficient solution might be the evolution of existing reviewer guidelines and trainings by adding a brief description, vignette, and/or guidelines rather than designing entirely new tools.

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Conflict of interest

The author works for a charity whose mission is to support scientists to replace the use of animals in biomedical research.

Presentation: Oral

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Establishment of 3D FCS-free cultures of human proximal tubule epithelial cells

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Introduction: Microphysiological systems are promising platforms in reducing animal testing in preclinical drug development. Conditionally immortalized proximal tubule epithelial cells (ciPTECs) cultured on hollow fiber membranes (HFM) in fetal calf serum (FCS) containing medium were previously shown to resemble human kidney proximal tubules [1,2]. Here, we evaluated transitioning to FCS-free culture of ciPTEC overexpressing organic anion transporter 1 (ciPTEC-OAT1) on HFM, which contributes to reduction of animal use for FCS production.

Methods: The ciPTEC-OAT1 were cultured on HFMs in either FCS-containing or human platelet lysate (hPL)-containing medium, at 33°C for 1-3 days and at 37°C for 7 days. Static culture conditions were compared with cultures on a 3D rocker to assess the impact of shear stress on cell cultures. Cell viability was as-

sessed by PrestobluTM assay and ciPTEC-OAT1-HFM were fixed and stained with DAPI and phalloidin to evaluate cell number and cell coverage.

Results: After initial optimization of FCS-free medium, the ciPTEC-OAT1 cultured in both media formed monolayers on the HFM, regardless of static or rocking cultures. Uncorrected Cell viability after proliferation ($p = 0.04$) and maturation ($p < 0.0001$), as well as cell density ($p = 0.02$, by quantification of nuclei) was markedly higher for ciPTEC-OAT1 on HFM cultured in FCS-containing medium. This was also highlighted by phalloidin staining.

Conclusion: ciPTEC-OAT1 cultured in FCS-free medium on HFM was successful based on cell viability and coverage, however, differences in cell density were evident, without a noticeable effect of shear stress. Future directions include evaluation of differences in monolayer integrity, drug transporter gene expression and protein abundance.

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Presentation: Poster

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Funding 3R research in Germany – A key to new innovative methods

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To date, animals continue to be an indispensable model for research. Animal testing delivers important data about how effective novel drugs are and whether certain substances are toxic for humans. An ethical dilemma emerges – the striving for knowledge and the safety of humans on the one hand and animal welfare on the other. In this regard, the 3R principle provides the current framework for doing research that is as best in line with animal welfare requirements as possible.

The German federal ministry for education and research (BMBF) has been funding the development of new alternative methods since

the early 1980ies. More than 700 projects with over 225 Mio Euros have been funded, making it the longest running funding call of the BMBF. Furthermore, there have been various additional funding calls over the years specifically tailored for specified scientific needs such as new methods for toxicology.

Seeing that constructive dialogue between various stakeholders is a key factor for policy changes,

the BMBF launched the “*Bundesnetzwerk 3R*” as a national platform for exchange about the 3R principle and possibilities for their implementation. The mission of the network is to facilitate an inter- and transdisciplinary dialogue between science, industry, politics, regulatory authorities and other stakeholders, thus building a strong community that jointly advances 3R research.

The new digital platform www.bundesnetzwerk-3R.de, forms a key element of the networks activities. All stakeholders of the German 3R landscape, each with their own research interests, are invited to become part of the interactive network.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Generation of human sensory macrophages to replace animal research in preclinical pharmacology and drug safety applications

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Healthcare industry has recently undergone significant changes, introducing novel immunotherapies, vaccines and other classes of modern therapeutics. The identification and pharmacological evaluation of these drugs often relies on animal models, but profound ethical concerns, and differences to human physiology have prompted a shift towards alternative approaches. Given the importance of the immune system, primary human immune cells and ar-

tificial cell lines have been proposed as alternatives. However, their availability and variability and the artificial cancer background, limit their widespread use. Thus, human induced pluripotent stem cells (hiPSCs) have become a promising alternative introducing next-generation evaluation, validation and assessment strategies to assess drug efficacy and safety. We developed a scalable GMP-compatible platform that generates different, highly standardized human immune cells from hiPSC. As an example, macrophages are key cells that act as important pro- and anti-inflammatory mediators in the onset and progression of various diseases, including fibrosis, cancer or autoimmunity. Our iPSC-derived macrophages (iPSC-Mac) exhibit convenient phenotypic properties, phagocytotic functionality and a transcriptional profile like blood-derived macrophages (BDM). In line with the plasticity of macrophages, we developed a highly reproducible platform for (i) the evaluation of novel immune-modulatory drug candidates and (ii) safety/pyrogenicity testing in the Monocyte-Activation-Test (iMAT). iPSC-Mac show a superior sensitivity to endotoxins (LPS) and non-endotoxins (e.g., MALP-2) compared to BDM. Overall, we present a scalable and efficient method to generate standardized human macrophages from hiPSC, suitable for multiple applications and paving the way for the phase-out of animal experiments for parenteral drug-safety testing, aligning European Pharmacopeia's vision.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Empowering researchers to take the leap from lab to business to increase the impact of animal-free innovations

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Background: Researchers developing animal-free innovations often wonder how to drive the wide-spread use of their technology [1]. The Proefdiervrij Venture Challenge is a training program that assists researchers to take their scientific innovation towards broader implementation [2]. This approach accelerates the adoption of novel animal-free assays and/or methods by the end user such as big pharma, small biotech companies and academia and in turn accelerates the reduction in demand for test animals.

Method: The Proefdiervrij Venture Challenge is a 3-month program comprising of multiple workshops, 1-on-1 coaching sessions and feedback from experienced entrepreneurs. The program focuses on the key aspects that are essential for building a commercially

successful venture such as confirming problem/solution fit, establishing meaningful differentiation from competition, pitch training, defining the starting opportunity and the subsequent steps to grow the business. The end product is a business plan and an investor pitch that is presented to a jury of experts in the Life Sciences investment community. The jury chooses a winner, who wins €25.000 to make the first steps of bringing the innovation into business.

Results and conclusion: Four editions were held since 2020 with 18 teams participating. 6 teams have developed into a start-up, another 6 are expected to enter the market in the coming years. The Proefdiervrij Venture Challenge has proven to be a valuable learning opportunity that provides new skills which can be directly implemented in daily practice. Besides, it serves as a guide for the next phase in implementing the animal-free innovation.

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Presentation: Oral

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The Swiss National Research Programme “Advancing 3R – Animals, research and society” (NRP 79)

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The 3R principle has seen wide acceptance in the last decades. Today, the 3Rs are incorporated as legal requirements in transnational legislation such as the European Directive 2010/63/EU as well as in national legislation, including in Switzerland, Norway and the UK. Despite its success, it has also been criticised in various ways [1]: Are the 3Rs sufficient to manage the ethical complexities of animal use in research? Does the idea of “humane experimenting on animals” live up with social priorities today? Are the 3Rs in need of amendment to navigate animal research in the future? Or, are they outdated and due for replacement? The Swiss National Research Programme “Advancing 3R – Animals, research and society” (NRP

79) investigates such questions in a multi- and interdisciplinary manner to probe how to advance the 3R approach effectively. The NRP 79 is financed and managed by the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) and structured in three modules: Innovation, Implementation, and Ethics and Society. In 27 funded research projects the NRP79 aims at identifying and addressing the potentials, the challenges and the limitations of the 3R. In this talk, the background, organisational structure, main goals and first results of the NRP79 are going to be presented.

Please note: To avoid self-plagiarism, the authors explicitly state that abstracts with comparable content on the nature of the NRP79 are also published in other conference proceedings under the same authorship.

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Presentation: Oral

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An optogenetic approach to investigating the molecular function of TLR4 and TLR10 in mesenchymal stem cells

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Introduction: Mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) are multipotent, non-hematopoietic, fibroblast-like cells that facilitate tissue regeneration. Human MSCs are known to express Toll-like receptors (TLRs) TLR1 to TLR10, which are associated with tissue injury and infection. Activation of TLRs has been demonstrated to have multiple roles, including the control of proliferation, differentiation, and the repair of damaged tissue. In contrast to TLRs 1-9, TLR10 remains the last human TLR without a known ligand, signaling role, or other clear function. Therefore, the objective was to establish an optogenetic MSC model in which the TLRs can be activated by light to gain in-depth knowledge of the underlying molecular mechanisms and function of TLR4 and TLR10 in MSCs.

Methods: The LOV domain was fused to the C-terminal end of the TLRs and stably integrated into adipose-derived stem cells (ASC-TERT) to allow dimerization by blue light (480 nm). Western blotting and RT-qPCR were performed to ensure the presence and

functionality of the optogenetic cell line. Next-generation sequencing (NGS) and mass spectrometry (MS) were employed for gene expression analysis and functional cell-based differentiation assays to investigate the effect of these receptors.

Results: The preliminary data indicated that LPS-stimulated and light-induced activation of TLR4-LOV has pro-inflammatory mediators, whereas TLR10 activation indicates a more anti-inflammatory response. Moreover, the NGS and MS data demonstrated that TLR10 activation in opto-TLR10 MSCs has regenerative potential.

Conclusion: These newly established optogenetic cell lines are optimal tools for investigating the mechanism of TLR4 and TLR10 homodimerization and may provide novel insights for therapeutic strategies.

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Presentation: Oral

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Prioritizing non-animal methods to improve environmental risk assessment for pharmaceuticals and promote innovation in the EU

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Amidst the revision of the EU pharmaceutical legislation, a critical juncture emerges to prioritise non-animal methods in environmental risk assessment. The proposal includes provisions that promote a transition from testing on animals to non-animal methods, which offers a generational opportunity to foster innovation, including in areas of unmet medical need, and adapt to new scientific and technological developments [1,2].

Moreover, the draft provision mandating environmental risk assessment of legacy pharmaceuticals underscores the necessity and opportunity to prioritize non-animal methods, as prioritizing non-animal methods will not only advance science but also enhance implementation of the 3Rs and address environmental concerns. This complements the European Commission's roadmap to phase out animal testing in chemical safety assessments, reflecting the EU's response to the recent European Citizens' initiative.

The European Medicines Agency has recently adopted the first revision of its guidance on environmental risk assessment to become effective in September 2024 [3]. Since this revision was started before the launch of the EU pharmaceutical strategy, as well as the relaunch of the 3Rs Working Party, there will be a need for a

further update in parallel with the EU pharmaceutical legislation to articulate clear methodologies for robust environmental risk assessment using non-animal methods and promoting innovative scientifically sound technologies. This poster examines how the latest guidance can be improved further by giving precedence to non-animal methods and aligning with broader initiatives, enabling the EU to take the lead in fostering innovation while safeguarding the well-being of animals, human health, and the environment.

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Presentation: Poster

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Novel 3D *in-vitro* psoriasis model based on specific genetically engineered keratinocytes

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Psoriasis is a chronic inflammatory autoimmune disease that is characterized by a dysregulated cross talk between keratinocytes and immune cells. Animal models are still very common in psoriasis research and the number of published murine models increased in the last decade. In opposite to that, *in-vitro* models are highly underrepresented. The few existing *in-vitro* models are not fully developed, are not standardizable or miss important characteristics of the disease. In this study, we established psoriasis specific genetic modified keratinocytes to generate a novel model of the disease. For this, we overexpressed the psoriasis associated transcription factor STAT3 in human immortalized primary keratinocytes and used the

cells for the set-up of epidermis and full-thickness skin models. The models were additionally stimulated with psoriasis-associated cytokines or activated T cells were integrated. All models were subsequently analysed with histological and immunohistochemical staining. A comparison of the models with psoriasis biopsies from patients showed a high consistency in the expression of characteristic markers. The expression of psoriasis markers was more pronounced in the STAT3 skin models compared to skin models set up from the base keratinocyte cell line. Thus, the genetic modification enhanced the sensitivity of the cells to psoriatic stimuli [1]. Concluding, the novel *in-vitro* psoriasis model mimics many psoriatic characteristics, is highly reproducible and well suited as alternative to animal models.

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Presentation: Oral

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3R-competence network North Rhine-Westphalia – The alliance for medical progress in line with the best possible animal welfare

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Use of laboratory animal models in basic research is a major cornerstone to advance medicine for human and animal health. For this progress, one should always ensure best possible welfare for those animals. Here, the principle of 3Rs (replacement, reduction, refinement) provide a framework for all involved in animal research to continuously improve animal welfare.

In 2022, the eight faculties of medicine in the German state of North Rhine-Westphalia formed the “3R-Competence Network NRW” to promote medical progress in line with the best possible animal welfare. By enabling new interfaces for inter- and transdisciplinary exchange as well as expanding the range of training and

further education opportunities, the network creates new synergies between researchers from different scientific disciplines. Besides, facilitating the dialog between science, industry, politics, regulatory authorities and other stakeholders and promoting the development of new 3R methods is part of the networks’ activities. For instance, the scientific events such as a monthly online colloquium, symposia, workshops and an annual network conference on 3R related topics are offered regularly. The network also engages in science communication to build bridges between science community and society. The main audience is high school students, who not only gain theoretical and practical experience with animal research and animal welfare, but also have the opportunity to discuss with experts.

The 3R-Competence Network North Rhine-Westphalia creates an environment for a more sustainable, future-oriented (bio-) medical science in line with best possible animal welfare and promotes the 3R principle as a catalyst for innovation.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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Measurement and simulation of transdermal delivery of topical drug formulations in a dynamic microfluidic diffusion chamber in health and disease

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Mathematical models of epidermal and dermal transport are essential for optimization and development of products for percutaneous delivery both for local and systemic indication and for evaluation of dermal toxicity. These models often help by providing information on the rate of drug penetration through the skin which is the base of their pharmacological effect. The simulations are also helpful in analyzing experimental data, reducing the number of experiments and translating the *in vitro* investigations to an *in-vivo* setting. In this study skin penetration of topically administered caffeine cream was investigated in a skin-on-a-chip microfluidic diffusion cham-

ber at room and skin temperature. Also, the transdermal penetration of caffeine in healthy and diseased conditions was compared in mouse skins from intact, psoriatic and allergic animals. In the last experimental setup dexamethasone, indomethacin, piroxicam and diclofenac were examined as a cream formulation for absorption across the dermal barrier. All the measured data were used for making mathematical simulation in a three-compartmental model. The calculated and measured results showed a good match, which findings indicate that our mathematical model might be applied for prediction of drug delivery through the skin in the novel, miniaturized diffusion chamber. This single channel setup was used for further analysis by Computational Fluid Dynamics simulation. The visualization of shear stress and fluid velocity within the microchannel and also the presentation of caffeine progression with the perfusion fluid were consistent with the measured data.

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The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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Do extracellular vesicles from mesenchymal stem cells inhibit cancer development?

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Cancer is a severe problem in the world. Current therapies destroying tumors, also lead to functional defects in surrounding tissues. A possible form of regeneration is using mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs). These from adipose tissue deserve special attention because of their regenerative, immunosuppressive, and anti-inflammatory potential. Unfortunately, many features necessary for the healing process also play an essential role in cancer progression. The direction depends on the properties of tumor cells remaining after treatment. Studies confirmed that extracellular vesicles (EVs) released by MSCs are responsible for their regenerative potential. They also mediate in cell communication. This seems interesting in

the context of the use of EVs among oncology patients. We decided to investigate their safety and the impact on the tumor microenvironment. They may be a valuable tool for oncology therapies if they limit or stop the development of tumors.

EVs were isolated from the conditioned medium of the ASC52te-10 cell line using a commercial kit. The exosome protein content was measured spectrophotometrically. Four bladder cancer cell lines (5637, HB-CLS-1, HT-1376, T24) were cultured with EVs (50, 100, 200 µg/mL) for 72 h. Then, the proliferation of cancer cells was assessed using the BrdU assay. In the next step, the activity of signaling pathways after incubation with EVs was assessed. The activity of ERK and AKT kinases was measured using a sandwich ELISA.

Performed analysis indicated that EVs significantly decrease cancer cells' proliferation depending on concentration. Analysis of signaling PI3K/AKT and MAPK demonstrates that EVs affect ERK and AKT activity.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Preregistration of animal studies improves reporting quality

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Building on lessons learned from clinical research, we recently established preregistration of animal studies as a pertinent intervention to improve transparency and study quality, yet no structured assessment has been performed to evaluate its efficacy.

Here we provide the first evaluation of the effect of preregistration on animal studies. We gathered preregistered protocols and

their corresponding publications from the platforms Preclinicaltrials.eu and the Animal Study Registry. They were compared to non-preregistered control publications similar in content (i.e., same species, techniques, fields, publication periods) either from the same authors to mitigate team effect bias (author-control group) or from the same journals (journal-control group). Subsequently, two independent assessors conducted a blinded evaluation of reporting quality using the *ARRIVE guidelines essential 10*. Each paper was assigned an overall score ranging from 0 to 1, corresponding to different quality categories: “Excellent” (0.8-1), “Good” (0.6-0.79), “Average” (0.4-0.59), “Mediocre” (0.2-0.39), and “Poor” (0-0.19). Analyses were performed on R using a two-way ANOVA.

The preregistered papers statistically scored better than both controls, and were categorised “Excellent” = 0.80 (SE = 0.02, 97.5%CI [0.75-0.84]), while author-control and journal-control papers scored “Good” = 0.64 (SE = 0.25, 97.5%CI [0.59-0.69]) and “Average” = 0.59 (SE = 0.25, 97.5%CI [0.54-0.64]) respectively. Analyses per ARRIVE item emphasised these differences, notably in reporting details about inclusion/exclusion criteria, randomisation and blinding methods, experimental procedures, and results (i.e., summary/descriptive statistics of results, with a measure of variability).

This evaluation shows first evidence that preregistration positively impacts reporting quality and should be considered a valuable method to increase transparency.

Conflict of interest

Julia M.L. Menon is the daily director of the platform Preclinicaltrials.eu. Celine Heintz works for the Animal Study Registry. Timothy M. Errington works for the Open Science Framework, a registration platform. Authors 4, 8-12 are members of Preclinicaltrials.eu’s Steering Committee. The other authors declare no conflict of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Inspecting the scientific literature for signs of animal methods bias

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Animal methods bias [1] is the bias against non-animal methods when a viable *in vitro* alternative exists, adversely affecting the advancement of alternatives to animal models. One aspect of this bias manifests as unfavorable manuscript reviews that may result in publication delays or publishing in lower impact factor journals, potentially affecting researchers' careers. Although self-reported survey data suggest this issue happens across different bioscience disciplines [2], the limited availability of manuscript review reports poses challenges in identifying its occurrence. Thus, to infer possible instances and characteristics of animal methods bias, we investigated the peer-reviewed literature. First, we created a natural language processing (NLP) pipeline to analyze over 300,000

peer-reviewed scientific publications, find their corresponding preprints, compare species mentioned in the preprint and final publication methods sections and identify studies where an *in vivo* model was introduced after the first available preprint was posted. A small number of positive matches was identified, possibly reflecting low preprint posting rates, but nevertheless confirming that authors occasionally perform additional *in vivo* experiments after initial manuscript submission, possibly in response to reviewers. Additionally, we processed over 1.1 million peer-reviewed publications between 2009 and 2023 to identify differences in publication rates, trends, and impact factors between studies using non-animal methods, *in vivo* methods, and both. Our findings show significant differences, consistent over time, between publications using animal models and their alternative methods-based counterparts, confirming self-reported findings of animal methods bias during manuscript peer review and subsequent effects on publication characteristics.

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Presentation: Oral

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A manifesto from the young generation advocating to go animal testing-free

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Over the last few years, a new approach has arisen from the 3Rs (replacement, reduction, refinement of animal testing) that is aimed specifically at the transition towards using animal-free innovations. This transition is complex: it involves many players and needs actions from all of them on different levels. As Young TPI, a network of young people stimulating the transition, we took a critical outlook on this shift. The network's reflection on the current status and future actions to accelerate the transition has resulted in a manifesto [1]. This manifesto was written with input from various brainstorming and feedback sessions with Young TPI members, working from our core values towards different themes that we believe need to be addressed.

The manifesto describes the problem and actions that are required from different players, including Young TPI, explained in six themes: improvements in Technologies, Transition Science, Policy Approach, Education, Interdisciplinarity, and The Bigger Picture.

While the technological innovations are an important part of the puzzle, so are the interactions between the different actors in this transition, leading us to ask significant questions such as: what is the paradigm shift we are aiming for? What are our societal goals and how do we get there? What risks do we accept? Who fulfils which role during the transition? Young people play a crucial role in this transition and we aspire to guide them through with this manifesto, together with all the other important actors in this transition towards animal testing-free science.

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Conflict of interest

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Presentation: Poster

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Development of a dual-flow microfluidic device to study the interaction of the intestinal epithelium and the enteric nervous system

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The intricate relationship between gut and brain has gained increasing attention due to its implications for human health and disease. Gastrointestinal health has become prevalent as a cofactor in the pathophysiology of various neurodegenerative diseases [1]. Current research relies on animal models, although their translatability is disproven and they have been criticised for being unsuitable [2]. Since the FDA approved Organ-on-a-Chip devices as substitutions for animal models, a need for more variety and complexity in such models has arisen [3].

We developed a microfluidic device consisting of the intestinal epithelium and enteric nervous system (ENS) to investigate effects on nervous tissue after passage of the intestinal barrier. It has the possibility of direct co-culturing of cells while still providing fluid dynamic conditions for each tissue. Mimicking the microenvironment of the intestinal epithelium by applying shear stress led to 3D organisation and promoted differentiation of the cells [4]. For neu-

ronal cells, interstitial flow through their 3D microenvironment reinforces neuronal outgrowth [5]. These conditions can be provided with our device by establishing two hydrostatic pressure gradients. The channel arrangement replicates the anatomy of the small intestine and ENS *in vivo*, which allows cell contact and nutrients to cross the intestinal barrier before reaching the ENS.

The device characterisation showed perfusion of the ENS layer with a uniform distribution in empty and cell-laden gels. An on-chip co-culture system based on human cell lines (Caco-2, SH-SY5Y, U87-MG) was established. Considerations such as culture media and cell viability provide a sound foundation for long-term experiments.

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The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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Development of a bioreactor for dynamic culture and laser-based non-destructive measurements of tissue models

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Background: The aim of the BMBF-funded project “TIRAMISU” is to develop a novel non-invasive endoscopic method, which enables early diagnosis of microbial infections and carcinogenesis in the human oral cavity. Within the project, tissue engineered models are being evaluated as alternatives to the C57BL/6J mouse model for the development and validation of the laser-based device [1]. In order to use tissue models to reduce and replace animal tests, new bioreactor designs are needed.

Methods: Tissue models for carcinogenesis [2] and an immunocompetent model to study microbial infections [3] were established based on a decellularized porcine small intestine scaffold (SISmuc) [4]. A novel bioreactor design was required in order to enhance mass transport, provide tissue-specific stimuli and enable fluorescence lifetime imaging microscopy (FLIM) and Raman spectroscopy measurements of the tissue models.

Results: The developed bioreactor comprises two individual chambers and provides physical stimulation by fluid shear stress in physiologically relevant ranges. Both the apical and basal surfaces

of the tissue model are optically accessible in the bioreactor, this enables long-term non-destructive measurements by fluorescence microscopy, FLIM and Raman spectroscopy. All materials used in the bioreactor are non-cytotoxic [5].

Conclusion: The bioreactor will be used to monitor metabolic changes associated with carcinogenesis and to detect microbial infections on the tissue models by using FLIM and Raman spectroscopy respectively. The bioreactor and tissue models could be used as an alternative to established animal tests during the development and validation process of laser-based medical devices.

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Conflict of interest

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Presentation: Oral

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Fostering effective communication and collaboration in animal research facilities

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Effective communication and collaboration are essential to the success and operation of animal research facilities. This presentation will address critical aspects of improving these elements that are specific to the unique environment of animal research facilities and the roles of laboratory animal technicians.

Strategies will be presented for creating an open and trusting climate where employees, including Laboratory Animal Technicians,

feel comfortable speaking openly with their supervisors. This includes creating an environment of psychological safety where all team members are encouraged to share their ideas, feedback and concerns about animal care and research procedures.

It is also important to establish a clear system to ensure that everyone knows their roles and responsibilities. In the context of an animal research facility, this means that the roles of each technician and researcher must be clearly defined to ensure that protocols are followed to the letter to ensure animal welfare and the integrity of the research.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Safety assessment through animal-free evolution (SAFE): The role of transformative governance in the transition to animal-free regulatory research

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The transition towards animal-free alternatives in regulatory safety assessment within chemical and pharmaceutical industries, presents a pressing societal challenge. Despite the ethical imperative, convincing scientific evidence and growing public condemnation of animal testing practices, regulatory agencies have been slow to embrace alternative methods. This research project, Safety Assessment through Animal-Free Evolution (SAFE), seeks to expedite the regulatory acceptance of non-animal New Approach Methods (NAMs) by applying a transformative governance approach. Transformative governance delves into the underlying causes of societal

problems, offering a nuanced understanding of barriers hindering the transition to animal-free innovations and – testing. SAFE project operates at three distinct levels of transition: niche, regime, and landscape. At the niche level, it generates transdisciplinary knowledge to validate the usability and applicability of current New Approach Methods (NAMs) for chemicals and pharmaceuticals. At the regime level, the project analyses the current transition and advocates for the regulatory acceptance of NAMs and NGRA. At the landscape level, economic and societal impediments to progress are analysed, focusing on the values, convictions, and interests of diverse stakeholder groups. Embedded within a transdisciplinary consortium, the SAFE project involves the collaboration of diverse stakeholders. By unravelling power dynamics, understanding societal values, and fostering collaboration across stakeholders, the transformative governance approach offers a promising pathway towards shifts in paradigms and mindsets, expediting regulatory acceptance of animal-free alternatives in safety assessment. In this discussion, we will present ongoing work which includes case studies at the niche level and active contributions to changes occurring at the regime level.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Can we agree on what the 3Rs mean?

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The 3Rs – replacement, reduction, and refinement – have gained enormous recognition as basic guidelines for animal research [1,2]. At this critical moment of increased recognition of the 3Rs, it is essential to work from a shared understanding of their meaning to facilitate their implementation [3]. Here, I discuss an explicit effort to reach a common interpretation by a network of over 200 participants in the COST Action “3Rs concepts to improve the quality of biomedical science” (IMPROVE). Our strategy toward consensus was to stay as close as possible to the original definitions, while disambiguating them and accommodating both the legal framework provided by the *EU Directive 2010/63* and the updated definitions provided online by the U.K. National Centre for the 3Rs. Following multiple rounds of paper revision, it proved unexpectedly difficult to reach a common interpretation. The variety of opinion could be situated along an axis with, as polar opposites, “originalism” versus “abolitionism”. Originalists see the 3Rs as a technocratic tool strict-

ly limited to proportionality testing to check whether animal experiments are justified and tend to deny the need to revise or review the definitions. Abolitionists see the 3Rs as a dynamic framework to avoid the use of animals overall, beginning with the use of animals for research, but also targeting other domains of animal use. Here I argue we should systematically address this tension between different perspectives to maximize the “zone of cooperation,” so that we can effectively improve the quality of biomedical science with the 3Rs.

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Presentation: Oral

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Enhancing anxiety behavior research in rodents with network meta-analysis

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Aim: Anxiety is a complex behavioral and psychological construct that can be difficult to measure in rodents. Pharmacological data involving different anxiety tests are often inconsistent across studies. This can be owing to factors such as variations in genetic background, test protocol and laboratory environment. Conducting a network meta-analysis (NMA) of various anxiety tests in rodents can evaluate the reliability and validity of these tests, ultimately identifying the most effective and reliable methods for measuring

anxiety-like behavior.

Methods: In this study, we conducted a network meta-analysis (NMA) of these methods to evaluate their reliability and validity in measuring anxiety-like behavior in rodents. Here we will present our optimized and refined pipeline to assess the complex behavioral data that measured from different test (open field, plus maze, etc.) in animal experiments through multistep network meta-analysis.

Outcomes: Findings from NMA results can be indicates anxiety-related outcomes in animal models can inform the development of novel therapeutic approaches for managing anxiety disorders in humans. In this study, total distance move, fecal boli, grooming, rearing, head dips, etc. were analyzed for different apparatus. At the end of the analysis, we could see which apparatus has much more reliable for recording these behavior.

Conclusion: By conducting a network meta-analysis incorporating various behavioral tests and outcomes, this study provided a comprehensive evaluation of interventions for anxiety behavior measurement in rodents. Furthermore, use of the most appropriate, effective and fewest number of tests for animals is also important in terms of animal welfare.

Conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Addressing pitfalls in animal behavior measurement through refinement in anxiety studies with meta-analysis

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Aim: For the advancement of science and to ensure ethical acceptability, scientific validity, reproducibility, and translatability to the target species, it is imperative to prioritize animal welfare, health, and safety. Most of the scientist indicated that the environment of the animal (housing condition, lighting condition, cage condition, etc.) is very important for the normal behavior and cognition of the animal. Developing a refined approach that integrates various behavioral tests and outcomes, utilizing network meta-analysis to synthesize data across studies is should be our priority.

Methods: Meta- analysis compares the relative efficiency of two interventions or drugs based on direct evidence obtained from studies. For systematic review of meta-analysis, databases should be searched (PUBMED, Web of Science, Scopus, Science Direct and Online Library) for appropriate evidence as minimum. There was no restriction regarding the time of publication.

Outcomes: For the mostly used test “Open field”; total distance travelled and time in centre in stress and control group were compared by meta regression and it was investigated whether sex, species, lighting, etc. factors affect the results.

Conclusion: The environment in which animals are housed, including factors such as lighting and cage conditions, plays a crucial role in their behavior and cognitive functions. Prioritizing the development of refined approaches that integrate various behavioral tests and outcomes, supported by robust network meta-analyses, is essential. The analysis of commonly used tests, such as the Open Field test, highlights the importance of considering variables like sex, species, and lighting conditions in influencing outcomes.

Conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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Development of a modular fluid system to investigate the permeation of drugs from different BCS classes through an epithelial barrier to predict pharmacokinetics

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The development of novel drug formulations still relies on pharmacokinetic data generated by animal studies. Therefore, we developed a lab-on-desk system as an alternative to investigate and predict human pharmacokinetics.

The fluidic coupled multi-modular system combines 3D-printed modules that simulate liberation, absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion (LADME) of substances. According to the Biopharmaceutical Classification System (BCS) that differentiates drugs based on intestinal permeability and solubility, caffeine (BCS

I, high permeability) and sodium fluorescein (BCS III, low permeability) were evaluated. The transport over an epithelial barrier (Caco-2 cells) was simulated. Moreover, the barrier integrity was observed using transepithelial electrical resistance (TEER) measurements.

For sodium fluorescein, an apparent permeability coefficient (P_{app}) of $2.5 \cdot 10^{-7}$ cm/s under dynamic conditions and $3.5 \cdot 10^{-7}$ cm/s for static conditions (control) was observed. In contrast, a P_{app} value of $1 \cdot 10^{-5}$ cm/s for the transport of caffeine under dynamic conditions and a P_{app} value of $1.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ cm/s (control) showed a faster absorption for the BCS I drug. TEER measurements indicated an intact barrier.

In this study, the developed system demonstrated the permeability under dynamic conditions. Future steps will focus on the permeation of acyclovir (BCS III) and ibuprofen (BCS II) coupled with an automated oral dosage form release. Online TEER measurements will underline the cell barrier integrity. Furthermore, the pulmonary administration route will be focused. In conclusion, the more physiological environment could improve the *in vitro-in vivo* correlation and therefore the prediction of human pharmacokinetics.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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Interdisciplinary and multisectoral collaboration to stimulate acceptance of the virtual human platform for safety assessment (VHP4Safety)

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The VHP4Safety project aims to develop an *in silico* platform to assess the safety of chemicals and pharmaceuticals solely based on human biology, thus protecting human health without relying on animal studies. The project focuses on three case studies that represent human scenarios on chemical and pharmaceutical exposure affecting kidney function, neurodegeneration, and thyroid-mediated brain development. The development of the Virtual Human Platform (VHP) requires interdisciplinary collaboration involving various scientific disciplines, including data scientists, toxicologists,

epidemiologists and clinicians. They collaboratively build the VHP with services towards application for safety assessment assisting in, e.g., AOP development, PBPK and omics analysis, and feed the platform by integrating several data sources including *in vitro*, epidemiology and clinical data. To stimulate acceptance of the VHP, the project actively aligns the research efforts with end-users from various sectors, including regulatory institutes, industry and NGOs. We will present participatory research activities that focus on acceptance of the VHP. These rely on social sciences knowledge and methods from the field of innovation and transition studies. We will show results of a longitudinal ethnographic process study of the VHP4Safety platform as an innovation journey, with particular emphasis on how researchers interact with societal partners and create societal impact. These aspects are also examined in a document and interview-based analysis of 16 other European funded research projects that develop integrated data infrastructures for toxicology. Employing an innovation system approach and systemic design thinking these insights are contextualized within the broader transition towards animal-free and next generation risk assessment.

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Presentation: Oral

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From research and development to uptake of new approach methodologies (NAMs): A landscape approach

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The Implementation of New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) for regulatory safety assessment is a complex process, involving many steps and stakeholders. This hampers the implementation of NAMs in the regulatory arena. Hence, there is a need for overview of the steps required to implement NAMs for regulatory safety assessment. To this aim, we used a landscape approach to provide overview and facilitate the process from research and development to regulatory uptake of NAMs. Through interviews and workshops with experts, two landscapes NAMs were developed, one for chemical substances [1] and one for pharmaceutical products [2]. These landscapes map the steps and stakeholders involved, the initiatives undertaken and the trends observed towards NAM implementation. Both landscapes follow a similar path, starting with research and development, then validation or qualification and finally uptake in

international regulatory frameworks. However, there are different dynamics at play in the chemical versus pharmaceutical domain. For example, in the chemical domain a NAM should ideally cover a wide range of the chemical space, while for pharmaceutical application a NAM is often connected to a specific product (class), which affects the criteria for that NAM. In conclusion, these overviews provide an essential first step to facilitate the implementation of NAMs. They show similarities and differences between the chemical and pharmaceutical domain, suggesting tailored approaches towards stimulating uptake of NAMs in different regulatory contexts. Future research will explore this landscape approach for biomedical research, among others by spreading a survey among the biomedical community represented in the COST-Action IMPROVE network.

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Presentation: Oral

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Arrhythmogenic drug evaluation in a high throughput 3D cardiac microtissue system

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Background and purpose: Cardiac side effects are heavily considered in drug development and tools that efficiently examine proarrhythmic risk are required. In a previous study, we presented a microphysiological system (MPS) using hiPSC-derived cardiomyocytes (hiPSC-CM) to identify arrhythmia inducing compounds based on voltage, calcium and motion transients [1]. Here we demonstrate a 384-well platform that dramatically increases throughput without compromising physiological relevance provided by the 3D tissue structure.

Methods: Our MPS platform is fully compatible with automated workflows such as liquid handlers. Each well features a micro-patterned substrate where hiPSC-CM form uniaxially contracting microtissues. We studied the Comprehensive *in vitro* Proarrhyth-

mia Assay (CiPA: <https://cipaproject.org>) drug panel and obtained phenotypic fingerprints of all 28 compounds (9 low, 11 intermediate, 8 high arrhythmia risk). The analysis was augmented with a computational pipeline that inverts experimental biomarkers into a mathematical model of cellular currents to infer which ion channels are affected.

Results and conclusions: We accurately identified the arrhythmic potential for most of the CiPA compounds and *in silico* results had strong concordance with known channel block values. All high-risk compounds showed action potential duration (APD) prolongation coupled with action potential abnormalities or beat cessation. Nine of the 11 intermediate risk compounds caused APD prolongation alone or in combination with early afterdepolarizations while 2 others showed beat cessation or beat rate change. Overall, the 384-well cardiac MPS in combination with *in silico* analysis allows for fast (full workflow in 2 weeks) and relevant screening of arrhythmia risk at massively increased throughput.

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Conflict of interest

All authors have financial interest in Organos Inc.

Presentation: Oral

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Application of silicone flow bioreactors for dynamic cultivation of *in vitro* and *ex vivo* corneal models

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Malfunction of the cornea, the protective outer layer of the eye, is a major contributor to global blindness [1]. Various preclinical corneal research models, including *ex vivo* and *in vitro* cornea models, are used for drug development or unraveling pathomechanisms. Studies have demonstrated that dynamic cultivation of *ex vivo* cornea tissue improves the overall tissue quality [2,3]. However, its effect on corneal *in vitro* 3D models, typically cultured statically, is unclear. Therefore, we developed a bioreactor system allowing dynamic cultivation of corneal 3D models, including the incorporation of mechanical barriers, such as tear flow.

Flow bioreactors were developed using computer aided design (CAD) and manufactured from silicone allowing low-cost production and scalability. The designed bioreactor comprises two main components with lids enclosing an insert membrane mounted on a chip, which seals the two silicone parts and provides compartments

for apical and basolateral media circuits. Human immortalized corneal epithelial cells (hTCEpi) seeded on a membrane were transferred into the bioreactor to generate *in vitro* reconstructed corneal epithelium (RCE) models. RCE models cultured in the bioreactor showed multilayered epithelium with increased CK14 and Ki67 expression compared to statically cultivated RCE models. Transparent silicone lids enabled non-invasive morphological assessment via optical coherence tomography (OCT). Replacement of the chip by a ring further allowed for the cultivation of porcine *ex vivo* cornea tissue.

In conclusion, the created flow bioreactor provides an improved culture system for RCE models and prospectively will be used to for wound healing and permeability studies in a dynamic setting

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Presentation: Oral

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Digital twinning as an alternative to animal experimentation in the treatment planning of cardiac arrhythmias

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Cardiac arrhythmias can be fatal. A typical, minimally invasive, treatment is catheter-based ablation of the arrhythmogenic tissue. Despite being the gold standard, such procedure is not always resolute (30% of the treated patients present recurrence and require new treatment within 1-year) and can trigger dangerous complications like blood clotting and cardiac wall perforations.

Active research aims at enhancing safety and efficacy of the procedure, but technologies and protocols are still being devised and tested through animal experimentation, both *ex-vivo* (excised

hearts) and *in-vivo* (sedated animals). Besides the obvious care required in extrapolating the results of *ex-vivo* experiments to real life applications, major interspecies differences between animal and human hearts hamper the efficacy of the devised solutions.

In this talk, we present the results and ongoing research of the grant “Digital twins for presurgical assessment of cardiac ablation”, funded by FWF and BBWF in the 2021 call *Alternatives to Animal Experimentation* (P35374).

Digital twins of patient upper bodies are reconstructed with great detail from medical imaging data, and virtual therapies are performed through the computer simulation of complex mathematical models accounting for both the biophysics and mechanics of the procedure. This virtual catheterization provides a personalization framework for the assessment of safety and efficacy of a planned therapy. Moreover, the creation of a database of human upper bodies, will provide a new benchmark for the testing of new ablation protocols, or new catheter designs, greatly reducing, if not completely replacing, the large amount of animal experiments required by current practices.

Conflict of interest

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Presentation: Oral

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Multiscale and multimodal characterization of thymus structure and mechanics for biomimetic design approaches

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The thymus is the primary lymphoid organ responsible for the development and selection of T-cells. Developing accurate *in vitro* models of the organ for stem cell therapies requires recapitulating the complex thymic extracellular matrix [1]. To date, the organization of the matrix's 3D mesh structure and mechanical properties of this organ have been poorly investigated, for instance, its viscoelastic behavior is still unknown [2].

In this work, a mechanical characterization of the bovine thymus (from a local slaughterhouse) was performed through indentation and bulk stress-relaxation tests, bulk compressive tests, shear tests

and dynamic mechanical analysis. A generalized Maxwell model was used to derive the instantaneous and equilibrium elastic modulus (E_{inst} and E_{eq} , respectively), as well as the characteristic relaxation time (τ). As regards indentations, maps outlined sample anisotropy, which is likely associated with cortical and medullar regions of the thymus – as also reported by microscopy. More specifically, throughout the entire tested area, values ranged between 3.5 and 36.9 kPa (E_{inst}), 0.8 and 10.1 kPa (E_{eq}), 7.9 and 17.7 s (τ).

Thymic tissue was also characterized in terms of its microstructure, using scanning electron microscopy and confocal microscopy. Furthermore, a histological analysis was performed to visualize nuclear content and tissue microstructure.

Improving the design of *in-vitro* tools through biomimetic approaches is in-line with the 3Rs concept. Moreover, recycling waste tissues from the food industry promotes the concept of a circular economy and contributes to the reduction of animals employed in research.

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Presentation: Oral

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Valuing testing: Understanding societal and stakeholder perspectives in developing and validating animal-free models for toxicological studies

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The Valuing Testing project aims to explore societal and stakeholder perspectives in developing and validating animal-free models for toxicological studies. The transition to animal-free models is social as much as technical, requiring new competences and modes of inquiry to navigate uncertainty and produce usable knowledge. Although far from ideal, the culture and practice of animal models has been integrated into a testing regime that has overseen chemical safety assessment through long-standing protocols typically shared and agreed across industry and regulators and with the minimal participation of citizens. Transitioning to a new regime of chemi-

cal safety assessment, including the regulatory adoption of new approach methodologies (NAMs), raises ontological, epistemological and sociopolitical questions. What are the epistemic challenges for animal testing to be reevaluated as a gold standard in regulatory practice? In what ways do the mechanistic models underpinning NAMs produce different kinds of uncertainty? How do regulators, academic scientists, citizens and other stakeholders including industry evaluate these uncertainties? Are there distinct epistemic cultures between academic and regulatory science? Do NAMs offer a technological solution to a societal problem? Do citizens support this technofix? What are the societal problems in the first place (animal experimentation, protection-production complex)? Is the problem one of producing more data or less chemicals? Can toxicity be understood as an uncertain encounter among beings, systems, and things, rather than as an inherent property of particular substances? We will conduct empirical research with scientists, regulators, industry and citizens through ethnography, semi-structured interviews, stakeholder workshops and a citizen jury.

Conflict of interest

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Presentation: Oral

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Emerging networks in Berlin: Charité 3^R, *Der Simulierte Mensch* and Einstein Center 3R

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With numerous research institutes, Berlin is a vibrant hub for biomedical research. Since 2018, three significant 3R research initiatives have emerged, driven by networked scientists and supported by financial and political backing. These initiatives recognize the potential of modern alternative methods in advancing basic biomedical research and translation.

Charité – Universitätsmedizin Berlin established Charité 3^R to embed the 3Rs within its science community. Together with TU Berlin, Charité will open a new research building, *Der Simulierte Mensch* in 2025. Additionally, in 2021, Berlin's universities and

non-university partners launched the Einstein Center 3R, enhancing the city's 3R activities through networking, communication, training, and research on robust 3D cell culture models.

Charité 3^R operates on three fronts: promoting scientific and political communication about animal experiments and alternatives, providing education and support to advance the 3Rs, and funding research in all 3R areas.

Der Simulierte Mensch will be a joint research center of TU Berlin and Charité, featuring interdisciplinary projects aimed at simulating human physiology from subcellular to organ/organoid level. It will also include two publicly accessible floors dedicated to science communication and outreach.

The Einstein Center 3R (EC3R) aims to strengthen Berlin's 3R efforts by fostering collaboration and innovation in developing high-quality new approach methodologies (NAMs) for biomedicine.

While animal models remain relevant for certain biomedical inquiries, Charité 3^R emphasizes refinement efforts to enhance their ethical use.

These interconnected initiatives are poised to significantly bolster Berlin's status as a leading science location by expanding scientific perspectives, encouraging spin-offs, and pursuing international cooperation.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Rat Trap: A popular science book about the limitations of animal research and the technologies available to replace it

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A great deal of evidence has accumulated over the last two decades on both the scientific limitations of animal research and the potential of human biology-based approaches for the generation of safe and effective treatments. Although scientists working within this field are familiar with the evidence, much of the general public still regard animal research as a “necessary evil”. “*Rat Trap: The capture of medicine by animal research – and how to break free*” is a popular science book that aims to make this evidence accessible to a non-scientific, lay readership. Published in August 2023, it is firmly rooted in up-to-date scientific evidence, but engages the reader with stories, conversations with experts and the author’s experiences.

The book begins by investigating how the practice of using animals as “models” for humans started, exploring how use of the experimental method helped raise the professional status of physiology and medicine and showing how the practice of using animals in science quickly flourished, with industries springing up to support the enterprise. The second part of the book discusses the limitations of using animals as “models” for humans, covering flaws in the methodology and scientific underpinnings of the paradigm, and the impact of this on humans. The third part explores our many options for animal free science, including clinical trials, epidemiology, AI, *in silico* modelling, organoids, organs-on-a-chip, systems biology, early detection and personalised medicine. Finally, the obstacles to change are explored, including regulations, funding, institutional lock-in and resistance from those using animals in research.

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Conflict of interest

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Presentation: Oral

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Myelin matters: Development of a human stem cell-based peripheral myelin toxicity assay for regulatory testing

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A fast, cost-efficient, and human-relevant evaluation of adult peripheral neurotoxicity of substances, which may harm humans, is urgently needed.

As member of the Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC), we aim to develop a human stem cell-based peripheral myelin toxicity assay to investigate the potential toxic-

ity of chemicals on myelin as part of an adult neurotoxicity *in vitro* test system. Myelin toxicity is a critical mode of action that affects peripheral sensory and motor functions. The PeriMyelinTox assay will not only provide an efficient assessment of myelin toxicity, but will also consider regulatory requirements.

Based on established methods, human induced pluripotent stem cells (hiPSCs) are used to differentiate into mature motor neurons and Schwann cells. We hypothesize that co-culture of these cells in 3D and in 2D configurations allows myelin formation and visualization. Currently, we are focusing on evaluation of defined cultivation time and conditions, as well as the composition ratios of cell types to enable reproducible myelin formation. Immunocytochemical analysis of myelin marker proteins and neurite staining should allow localization and quantification of myelin formation. In addition, to optimize the method further, we evaluate the use of xeno-free, chemically defined culture components. This improves consistency and reproducibility and enhances the suitability of this method for its intended use as an assay for regulatory assessment. After establishing the assay, we are studying a compound set to identify potential toxic substances, contributing to a more comprehensive and effective neurotoxicity test battery for regulatory use.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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hiPSC differentiating into renal proximal tubular cells are more sensitive to nephrotoxins and oxidants than iPSC and iPSC differentiated into renal proximal tubular cells

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Kidney proximal tubular epithelial cells (PTEC) are constantly exposed to toxic metabolites and oxidants. The kidney has the potential to regenerate after injury either by stem cell differentiation or by restoring proliferation in PTEC. Still, it is known that kidney function declines, suggesting that damaged cells are not replaced by fully functional cells. To understand this loss of renal cell function, we study the impact of toxins on tubular differentiation processes.

Human induced pluripotent stem cells (hiPSC) were differentiated into PTEC-like cells (PTELC). Proliferation, apoptosis, senes-

cence, expression of DNA repair genes, oxidative defence genes, renal cell function and epithelial to mesenchymal transition (EMT) were analyzed in hiPSC, differentiating cells and differentiated cells treated with cisplatin, cyclosporin A and oxidants.

PTELC showed typical morphological features of PTEC and increased expression of renal markers after 9 days of differentiation. DNA repair and antioxidant defence genes were most downregulated in differentiating cells compared to hiPSC and PTELC. Accordingly, differentiating cells were the most sensitive to cisplatin and oxidative stress. Oxidative stress and cisplatin induced apoptosis at all differentiation stages, and cyclosporine A also induced senescence. EMT was most strongly induced by cyclosporin A, followed by cisplatin, while the oxidizing agents did not upregulate EMT markers to a relevant extent. Treatment during differentiation with cisplatin and cyclosporin A reduced the uptake function of the differentiated PTELC drastically, while the oxidants had differing effects.

Our results suggest that differentiating cells are highly sensitive to various noxae, which could negatively affect regenerative processes.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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***In silico-in vitro* design of biomimetic alveolar models for high-throughput inhalation tests**

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The rise in lung diseases has driven the development of human-relevant models for inhalation studies. However, animal models are still widely employed since current *in vitro* models struggle with replicating alveolar curvature and breathing. To address this, we introduce an *in silico-in vitro* framework for designing a multiscale fluidic platform capable of replicating the mechano-architectural features of the alveolar barrier by incorporating 3D transparent curved membranes, breathing, physiological air and blood dynamics.

The optimal material composition to mimic lung mechanical properties was identified through computational modelling. 3D membranes were fabricated by casting agarose-gelatin solutions in custom PDMS moulds. They were then stabilised with mi-

crobial transglutaminase, dried, sterilised, and rehydrated. Their mechanical, functional, and biological properties were assessed before integration into multiscale fluidic platforms fabricated via stereolithography. Air and blood dynamics in alveoli were also computed to identify physiological shear stress conditions as well as air inlet pressure to achieve physiological breathing deformation. Fluorophore-labelled CaP nanoparticles (NPs) were finally aerosolised onto 2D and 3D membranes seeded with A549 cells for preliminary translocation studies. The membranes were highly stretchable and outperformed Transwell controls in A549 barrier tightness and transport characteristics. NP translocation was lower in the 3D geometry. Integrating 3D curved membranes into multiscale fluidic platforms enhances the reliability of *in vitro* inhalation studies, offering an alternative to animal testing. We will further evaluate innovative dynamic conditions replicating breathing muscle actuation, advancing toxicology research and providing novel insights into lung diseases and drug delivery.

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Presentation: Oral

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Patient-specific assays to identify and characterize new drugs for chronic wound therapy

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Chronic human skin wounds, e.g., venous ulcers, arterial ulcers, pressure ulcers or diabetic foot ulcers, are a major health issue worldwide with 10-20 million patients in Western countries alone. Drug development for chronic wounds is hampered by the lack of translatability from preclinical animal models to patients. Despite attempts to mimic certain underlying pathologies, e.g., diabetes, ischemia, inflammation or infection in rodent or pig models, they do not reflect the complexity of human chronic wounds [1,2].

Exudates of non-healing wounds contain the drivers of pathogenicity. We utilized wound exudates to develop wound-specific, cell-based functional biomarker assays [3]. Human dermal fibroblast proliferation in 2D and 3D systems served as readouts to a) differentiate between healing and non-healing wounds, b) follow

the healing process of individual patients, and c) assess the effects of therapeutics for chronic wounds *ex vivo*. We observed a strong correlation between wound chronicity and inhibitory effects of individual exudates on fibroblast proliferation. Transition of a clinically non-healing to a healing phenotype restored fibroblast proliferation and extracellular matrix formation while reducing inflammatory cytokine production. Moreover, two wound therapeutics yielded responses in line with clinical experience. This *ex vivo* model could in the future replace chronic wound healing experiments in animals.

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Conflict of interest

BW and AS are co-founders and PD, NS and GC are employees of Akribes Biomedical GmbH.

Presentation: Oral

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Synthetic fibrous scaffold-based 3D small intestinal mucosa *in vitro* model

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Regulatory developments and differences in drug response between species shift testing methods more and more from performing animal studies towards the use of human cell-based tissue models. Especially in the context of bioavailability of orally administered drugs, *in vitro* test systems mimicking the intestinal tract to a high degree are needed. Unfortunately, most current tissue equivalents and even new developments are assembled by animal materials as scaffold material such as collagen or decellularized tissue or based on a simple, semipermeable membrane which is of synthetic nature. Therefore, modern synthetic scaffold materials which are bioactive and representative for the biomimetic structure of the native tissue would have massively impact on organ/tissue function *in vitro*. In

this context, we present here a porous fibrous scaffold that is seeded with primary enteroid-derived intestinal epithelial cells to be compliant with the 3R principle.

A conventional electrospinning process was modified by the combination with porogens, resulting in a highly porous scaffold. For the setup of small intestinal *in vitro* test systems, they were seeded with small intestinal stromal tissue cells (hiF) for 2 weeks. Fibroblasts were able to rearrange the fibrous structure and led to the synthesis of ECM. Subsequently, primary enteroids were seeded as single cells on the respective scaffolds, forming a confluent epithelial cell layer after 10 days [1,2]. Epithelial integrity was investigated by FITC-dextran (4kDa) as well as transepithelial electrical resistance (TEER) measurements. In addition, a high comparability to the *in vivo* tissue was demonstrated by histological analyses and bioavailability studies.

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Presentation: Oral

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Effect of nephro- and hepatotoxins on precision cut tissue slices as a potential 3R-compliant method to assess organ toxicity

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For the investigation of organ toxicity under the 3R principle, cell culture, co-cultures or even organoids are not sufficient to seize the high complexity of whole organs. *Ex vivo* cultivation of precision cut tissue slices (PCTS) could act as a link between the classical *in vitro* and *in vivo* systems, reflecting the complex organ anatomy and the interplay of different cell types and allowing kinetic analyses while lowering the animal numbers.

PCTS of liver (PCLS) and kidney (PCKS) were incubated with known organ toxins and analyzed after different time points. Viabil-

ity assays were performed to determine IC_{50} values and compared with IC_{50} values measured in kidney and liver cell cultures.

Treatment with the hepatotoxin acetaminophen resulted in a dose-dependent loss of viability of PCLS and PCKS. While the IC_{50} values of PCKS and cultured kidney cells were comparable, the values of PCLS and cultured liver cells differed tremendously, with PCLS being much more sensitive. The same was observed after treatment with the nephrotoxin cyclosporin A, which also exhibits acute toxicity to the liver. When comparing different viability assays, the MTT assay proved to be more robust but less sensitive than the quantification of ATP levels.

In conclusion, in the assays used here, PCLS proved to be much more sensitive than cultured liver cells, while PCKS were as sensitive as cultured kidney cells. Both the MTT and ATP viability assays showed too much variation, which is why better endpoints need to be found for a further reduction in animal numbers.

Conflict of interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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Modeling glioblastoma: From primary tumors to relapse and the use of post-mortem samples for translational research

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In recent years, advancements in the diagnosis, treatment, and prognosis of intrinsic brain tumors, including glioblastoma, the most prevalent malignant brain tumor in adults, have been notably constrained. The lack of clinically meaningful new treatments is largely due to fundamental gaps in our understanding of tumor biology and pathogenesis, compounded by the lack of robust *in vitro* biological models and timely translation to clinical trials.

Biopsy specimens or surgical resections are often unable to capture the spatial or temporal heterogeneity inherent in glioblastoma. In addition, recurrences, which are of considerable value for histo-

logical and molecular profiling, often remain out of surgical reach due to patients' compromised health status or widespread dissemination of the tumor.

Our research group has succeeded in establishing five continuously proliferating cell lines out of ten primary glioblastoma patients, four of which demonstrated growth in *in vivo* models. Additionally, we cultivated samples from two recurrences in two patients.

All cell lines were then comprehensively characterised, including quality controls, doubling time, phenotypic analysis, CD133 expression, molecular pathological profiling and comparison to parental tumour tissue. In addition, mutation analysis was performed and finally tumourigenicity was tested. To simulate the terminal phase of the disease, we succeeded in establishing a metastatic glioblastoma model 48 hours post mortem. It is particularly noteworthy that post-mortem glioblastoma samples offer a unique opportunity to study the disease in its final stage.

Leveraging these models, we can delineate crucial clinical milestones such as primary disease onset, recurrence, and end-stage progression, pivotal for translational research endeavors.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Promoting applied 3Rs research – Insights from Switzerland

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This talk underscores the critical role of funding in advancing the implementation of the 3R principle (replacement, reduction, and refinement) in animal research, drawing attention to the Swiss 3Rs Competence Centre's funding approach as a model for promoting applied 3Rs research. By providing financial support for projects focused on developing comprehensive strategies to replacing, reducing and refining animal experimentation in specific areas of high concern, we aim to foster innovation for the purpose of ad-

vancing 3Rs methodologies. Through targeted funding, we can empower researchers to innovate and elevate the profile of 3Rs research, ultimately driving positive change in the scientific community and beyond.

Lacking resources for learning new 3R approaches is often considered a major hurdle in implementation. Through our 3Rs Support Grants we provide the crucial financial support needed to take established 3Rs methods into active practice either by promoting training and dissemination, or by peer-to-peer lab exchanges that facilitate knowledge transfer.

Additionally, our funding initiatives create incentives for Swiss researchers to prioritize 3R research, leading to increased awareness and hopefully also adoption of 3R methods.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Animal-free biomimetic fibrous scaffolds for the setup of 3D multi-layered epithelial models

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The stromal part is a key element of current tissue equivalents as an alternative for animal experimentation. Due to the lack of synthetic alternatives, most researchers rely on animal derived materials such as collagen [1]. However, besides ethical concerns, these scaffolds show batch-to-batch variances together with increased costs. Suitable synthetic 3D scaffold materials have to fulfill several challenges, like being bioactive, highly porous or biomimetic [2]. Here we present the generation of highly porous fibrous scaffolds with subsequent cellular biologization, resulting in synthetic-based 3D scaffolds used for a wide variety of current tissue models consisting of connective tissue and epithelium.

Polyamide-6-based scaffolds were generated by modified electrospinning process. The resulting scaffolds were biologized with human stromal tissue cells (fibroblasts). After 1-4 weeks of migration, proliferation, differentiation and matrix synthesis, the resulting human ECM tissue was combined with epithelial cells or tumor cells to form monolayered, multi-layered or hierarchically structured tissues.

Our newly developed scaffolds allow cellular migration of primary human fibroblasts as well as dynamic rearrangement of the fibers, which results in homogeneously populated scaffolds together with tissue specific ECM components. Through the combination with human epithelial cells (e.g., intestine, airway) or tumor cells we generated physiological and functional models of airways, intestine and tumor demonstrated by a representative cellular composition, infection process, barrier integrity as well as cell polarization. Taken together, our modular principle generated a platform technology which can address a diversity of current tissue models and enables replacement of animal derived materials.

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Presentation: Poster

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A replacement approach to animal models for the toxicity evaluation of autogenous vaccines

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Autogenous veterinary vaccines represent a tool for the prevention of infectious diseases. In particular, this approach is both part of the plan to prevent antibiotic resistance and, at the same time, from a One Health and animal welfare perspective [1]. Vaccines must undergo a series of efficacy and safety checks, partly carried out with *in vivo* tests [2]. According to EU Pharmacopeia some *in vivo* assays, such as the abnormal toxicity test (ATT), are obsolete or not in line with current biotechnological advances.

This study aimed to investigate the feasibility of an *in vitro* cytotoxicity assay: ATP Cell Viability Assay (ATP) as a replacement for the ATT. Furthermore, a comparison with the better-known MTT test (MTT) was carried out.

Both methods are based on the use of a cell culture as a toxicity detection system. The MTT is cheaper and frequently used, while

the ATP is more advanced and allows the measurement of *in vitro* toxicity with high precision [3]. To perform the test, cells were seeded in 96-well plates at different densities, vaccines were tested starting from the original material and up to 1:64 dilution and incubated with cell culture for 24 h before proceeding with the absorbance (MTT) or luminescence (ATP) analysis.

The results showed that the vaccines were cytotoxic when tested at the highest concentrations. In most cases, slower viability values were recorded with the ATP. This is because the ATP is able to yield lower and more accurate values while MTT relatively overestimates the viability.

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Presentation: Poster

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Innovation in action: Collaboration between the Austrian 3R Center and government initiatives

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In the following we summarize the work of the Austrian 3R center with significant support from the federal government. The first work package “Dissemination of knowledge on 3R topics” encompasses several key initiatives aimed at advancing knowledge dissemination in the field of the 3Rs, including: i.) 3R Lecture Series. Which serves as a cornerstone for knowledge dissemination within the scientific community. These lectures provide a platform for researchers, practitioners, and stakeholders to share insights, advancements, and best practices related to the 3Rs. Through expert presentations

and interactive sessions, participants gain a deeper understanding of the principles and applications of 3Rs across various domains. ii.) Organization of 3R Days. 3R Days serve as focal points for raising awareness and fostering dialogue on 3R principles and practices. These events bring together professionals from academia, industry, and regulatory bodies to discuss emerging challenges, innovative approaches. iii.) Establishment of a 3R Information Dissemination Network within the Austrian Scientific Landscape: Building a robust information dissemination network. By utilizing existing networks and establishing new collaborations. iv.) Creation of an Educational Platform for 3R Training: Education and training play a pivotal role in promoting the adoption of the 3R principle. This platform will offer a comprehensive suite of online courses, workshops, and resources tailored to the needs of researchers, students, and laboratory personnel involved in animal-based research.

By advancing these initiatives, we aim to elevate awareness, promote collaboration, and empower stakeholders to embrace the 3R principle as an integral component of ethical and scientifically rigorous research practices.

Conflict of interest

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Presentation: Poster

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JSAAE activities toward the formation of the Asian Federation

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After the establishment in 1989, the Japanese Society for Alternatives to Animal Experiments (JSAAE) has been promoting 3Rs research in Japan through a wide variety of activities. While we have annual scientific meetings, publish the official journal, AATEX, open practical seminars on various alternative methods for the domestic 3Rs, we have been developing international cooperation with EU-SAAT, ESTIV and ASCCT as well as Asian counterparts, KSAAE in Korea, SAAE-I in India and TATT in China (Society of Toxicological

Alternatives and Translational Toxicology, Chinese Society of Toxicology). First Asian Congress was held in Saga, Japan in 2016, then it has been continued by Chinese Society in Guangzhou, China in 2018 (2nd), by KSAAE in Jeju Island, Korea in 2022 (3rd) and by SAAE-I in Delhi, India, December 2024 (4th). On the basis of these efforts, we agreed to establish Asian Federation of Societies for Alternatives to Animal Experiments (AFSAAE) in the coming 4th Asian Congress in Delhi. The missions of AFSAAE are to support this Asian Congress series and to establish an official scientific journal in the future. Also, we highly recognize the importance of the communication among the young generations in Asian countries and to ensure the sustainable development of the 3Rs research and their implementation in this area.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Integration of the blood-brain barrier and brain organoids in a modular microfluidic platform for sensor-based analysis in drug screening and disease modeling applications

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Over the years, *in vitro* blood-brain barrier (BBB) models have transitioned from initial two-dimensional (2D) static setups to today's three-dimensional (3D) dynamic microfluidic chips. This evolution towards more *in vivo*-like tissue is improving cellular interactions but complicating device handling, particularly for long-term cultures such as brain organoids, thus increasing errors and costs. For a biologically relevant setup, brain organoids need to interact with a functional BBB consisting of brain vascular endothelial cells, astrocytes and pericytes. We propose a modular device for separate fabrication and culture of BBB and brain organoids, streamlining the process while ensuring quality control of each tissue component prior to assembly.

The presented device has two main components: the brain unit, a single 3D-printed module, and the BBB unit, a 3D-printed part with media reservoirs, an upper channel, a porous membrane with

impedance electrodes, and a lower PDMS channel, that effectively seals the system when tightened with six screws. After seeding, quality control of both units will ensure that functional BBB and brain organoids are assembled to create the final modular device.

This setup will enhance currently existing modular BBB models [1,2] by integrating 3D-printing technology for simplified production and scalability while allowing the integration of complex tissues like organoids. Additionally, integrated biosensing on the BBB membrane is particularly suitable for high-throughput drug screening with precise control over culture conditions and medium flow, compared to conventional Transwell models. This innovation improves usability, contributing to better disease models and personalized medicine applications.

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Conflict of interest

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Presentation: Poster

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Autologous co-culture tumor models: Novel therapeutic approaches for clear cell sarcoma

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Clear cell sarcomas (CCS) are rare, aggressive soft tissue tumors that primarily affect young adults and have poor prognosis particularly in metastatic stages. The lack of models has hampered the development of effective treatments. Recently we successfully established a primary tumor, a cancer-associated fibroblast (CAF), a metastatic, and skin fibroblast cell line from the same patient, creating an autologous CCS tumor model, reflecting various phenotypic stages of CCS and allowing reconstruction of the microenvironment for *in vitro* testing's without the use of excessive animal models [1].

In a functional drug screening followed by comprehensive *in vitro* validation using 3D spheroids of the new model, three top candidates showed the highest potential for clinical translation based on their efficacy in reducing cell viability: lurbinectedin, panobinostat and selinexor. Especially, lurbinectedin emerged as the best candidate inducing cell death in a subnanomolar range. Transcriptional analysis of lurbinectedin treated CCS cells revealed a substantial number of dysregulated genes only in metastatic but not in primary CCS, indicating a distinct mode of action for lurbinectedin based on each phenotype. To improve the therapeutic strategy, the combination of lurbinectedin and selinexor was tested revealing synergism between the two drugs in single-cell cultures as well as co-cultivation systems multicellular 3D models, which were generated by co-cultivation of tumor cells and fibroblasts.

The findings of the study support the potential of combination therapies and advanced modeling techniques to improve outcomes for CCS patients and highlight the importance of integrating functional drug testing into modern precision oncology.

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Conflict of interest

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Presentation: Poster

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The novel monoclonal human alveolar epithelial cell line “Arlo” for modeling the pulmonary air-blood barrier *in vitro*

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In vitro models of the deep lung are important tools for investigating the healthy and diseased state of the respiratory tract. The alveolar epithelium comprises type-1 and type-2 alveolar cells that form a tight barrier to protect the organism from pathogens and toxins. However, this barrier can be compromised under pathophysiological conditions like infections with SARS-CoV-2, Influenza A, or bacteria.

Disease-relevant *in vitro* models are a great alternative to overcome limitations and replace animal- and human *ex vivo* models to study the (patho)-physiology and its diseases and to evaluate safety and efficacy of drugs. While primary human alveolar epithelial cells (hAEPc) are often considered as the best representation of deep lung cells, cell lines offer promising alternatives due to their accessibility and reproducibility. Unfortunately, most available cell

lines are unsuitable for many applications due to their lack of barrier properties. To address this need, we immortalized hAEPc and established the hAELVi cell line, which we then improved via single-cell printing to generate the monoclonal cell line “Arlo” [1,2]. Arlo exhibits pronounced and reproducible barrier properties, strict monolayer formation, and TEER values of approximately 3000 $\Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$.

- 1) To demonstrate the suitability of Arlo for modeling the air-blood-barrier, we are currently investigating Arlo in the following aspects:
- 2) Alveolar-specific drug permeability
- 3) Proteome and transcriptome analysis to identify lung-related barrier-determining factors
- 4) *In vitro* pulmonary edema model as screening tool for drug candidates

Overall, Arlo is a promising and versatile cellular tool for human disease modeling, drug efficacy testing, and fundamental research.

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Presentation: Oral

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Why do drugs keep failing? A systematic analysis of drug failure rates from 1963 to 2017

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Drug efficacy, safety, bioavailability, and other pivotal drug properties are routinely assessed in animals throughout preclinical trials. However, the high attrition rates during clinical drug assessment raise the question whether current animal-intensive practices are adequate to test drugs for human use. Here, we expand upon our previous work by performing a systematic analysis of new drug

candidates' clinical attrition rates and the reasons for their failure. After screening 2,147 PubMed entries, we extracted data from more than 30 scientific publications containing drug failure rates or reasons for failure for more than 50 partially overlapping periods between 1963 and 2017. This broad landscape analysis identifies some concerning trends: the overall clinical drug attrition was at its lowest in the 1980s and has continuously risen in the following three decades, reaching and sustaining its highest levels so far between 2000 and 2017. Furthermore, we show that biological reasons such as safety and efficacy issues, classically assessed in animal trials throughout nonclinical drug evaluation, constitute approximately 77% of causes for drug attrition. Taken together, our systematic analysis provides a detailed overview of the drug failure trends and reasons for failure between 1963 and 2017. The fact that drug failure has remained at its highest level since 2000 despite the overall scientific and technological advances strongly suggests that the current animal-based preclinical assessment systems cannot reliably predict human reactions. Our findings indicate that the integration of more human-relevant systems into drug development is urgently needed to improve preclinical predictability and drug success rates.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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3DTransfect – Multi-scale drug-target validation by transfected 3D cell cultures

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3D models are increasingly used to replace animal models or least to reduce the number of animal experiments. They significantly contribute to early decision making in drug development by being widely used for chemical screening. In order to ensure specificity of drug candidates, the results need to be validated by genetic manipulations of drug targets. These, so called, drug-gene matches frequently require gene silencing or over-expression, that, in turn,

rely on effective intracellular delivery of RNAs, DNAs or proteins. One of the most widely used cargo delivery methods is transfection that is still challenging in a 3D-setup. To improve the efficiency and reliability of transfection-based methods in spheroids and the subsequent comparison with drug effects, we combine the expertise of experimental and computational groups with the aim to create a modelling-driven platform for drug-gene matches in transfected 3D systems. We aim to build 2D and 3D computational models encompassing the transport, uptake, diffusion and endosomal release of different cargo molecules. Our work aims to enhance correct decision making at early stages of drug development, thereby, implementing the 3R principle. We believe, that our platform leads to a reduction of the number of animal tests and refinement of the necessary experiments by sorting out unspecific compounds with adverse effects.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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RE-Place: A tool to stimulate the use of new approach methodologies in Belgium

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New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) encompassing *in vitro*, *in chemico* or *in silico* methods can play a pivotal role in replacing or reducing the use of laboratory animals. Despite their promising potential, the fast and continuous development of NAMs makes it difficult to access relevant, reliable and up to date information.

Therefore, the RE-Place project was launched in Belgium in order to collect the available expertise on NAMs in one central open access database. This database, available at www.re-place.be, links each NAM to the name of a scientist and an organisation involved

in its development or application. This link considerably facilitates the transfer of expertise and the connection between peers within the field.

From the launch of the project in 2017 until May 2024, 280 methods have been submitted to the database by 182 experts from 33 Belgian organisations. The majority of the methods are *in vitro* methods, probably due to the development of stem cells technologies and 3D models. These methods are also situated in basic and applied research.

Another key aspect of the RE-Place project is the dissemination of knowledge about recent advancements in the field of NAMs through various channels (website, newsletters, social media, webinars). As such, RE-Place constitutes an important tool to facilitate the exchange of information and know-how on NAMs. Ultimately, RE-Place aims to accelerate the adoption of these methods on a broader scale, contributing to the long-term goal of reducing and replacing animal testing.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Autologous co-culture tumor models: Novel therapeutic approaches for cholangiocarcinoma

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Cholangiocarcinoma (CCA) is a cancer of the bile duct system in the liver characterized by its desmoplastic and hypervascularized tumor microenvironment, primarily consisting of tumor cells and cancer-associated fibroblasts (CAFs). CAFs play a central role in CCA tumor progression, angiogenesis, metastasis, and the development of therapy resistance.

Recently, we developed a new model system (MUG CCArly) that mimics the desmoplastic microenvironment typical of CCA [1]. This enables long-term experiments to be conducted with tumor cells and CAFs in co-culture systems isolated from one patient. The focus of this study is on establishing innovative therapies in the field of cationic antitumor peptides. These peptides, derived from the human host defense peptide lactoferricin [2], exhibit selectivity against various cancer cells by targeting the negatively charged

lipid phosphatidylserine (PS), which is specifically exposed on the outer leaflet of the plasma membrane in cancer cells [3,4]. The peptides D22, RDP22, RDP34, RDP215, and 9D-RDP215 were tested on the MUG CCArly cell line, corresponding CAFs, and co-culture model, with the IC50 concentration determined by means of PI uptake. Zeta potential measurements verify the binding to the cell surface through changes in membrane potential.

In summary, all used peptides selectively target the tumor cell line, as evidenced by the at least double (2.0-5.4-fold) IC50 concentration for non-tumorigenic cells. Finally, 9D-RDP215 was selected as the most effective and promising peptide for a new treatment strategy that can improve and support the current therapy strategies.

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Presentation: Poster

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Animal-free optimization of energy delivery in cardiac radiofrequency ablation: A virtual human study

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Radiofrequency ablation (RFA) is a minimally invasive procedure used to treat abnormal electrical signals that cause cardiac arrhythmia. During RFA, the tip electrode of a catheter delivers radiofrequency current at a frequency of 500 kHz. Electrical current flows through the resistive volume, which includes myocardial tissue and blood, and it reaches a dispersive patch positioned on the patient's skin, typically on the back or thigh. Our research aims to surpass the need for animal experiments currently used to devise and optimize

protocols by developing highly realistic *in-silico* models of human patients in terms of anatomy and physiology. To achieve this, we use patient imaging data to create a comprehensive 3D model. We produce detailed segmentations using 3D Slicer software, encompassing not only the heart but also taking into account surrounding structures such as the lungs, esophagus, and liver. In this talk, we present a virtual patient whose upper body has been segmented into 36 uniquely labeled subdomains, each exhibiting heterogeneous conductivity.

Additionally, we discretize the multi-label subdomains into an unstructured tetrahedral mesh.

We position an electrode on the myocardium of the left atrium in proximity to the pulmonary vein, a typical occurrence in the clinic.

A dispersive patch is placed at various positions on the torso.

We examine the impact of the patch location on both tissue power dissipation and the power dissipation within the entire torso geometry. Our study sheds light on optimal patch placement strategies to maximize lesion efficacy.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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Rumination behavior as an animal-based indicator in sheep

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Sheep are crucial in applied and translational research. Assessing their stress and health is challenging since they often hide signs of pain and distress. Rumination duration and frequency have been reported as indicators of potential stress, by otherwise normal behavior. Painful interventions [1], social isolation [2], heat stress [3], and transportation stress [4] reduce rumination time, also the proportion of rumination while standing or lying was reported as reliable stress indicator [5].

This study aimed to identify which behaviors (rumination, idling/resting, eating) change most in response to low stressors (separation and relocation) and to test a new tri-accelerometer-sensor for monitoring these behaviors. A 24-hour baseline of sheep behavior was established through visual observation. In two trials, two sheep were separated and relocated, and their behaviors were observed again. A t-test compared the mean durations of these behaviors in familiar versus unfamiliar settings. The accuracy and reliability of the sensor data were also assessed. Also, the proportion of time sheep spent performing a behavior in standing versus lying position was assessed.

Rumination changed the most in response to relocation (decreased by 45.6% $P < 0.0009$). Resting/idling increased by 47.9% ($P < 0.003$), and eating decreased by 36.2% ($P < 0.041$). However, rumination while standing did not significantly indicate stress.

These results align with prior studies on severe stressors, suggesting that rumination duration is a useful indicator, even for mild stress. Further research is needed to confirm rumination's reliability as a welfare indicator in various contexts, including laboratory and farm settings. Sensor-based systems for detecting rumination could facilitate continuous welfare monitoring.

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Conflict of interest

Author Sven Schmidt was employed by the company BITSz Electronics GmbH, and author Tanja Schmidt was employed at Nuvisan ICB GmbH. The remaining authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Pathways to regulatory acceptance of new approach methodologies for endocrine-disrupting chemicals

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Endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs) are a class of chemicals increasingly linked to human health concerns, leading to societal pressures to strengthen risk governance approaches. Currently, strategies for risk assessment of endocrine disrupting properties rely on invasive animal models. These models are ethically debated and have limited translatability to humans. Therefore, the research community strives to develop animal-free testing strategies for EDCs. However, this effort faces considerable challenges, many of which relate to regulatory acceptance and use of animal-free models by

regulators, academics and industry. In the transdisciplinary AFARA project, social sciences and humanities (SSH) scholars from ethics, law, innovation and transition studies collaborate with toxicologists to facilitate the pathways to regulatory acceptance of animal-free models for endocrine disruption. We present various SSH research activities that shed light on the functioning of the risk governance system for EDCs and the pathways for accepting, implementing, and using animal-free models for EDC identification. First, a legal analysis of the EU legislative framework and regulatory decision-making for EDC identification with and without the use of animals. Second, an interview-based study about roles, responsibilities and strategies of stakeholders in advancing models for EDC identification from research and development to regulatory acceptance. Third, dialogues with various stakeholders and citizens to discuss moral problems and value trade-offs implicated in (not) advancing animal-free testing strategies for EDC identification. These activities contribute to developing an actionable understanding of how risk governance systems can accommodate societal concerns relating to endocrine disruption and transition to accelerate uptake of animal-free innovations.

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The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Use of public transcriptional datasets for validating pulmonary *in vitro* models

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In vitro models of the lungs may be important tools for both pharmaceutical and infection research. However, evaluating and validating the translational predictivity of complex *in vitro* models is challenging due to the limited availability of appropriate *ex vivo/in vivo* models.

Pulmonary epithelial primary cells and cell lines may be used for Transwell®-based *in vitro* models, provided they express tight junctions to form a biological barrier. Complementary to established functional and morphological characteristics and consensus markers, we generated bulk RNA-Seq Data from primary cells and the recently established cell line Arlo [1] for comparison with publicly available Datasets of several (alveolar and bronchial) tight and leaky lung cell lines [2]. While Na⁺/K⁺ ATPase, and ENAC chan-

nel were characteristic for barrier-forming cells, identity markers for alveolar cell fate, such as NKX2-1 and HOPX, were not related to barrier properties or alveolar origin. Identifying correlations between expression patterns and alveolar-specific physiological function is an important task for future research.

To investigate pathophysiological changes of the airway epithelium in the context of bacterial infection we generated transcription data after exposing the bronchial cell line Calu-3 cells to the *P. aeruginosa* virulence factor LASB. Differences to reported data of infected human airway epithelial cells [3] need to be further investigated, but support the value of transcriptional data for the validation of complex *in vitro* models.

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Presentation: Poster

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MUG-hOSEC: A human *ex vivo* skin model breaking boundaries

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In recent decades, *in vitro* and *ex vivo* skin models have gained popularity as alternatives to animal testing. Various models with differing levels of complexity have been developed to meet diverse testing needs. Among these, *ex vivo* skin models closely mimic *in vivo* conditions and have demonstrated wide-ranging applications. However, culturing skin models under standard cell culture conditions may limit their ability to accurately simulate real-life scenarios, such as studying the impact of air pollution on skin or conducting interdisciplinary research. To enhance the flexibility and applicability of these models, a simple yet effective approach is required.

In this study, we present the adaptability of our *ex vivo* skin model, the Medical University of Graz – human Organotypic Skin Explant Culture (MUG-hOSEC) model, derived from foreskin samples. Our model is cultured outside the traditional cell culture incubator at room temperature, using an antibiotic and animal component-free medium.

Recognizing the emerging importance of cell communication via extracellular vesicles, we employed chip-based ExoView technology to detect extracellular vesicles in the supernatant of our model over a defined timeline. This discovery opens avenues for deeper insights into skin cell signaling mechanisms. The lower cultivation temperature results in a delayed degradation process, which may be advantageous for reproducibility of experiments but could also limit the range of applications.

Our initial findings highlight the potential of the MUG-hOSEC model for more targeted validations of specific applications.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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Gas-permeable membrane-based direct oxygenation enables cellular aerobic respiration both in static culture and in perfusion microphysiological systems

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Toward physiologically relevant *in vitro* tissue models for efficacy/safety testing and disease modeling, we need to integrate various pericellular microenvironments using latest technologies and knowledge; they are concerning stem cell-derived mature organ cells, 3D hierarchical organization of organ parenchymal cell, non-parenchymal cells and extracellular matrices, good oxygen/nutrient supply, waste removal, physiological culture medium, and mechanical stimulations, etc. Among them, oxygen supply enough to allow *in vivo*-like cellular aerobic respiration has been a historical [1], forgotten, but still unsolved problem even in modern cell culture. We have been demonstrating that direct oxygenation using a new gas-permeable polymer membrane is a simple and very effective method to overcome the diffusion limited oxygen supply flux in static culture, particularly hepatocyte cultures [2,3]. Such di-

rect oxygenation is also effective in the micro-stirrer-based on chip perfusion MPS (KIM plate [4]); we observed enhanced drug metabolism of hepatocytes cocultured with small intestine [5]. Direct oxygenation also enables formation of 3D heterogenic multilayered liver tissue consisted by parenchymal hepatocytes, stellate cells and endothelial cells for liver disease model. This can be called as “Open Organoid”, better compatible with perfusion MPS formats than spherical aggregates. As such, gas-permeable membrane-based direct oxygenation allows cells to take physiological aerobic respiration as an important premise for the high and physiological functionality and metabolism in the future.

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Presentation: Oral

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3D bioprinted tumor-on-chip models to study tumor microenvironment for drug testing and disease modelling

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For decades, animal experiments were the “gold standard” for testing drugs and novel therapeutic approaches in tumor biology, despite significant differences in physiology between humans and animals. The evolutionary gap between humans and animals is, however, also a main reason why the majority of drugs fail, when they are tested in clinics, which questions animal experimentation in general. To address this issue, we are developing micro-vascularized human tumor tissue models that are 3Dbioprinted into custom-designed laser-manufactured or 3D printed fluidic chip-devices. This strategy combines the advantages of perfused fluidic chip sys-

tems with 3D bioprinted tissue equivalents. We demonstrate that in these “bioprinted-tumor-on-chip” models, blood capillaries can be grown to form dense networks around tumor spheres, which directly allows us to test anti-angiogenic substances in these model systems. These “tumor-on-chip” models can be also used to directly visualize and monitor tumor metastasis “online”, on one hand by studying metastatic cells that are released by the primary tumor into channels and surrounding connective tissue (neuroblastoma-on-chip model) on the other also the interaction of tumor spheroids with surfaces such as biofabricated mesothelium (in case of ovarian-cancer spheroids). Third, the tumor on chip also directly assesses the impact of tumor-microenvironment on drug sensitivity allowing medium throughput, high-content drug screening and drug validation applications in multi-receptacle fluidic chip devices.

Thus, we developed a novel, medium-throughput biofabrication platform that assesses multiple aspects of tumor biology such as growth, drug sensitivity, metastasis and angiogenesis thus representing a valid, human-tissue based alternative for experimental animals in cancer research.

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Presentation: Oral

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Fluid dynamics optimisation in flow-through permeation test systems

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Different miniaturised test systems are available in dermatopharmacology, which provide inexpensive, reproducible, and physiologically relevant experimental models. These novel microfluidic diffusion systems are applicable for transdermal drug penetration studies with a wide variety of barrier models, such as synthetic membranes, *in vitro* 2D and 3D cell cultures and *ex vivo* skin samples. These techniques require less tissue samples, lower number of sacrificed animals and small amount of cell cultures or artificial

tissues compared to classical diffusion systems. Since the fluid flow in the blood and lymphatic vessels is continuous, to achieve physiologically relevant condition, the fluid flow in the developed diffusion systems is also dynamic. However, regarding the optimal flow rate there is no consensus in the literature. To fill this gap, we aimed to optimise the flow rate in three different setups, including two in-house developed skin-on-a-chip systems, and a commercially available construct (LiveBox2, IVTech Ltd). For the assessment, the transdermal delivery of a hydrophilic model drug was tested on five different barrier models. Cellulose-acetate membrane was chosen as a control since it is widely used in *in vitro* release studies. Polyester membrane was also tested because it is a common base of cell culture inserts. Acellular polymer scaffolds (collagen containing alginate and GelMa C) were applied as well, which are important bioinks in bioprinting. Taking a step closer to the artificial skin models, keratinocyte containing scaffolds were also tested. Finally, as an even more complex model, the permeability of excised rat skin was measured.

Conflict of interest

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Presentation: Poster

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Supporting replacement in academia: Examining the social and cultural barriers and opportunities around the acceptance and uptake of non-animal methods

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This presentation will discuss an ongoing project exploring the socio-cultural factors within academia that may impact upon the ability of students and researchers to train in and adopt non-animal

methods. Drawing on findings from in-depth semi-structured interviews with researchers and students using animals across UK universities, this presentation will highlight drivers of animal use and barriers and opportunities around the uptake and acceptance of non-animal methods in academic research. This will cover themes such as: knowledge, skills, and expertise; communities and networks; academic environment; access; and awareness and engagement. In examining these factors, the project aims to offer tailored recommendations for further stimulating and supporting the replacement of animal use in academia.

Conflict of interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Non-animal approaches in biomedical research and testing of pharmaceuticals: An ERA policy agenda proposal

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Non-animal New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) [1] have the potential to bring human-relevant, accurate, reproducible and sustainable innovations in biomedical research, while reducing animal testing. Although NAMs are unlikely to replace all animal experiments in the near future, they can, in complementarity with animal experiments and clinical studies, help to understand, prevent and treat diseases, as well as to ensure the safety, quality and efficacy of pharmaceuticals. The development, validation, acceptance and implementation of NAMs have therefore a high priority for many stakeholders, including the European Commission and several Member States. Equally, civil society manifests its support for NAMs, illustrated by the recent 2023 European Citizen's Initiative "Save cruelty free cosmetics", calling to move towards a regulatory

system for safety assessment of chemicals without animal testing and for a gradual ban of animals in research.

The European Research Area policy agenda offers, in our belief, an opportunity to harmonize actions that will help contribute to achieving those aims. Therefore, The Netherlands, together with other member states and stakeholders, submitted an ERA proposal that seeks to coordinate and streamline Member States' actions to promote the development, validation and the use of NAMS, when they are scientifically proven and validated alternatives for biomedical research and effective innovation in pharmaceuticals. Ultimately, also intended as an important driver to sustainably reduce the number of animals used in research and regulatory testing of pharmaceuticals with validated NAMs that can produce at least equally accurate and reliable results as current animal-based methodologies.

Reference

[1] Non-animal NAMs refer to any new methodologies without using live animal testing, but it could include animal material, such as for instance foetal calf serum in cell cultures.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Start the transition to animal-free antibodies for your research

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Common laboratory reagents, like antibodies, are one of the most underestimated aspects of the 3R principle. Within the EU, 1 million animals are used for antibody production. Today's life sciences would be unrecognizable without the millions of available research antibody products. However, methods of production vary widely in their impact on animal-welfare, as illustrated below.

Ascites antibodies: Representing the lowest standard of animal-welfare and involves significant animal suffering. Mice experience considerable pain due to the buildup of ascitic fluid and related complications. This method is still used for producing large quantities of monoclonal antibodies.

Polyclonal antibodies: Immunizing animals and repeatedly collecting blood to harvest antibodies, causes substantial stress and discomfort over extended periods. Additionally, variability in polyclonal antibody batches complicates their use in research.

Monoclonal antibodies: The widely used hybridoma technology, involves immunizing animals and fusing spleen and myeloma cells, generating hybridomas. When done *in vitro*, this method has less impact on animal welfare, besides the initial immunization.

Recombinant antibodies: These antibodies are often generated from existing monoclonal hybridomas. Mostly, PCR or next-generation-sequencing are used to identify the correct pair of VH and VL.

Animal-free antibodies: Phage display technology is entirely animal-free, relying on bacterial and phage-systems instead of animal-immunization. This eliminates ethical concerns and avoids animal suffering associated with traditional methods. Production involves *in vitro* cell cultures, without using animals and ensuring product reproducibility.

Recombinant and animal-free antibodies represent the highest standard of animal-welfare. The Abcalis technology develops and produces completely animal-free antibodies, aligning with ethical standards and enhancing research reproducibility.

Conflict of interest

The authors are associated with a company that offers animal-free antibody generation and antibody engineering (Abcalis GmbH).

Presentation: Poster

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Stem cell-derived human brain tissue to study invasion mechanisms of primary brain tumors

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Glioblastoma (GB) represents the most prevalent and aggressive brain tumour, underscoring the urgency for novel therapeutics. Patients diagnosed with GB display at most a 15-month survival rate, despite extensive surgical resection alongside radio- and chemotherapy. This poor therapeutic response is rooted in the trait characteristics of GB, the widespread invasion of tumor cells into

healthy brain parenchyma. We utilised classical *in vitro* trans-well invasion assays combined with advanced profiling techniques, including RNA sequencing and DNA methylation analysis, aiming to delineate candidate genes associated with GB invasiveness. For the functional validation, we applied the Glioma Cerebral Organoids (GLICO) model, enabling us to study several aspects of tumoral invasion in a complex microenvironment without the need of animal experiments. We adapted established protocols and generated human induced pluripotent stem cells (hiPSCs)-derived cerebral organoids (COs) which we characterised morphologically and immunohistochemically. COs were fused to GB tumor spheroids resulting in a representative 3D model to study tumor cell invasion. Using live-cell imaging techniques we were able to trace the movement of single tumor cell within the CO tissue and to assess invasion relevant parameters on single-cell level. Furthermore, we will modulate candidate gene activity in GB cell to elaborate the relation between candidate gene expression and GB cell invasion. Finally, our project will further focus on the interaction of the tumor cells with the brain microenvironment for which the GLICO model offers a compelling alternative to conventional animal models.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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Germany's political goal of "reducing animal experimentation" – Are we making progress?

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The successful European Citizens' Initiative (ECI) "Save Cruelty Free Cosmetics – Commit to a Europe Without Animal Testing" asks for an ambitious EU-wide action plan to gradually phase out animal use in science. In response to the ECI, the European Commission started working on a roadmap to phase out animal testing for chemical safety assessments. Moreover, some EU member states have declared or already commenced actions to comply with the growing public demand of reducing and replacing animal use in

science. In Germany, the coalition agreement (2021) states that the government will present a strategy to reduce animal experimentation. Although at the time of writing there is no reduction strategy in place, one million euros were recently made available for the development of such a strategy, and the German Centre for the Protection of Laboratory Animals (Bf3R) is apparently responsible for developing the strategy. Against the background of this halting development, an expert working group was initiated to gather ideas on areas and ways to reduce animal use. The working group consists of NAMs researchers from universities, 3Rs experts from NGOs and former members of competent authorities in charge of assessing animal experiments. The group focusses on ways to reduce animal experiments in academia as this is where most animals are tested on. The ideas from the expert working group will be presented, along with their implications for the broader response to the ECI.

Conflict of interest

The author declares no conflict of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Transcriptomic profiling of native versus human skin equivalent

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Since 2013, a total ban on animal testing for cosmetics has been in place in Europe. Although use of native human skin (NHS) samples is an optimal alternative, it raises a major problem of reproducibility due to inter-donor variabilities. Human skin equivalent (HSE) developed from the early 1990, represents good substitute to human skin and animal testing. However, compared to NHS, lipid barrier formation in HSE remains impaired. The aim of this study is to provide a better understanding of differences between the HSE and NHS model at the transcriptomic and histological level focusing on differentiation and proliferation of the epidermis.

The first results of this comparison show that at the transcriptomic level, keratinization and keratinocyte differentiation are

over-expressed in HSE. However, keratinocyte proliferation (KRT) is much more pronounced in NHS. Regarding lipids, ceramides (CER) were also over-expressed in HSE as opposed to free fatty acids (FFA) and cholesterol (CHOL), which were more abundant in NHS, as described by Thakoersing et al. (2013). Confirming the results of transcriptomics analysis, histological sections analysis shows a lesser dense cells population at the basal membrane as well as at the whole epidermis level.

In summary, we have been able to highlight significant differences between the HSE and the NHS, the keratinocyte differentiation is more marked in the HSE at the transcriptomics level, whereas proliferation pathway is down regulated. These results could open to new approaches to improve the RHE and develop a better skin model for skin irritation or sensitization cosmetic products assessment.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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Findings of a workshop to explore animal methods bias in funding

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In this session, findings will be presented describing a 16 May 2024 workshop that explored animal methods bias in biomedical research funding. Data from a pilot study were presented demonstrating possible animal methods bias in NIH grant funding for neuroscience research, where reviewers had dominant expertise in animal-based

methods and funded grants scored by these reviewers were predominantly animal-based. Participants of the workshop discussed further evidence needs, which could include: (1) surveys or interviews with grant applicants, reviewers, or funders; and (2) generating buy-in from funders to conduct or facilitate meta-research on this topic, which requires improving transparency in reviewer reports. Participants also relayed personal experiences with animal methods bias during grant application and its impacts on research, careers, and innovation. Other topics included the relationship to other peer review biases and possible mitigation measures, including ensuring proper peer reviewer expertise and expanding reviewer pools, implementing bias mitigation trainings, establishing non-animal-specific funding streams, establishing more rigorous standards for the assessment of translational research, and generating global support for addressing this issue. The workshop successfully gathered stakeholder input on this important issue and has served to launch further investigation and mitigation efforts to overcome animal methods bias and advance animal-free research.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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A Dutch perspective on funding the transition towards animal-free innovations

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The transition to a future without animal testing requires targeted investments in scientific research on the development and implementation of animal-free models. The Netherlands Organization for Health Research and Development (ZonMw) has been doing this for the last 24 years through the program *More Knowledge with Fewer Animals* (MKMD) [1].

MKMD funds groundbreaking research that has led to the development of advanced alternatives to animal testing, such as organoids, organ-on-chips, microfluidic systems, and artificial intelligence-based models. In addition, MKMD also promotes knowledge sharing and implementation through workshops, symposia, and online platforms. This fosters collaboration between scientists, policymakers, and civil society organizations, crucial for the acceptance and integration of animal-free methods into scientific practice.

To identify the challenges that impede the transition to animal-free innovations, the MKMD program has also recently developed a prominent knowledge agenda, in which many obstacles and solutions in the Dutch transition to animal-free innovations were identified, both at a scientific, technical, educational, political, societal and cultural level. Moreover, the MKMD program has also recently conducted a pilot study in which various transparency methods (such as preregistration and the ARRIVE Guidelines), have been investigated, including their impact on the practice of animal research, with a focus on their possible effects and bureaucratic burden on researchers.

MKMD's investment in animal-free innovation contributes to a more humane and ethical science, while also increasing scientific progress and societal impact. This illustrates how a funding program can be a valuable catalyst in the transition to an animal-free future.

Reference

[1] More Knowledge with Fewer Animals | ZonMw. <https://www.zonmw.nl/en/program/more-knowledge-fewer-animals>

Conflict of interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Induced pluripotent stem cells vs healthy fish stem cells for comprehensive *in vitro* toxicology

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In recent years, the use of induced pluripotent stem cells (IPSCs) and *in vitro* models derived from them has opened up a wide range of options for replacing animal testing. In many areas of preventive toxicology, IPSCs enable the application of the Adverse Outcome Pathway Approach. However, there are two important functions of natural embryonic stem cells that are not given with IPSC. They do not have the potency to control the development of a new organism via the oocyte, and in many cases their exploitation is only possible after inactivation of protein 53. This protein is an important factor in maintaining the genetic stability of pluripotent cells. In many tumour-derived mammalian cell lines, P53 is also dysfunc-

tional, which makes a realistic prediction of genotoxic effects *in vitro* difficult. Based on developmental *in vivo* studies in fish, we have identified a cell type and isolated a corresponding cell line that has the genetic signature of mesenchymal stem cells in general, expresses key genes of the oocyte transcriptome and has an intact P53 system. We show how the systems biology properties of these cells can be used to replace costly animal experiments to protect human and environmental health, thus justifying our initiative to use these fish cell lines as complements and alternatives to mammalian systems in existing and future OECD guidelines in the areas of genotoxicity-, carcinogenicity-, endocrine disruption and reproductive health testing [1].

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Optimization of the synaptosome model to reduce tissue requirement and its application to examine the role of neural RAS

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Introduction: Central nervous system effects of angiotensin receptor blockers (ARBs) gained a massive interest recently. Previous findings from our research group have demonstrated the anti-aldosterone effect of ARBs in neuropathic animal model.

Objective: In this study, we aimed at investigating the effects of ARBs on synaptic glutamate transmission using a synaptosome model. Our aim was to transfer the previously used model into a suspension format and optimize it for a more sensitive and robust assessment of neurotransmitter release and to significantly reduce the tissue required.

Methods: Rat brain synaptosomes were prepared and several cryopreservation procedures were studied. Their viability was as-

sessed by resazurin reduction and LDH release assays. The amount of glutamate released was quantified by a glutamate oxidase coupled assay.

Results: Compared to the previously used method, a significantly decreased amount of synaptosome could be used, as about 5 times less synaptosome released similar amount of glutamate. According to the results of storage stability experiments of the freshly prepared suspension indicate that loss of viability can be avoided by snap freezing in HEPES sucrose buffer containing 10% FBS with 5% of DMSO. ARBs inhibited 4-aminopyridine-induced glutamate release in a concentration-dependent manner, yet surprisingly angiotensin II alone was unable to increase glutamate release.

Conclusion: The optimized model provides a more physiological method to investigate the presynaptic neurotransmission. This approach significantly reduces the amount of tissue required, thus minimizing the number of animals to be sacrificed. Reduced glutamate release in response to ARBs may contribute to their previously observed antinociceptive effects.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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The investigation of synaptic monoamine uptake in rat brain synaptosomes

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Background: Monoamine uptake inhibitors represent a drug class with paramount importance in the treatment of depression and other CNS disorders. For screening new inhibitor candidates *in vitro* methods are to be used instead of animals. Synaptosomes are more physiologic than cell lines and allow the analysis of interactions of various transporter systems.

Aims: We aimed at developing a synaptosome model appropriate for assessing synaptic monoamine transport.

Methods: The effect of reuptake inhibitors and other drugs on monoamine transport was examined using synaptosomes isolated from rat brain. 4-(4-(Dimethylamino)styryl)-N-methylpyridinium (ASP⁺), a selective, fluorescent substrate of monoamine carriers

was used to monitor monoamine uptake by measuring its intracellular accumulation by fluorescence detection.

Results: ASP⁺ was found to accumulate into the synaptosomes on a concentration-dependent and saturable manner. Optimal ASP⁺ concentration was chosen from the linear part of the curve. The method was validated by known monoamine-reuptake inhibitors that concentration-dependently inhibited ASP⁺ uptake according to their selectivity demonstrating the applicability of the model. The method was used assaying uptake inhibitory effect of tolperisone and other CMRs. These results can support the potential analgesic effect of tolperisone in neuropathic pain.

Conclusions: A fast and high throughput method for studying monoamine transport in synaptosomes was optimized and validated by established uptake inhibitors. The method can be used to study the effect of potential inhibitors.

The work was supported by ÚNKP-23-2-I-SE-46 grant.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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Indicators for 3R monitoring in Switzerland

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Over the last two decades, European countries have made significant strides in monitoring animal use for scientific purposes, primarily through systematic tracking via licenses. Enhanced transparency in reporting is achieved through online access to datasets detailing animal numbers, severities of use, scientific purposes, fields, institutions, and other key descriptors. Despite these advances, public debates often focus narrowly on total animal use as a measure of progress in the 3Rs (Replacement, Reduction, and Refinement). In Switzerland, the steady total of around 600,000 animals used annually over the past three decades is frequently cited as

evidence of stagnant 3R progress. Although there is some attention to the increasing proportion of severe uses, deeper analyses of institutional and scientific field contributions are rare.

To enhance data-driven discussions in public debates and policymaking, we propose new measures of 3R progress centered on harm-benefit ratios, a key 3R indicator. We argue that animal numbers should be assessed relative to the scale of scientific activity. In Switzerland, a significant expansion in scientific activity, as evidenced by research funding data, suggests that animal intensity (animals used per unit of research effort) has likely decreased, indicating some 3R progress. However, this progress is uneven. For instance, in cancer research, animal intensity appears to be increasing, as the number of animals used grows faster than the funding.

We discuss the opportunities and challenges in matching datasets on animal uses with research funding.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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French Centre for 3Rs: Promotion of open science

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In 2021, the French Ministry of Higher Education and Research and leading French public research organisations created the French Centre for 3Rs (FC3R). The primary objective of the FC3R is to promote and implement the Replacement, Reduction and Refinement principles in animal experimentation throughout France. This objective is pursued by promoting responsible and innovative research, funding research projects, providing comprehensive training, ensuring transparent communication and supporting researchers in their experimental design.

To help researchers with their experimental design and to share their unpublished results, FC3R has created a dedicated platform, the FC3R Short Notes. This platform encourages Open Science, promotes robustness in research and minimises redundancy. Eligible studies include original research or replications with any type of positive, negative or inconclusive results. FC3R Short Notes are concise (limited to two figures and 2,000 words) and are assigned a DOI after evaluation and validation by the FC3R Scientific Committee and external reviewers. The evaluation criteria focus on experimental design, treatment of results and statistical analyses rather than perceived significance and impact. FC3R Short Notes are not limited to animal experiments and include *in vitro* and *in silico* studies that promote the 3Rs in research. The Short Notes platform has an international scope and is hosted on the HAL open science portal. The publications are easy to find, well referenced by search engines and linked to other services such as ORCID and possibly pre-registration platforms.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Development of experimental setup based on a tissue-engineered 3D-cell phantom to evaluate electroporation

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Background: Medical devices and technologies must undergo rigorous testing and validation before being certified for public health-care use. Human 3D-tissue models offer valuable insights into cancer behavior and treatment efficacy.

Methods: We optimized an experimental setup using a collagen-based hydrogel human 3D-tissue model to facilitate reproducible investigations into ablation techniques, focusing on electroporation (EP) for lung tumor cells [1]. EP, a minimally invasive procedure, employs high-voltage electrical pulses to create pores in cell membranes, leading to cell death. This selective technique should preserve surrounding healthy tissue and is utilized in tumor treatment [2]. A test system is crucial for electrode material development, non-thermal ablation control, tumor cell behavior study, and image-guided treatment simulation [3,4].

Results: The test system comprises a standardized setup, a cell-mimicking hydrogel model, and reliable result measurement. A 3D-printed setup, using sterilizable materials, includes invasive

temperature sensors and non-invasive MR-thermometry. Models cultured with fibroblasts and lung tumor cells enable comparison of healthy and cancerous tissue behavior, viability, and morphology.

Conclusion: We demonstrated the reliability of the selected methods and especially the temperature monitoring displayed interesting insights. The thermal effect due to EP cannot be neglected and it has to be discussed if this technique is non-thermal. The lesions in the phantom were able to visualize apoptotic and necrotic regions. The EP further led to a change in viability. These results suggest that the phantom can mimic the response of soft tissue and is a useful tool for studying cellular response and damage caused by EP.

References

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Conflict of interest

Thomas Rauff, declares that he has no conflicts of interest related to his involvement in this project, despite my employment with IGEA S.p.A., which provided an Elektroporation device.

Presentation: Poster

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Translation and reproducibility – Standardized human biomaterials

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Despite the ongoing developments in new biomaterials, scientific research, the starting point for many medical applications, is still performed with human cells embedded in animal-derived materials. Animal-derived materials are not only regularly associated with the sacrifice of many animals, but the cultivation of human cells in combination with animal-origin products also does not reflect an ideal human cell environment. An alternative source of biomaterials is human placenta tissue which is globally available in large quantities.

By using human placenta tissue, a so-called medical waste, THT Biomaterials reuses clinical material that would otherwise be discarded after birth to develop new innovative human biomaterials.

Human placenta extracellular proteins are isolated using enzymatic or non-enzymatic strategies allowing the obtention of large protein quantities through a sustainable process. THT human placenta-derived biomaterials have been successfully used in cutting-edge life sciences applications such as 3D cell culture (stem cells,

organoids), organ-on-a-chips, and 3D bioprinting replacing popular materials like mice tumor-based hydrogels and fetal calf serum (3Rs).

Human placenta-derived biomaterials have demonstrated a vast potential not only to replace animal materials in science but also to boost the translation of *in vitro* results into clinical applications [1-4]. In prospect, THT Biomaterials based on a circular economy also aims to integrate these human biomaterials into clinical applications since they have a recognized potential as medical products.

THT solution minimizes the lifecycle environmental impact of new products and can therefore contribute to a more sustainable future in light of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) from the United Nations.

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Conflict of interest

Dr Johannes Hackethal is the CEO of THT Biomaterials GmbH.

Presentation: Oral

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Autologous co-culture tumor models: Correlation of lipid signatures with drug resistance in *CIC::DUX4* sarcoma cell line

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The ultra-rare *CIC::DUX4* sarcoma (CDS) is a subtype of small round cell sarcoma that shares morphological features with Ewing sarcoma (ES). However, CDS exhibits a more aggressive clinical course and rapidly develops chemoresistance. Recently, studies in other cancer entities have suggested that lipid droplet (LD) accumulation caused by a hypoxic tumor microenvironment, correlates with increased chemoresistance in cancer since hydrophobic cytotoxic drugs are readily sequestered within LDs.

We recently established a novel CDS cell line derived from a primary tumor of 60-year-old CDS patient. The tumor cell line was authenticated by expression of characteristic tumor markers, namely CD99 and the *CIC::DUX4* fusion gene. In addition, a cancer-associated fibroblast cell line, the most abundant component of the CDS stroma, from the same tissue was isolated allowing co-cultivation of both entities mimicking the solid tumor *in vitro* without the use of animal models. Furthermore, a comparative analysis between fetal bovine serum and human platelet lysate was performed to explore the potential for reducing animal products during cultivation.

Using this new model, we aimed to characterize the lipid profile of CDS and compare it with the ES cell line MHH-ES-1 under hypoxic and normoxic conditions using mass spectrometry. This approach revealed a significant accumulation of triglycerides and ceramides in CDS under hypoxic conditions, indicating a dysregulated lipid metabolism, which was not observed in ES under the same conditions. These findings provide evidence for distinct lipid signatures in CDS, potentially contributing to the understanding of their role in drug resistance.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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Optimization of a 3D multi-layer cell culture to study NSCLC chemoresistance mechanisms

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Non-small-cell lung cancer (NSCLC), originating from epithelial cells of terminal alveoli, constitutes 85% of total lung cancer cases [1]. Despite advancements in therapies, resistance to drugs remains a significant issue often associated with interactions within the tumor microenvironment (TME) [2].

3D *in vitro* models represent a viable alternative for replicating the TME, thus avoiding the use of animal models according with 3R principles [1]. The aim of this work is thus to establish a multi-layered cellular co-culture to understand how heterotypic interactions influence the response against chemotherapy. To fully replicate the complexity of the tumor environment, the multi-layered culture is integrated into innovative 3D spherical agarose-gelatin membranes capable of reproducing alveolar geometry at the air-

liquid interface, enabling a better study of NSCLC metabolic and molecular features.

Initial results show effective multilayer formation through long-term culture of A549 lung adenocarcinoma cells, which was assessed by confocal microscopy. Moreover, cell viability (Alamar-Blue assay) is comparable to PET transwell and flat membranes controls, indicating good metabolic functionality.

Further studies will focus on the characterization of the cellular multilayer and cancer progression features using immunocytochemistry analysis of adhesive molecules and metabolic transcripts through PCR. This will include examining not only acquired aggressiveness signatures but also the expression of metabolism enzymes conventionally linked with this type of tumor.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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In vitro phototoxicity assays – Limitations and benefits of a combined approach to compound testing

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Several animal-free assays have been developed to assess the risk of a compound becoming (more) harmful upon light exposure. Three assays are commonly employed to derive an assessment of a substance's phototoxic potential. The 3T3 NRU phototoxicity assay (OECD TG 432) exposes mouse fibroblasts in a 96-well format to light of UVA and higher wavelengths. While this easy-to-use assay provides reproducible results, it cannot predict substances absorbing light in the high-energy UVB/C range. Also, transferability to human tissue may be limited. The ROS assay (OECD TG 495) is

an *in chemico* assay for reactive oxygen species production upon exposure to light of UVB range and higher wavelengths. This assay is fast and amenable for high throughput analyses but is restricted to a subset of substances. Reconstructed human skin to simulated sunlight (OECD TG 498) is closest to a normal exposure scenario. It thereby presents a highly valuable addition to the results from the other assays, but experience with this model is still limited.

Here we present an overview over the strengths and limitations of each assay using seven reference chemicals employed in at least two of these assays. We also discuss the findings from two case studies, in which test items were analysed by a 3T3 phototoxicity and a ROS assay or a 3T3 and a skin model phototoxicity assay. These results contribute to the ongoing discussion how these assays can be successfully combined to improve the predictive power of *in vitro* assays in the context of phototoxicity.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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Revealing molecular mechanisms of SARS-CoV-2 spike protein in renal epithelium through micro-physiological modeling (MPS)

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This study investigates the transcriptomic profiles of renal proximal tubules influenced by the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein (SP), in the presence and absence of renal cell carcinoma (RCC). Utilizing the TissUse Humimic chip to simulate RCC physiology, we created a microphysiological system comprising reconstructed renal proximal tubules and RCC spheroids derived from RPTEC and Caki-1 cells [1]. Gene Set Enrichment Analysis (GSEA) was conducted to identify affected biological processes, using a log₂ fold-change threshold of 2-fold and a p-value of 0.01. Differential gene expression was analyzed with g:Profiler and KEGG mapping tools [2,3].

Distinct deregulation patterns were observed upon SARS-CoV-2 SP exposure, such as the upregulation of monocarboxylic acid metabolism (GO:0032787) and changes in extracellular space composition (GO:0005615). Without SP in the cancer co-culture, genes related to chromatin structure (GO:0030527) and nucleosome formation (GO:0000786) were upregulated, whereas key biological process pathways (GO:0007166, GO:0048856, GO:0048518) were downregulated.

SP exposure in cancer co-culture notably overexpressed genes involved in cytokine activity (GO:0005125) and regulatory functions (GO:0098772), while downregulating crucial molecular functions like signaling receptor binding (GO:0005102), DNA-binding transcription factor activity (GO:0003700), and extracellular matrix organization (GO:0030198). This trend extended to processes involved in gene expression regulation and cation/anion transport (GO:2001258, GO:0015711).

These findings reveal intricate gene regulation dynamics within three-dimensional RCC systems under varying conditions. SP exposure induced significant molecular adaptations, as shown by gene profiling data. This study suggests potential metabolic and gene expression crosstalk between RPTEC and Caki-1 cells under viral mimicry, contributing to the understanding of molecular dynamics in three-dimensional cell culture, particularly concerning SARS-CoV-2 SP exposure and its lasting effects on renal physiology.

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Presentation: Poster

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CAMSkin model: Re-vascularized human skin after cultivation on the chorioallantoic membrane

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Introduction: Human skin testing model is one of the most demanded models in testing several products. Absence of proper vascularization remains a critical obstacle in engineering proper tissues culture. Hen's Egg Test – Chorioallantoic Membrane (HET-CAM) is considered one of the well-known models suitable to engraft cells/tissues from different species. CAMSkin is a part of larger project of Humanized HET-CAM system intending to integrate HET-CAM with different types of human tissues to develop well-constructed tissues that mimic their proper environment and functionality.

Aim: Develop an *ex vivo* model to cultivate human skin tissue on CAM and investigate its viability, neovascularization and skin layers integrity.

Methods: The skin tissue was collected from donors after plastic surgery and cut into discs with 8 mm diameter. Each disc was inoculated on CAM for six days. The skin viability was assessed using MTT assay, and skin layers integrity and developing capillaries were investigated through histological analysis.

Results: MTT assay showed an increase in viability by 26% for skin cultivated on CAM when compared to fresh sample, and an increase by 79% when compared to media culture. Histological sections showed healthy skin with proper dermis layer with developed capillaries inside skin and migrating blood cells.

Conclusion: This constructed system gives the advantage of inducing blood vessels development inside the skin. This neovascularization might help in increasing its efficacy in several applications such as penetration, irritation, metabolism, toxicology and primary cell isolation where its vasculature plays an important role in its proper functionality.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Impedance-based identification of severe and mild eye irritation *in vitro*

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New Approach Methods (NAMs) based on *ex vivo* or *in vitro* models have been developed for the endpoint of eye irritation. There are promising NAMs that can classify a wide range of chemical eye irritants [1]. However, no NAM is yet able to replace the Draize eye test by predicting the full range of different chemical categories of eye irritation according to the Globally Harmonised System for the Classification and Labelling of Chemicals (GHS) in a single test [2]. Therefore, we aimed to establish the ImAi-test, an impedance spectroscopy-based non-invasive method allowing a continuous monitoring and capturing of tissue recovery.

To broaden the applicability domain of eye irritation testing, we investigated the effects of chemicals of GHS category 1 and 2, as well as category 1 dilutions using a modified protocol of the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) 492 test guideline [3]. Instead of destructive methods, we used

non-destructive impedance spectroscopy to analyse reconstructed cornea like models based on primary human keratinocytes. Chemical-induced tissue damages were analysed *via* the transepithelial electrical resistance at the frequency of 1000 Hz. TEER measurements of category 1 and 2 chemicals strongly decreased directly after treatment, indicating loss of membrane barrier functionality. Tissue recovery was observed only in models treated with category 2 chemicals. TEER analysis of cat. 1 dilutions was additionally compared to histological H&E and MTT assays.

The identification of eye irritations based on impedance spectroscopy could have impact for the labelling of formulated consumer goods and further development for NAMs.

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Conflict of interest

The corresponding author declares that there is no conflict of interest with the authors. Statement on ethics vote: There is a positive ethics vote.

Presentation: Poster

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Development and implementation of the *Hyaella azteca* bioconcentration test (HYBIT)

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The standard regulatory assessment of bioaccumulation is based on bioconcentration in fish according to OECD TG 305. The ultimate decisive bioaccumulation criterion as part of the regulatory chemical safety assessment of pesticides, biocides, pharmaceuticals, and other chemicals is the bioconcentration factor (BCF). In the past, no non-vertebrate test system was available which allows the estimation of BCF values. Over the last years a test concept for an aqueous exposure bioconcentration test with the freshwater amphipod *Hyaella azteca* (HYBIT) has been developed which provides the opportunity to reduce the use of fish for BCF testing in accordance to the 3R principles [1,2]. Following the development of a standardized test protocol an international multi-laboratory ring trial involving HYBIT showed the robustness and transferability of the

methods to other labs as well as the variability of the results within and among laboratories. Based on the validated test protocol a draft OECD test guideline (TG) on HYBIT was developed, which was adopted in April 2024 by the OECD. In addition to the broad range of organic compounds which have been tested so far, further studies have been shown that *H. azteca* is also suitable for testing manufactured nanoparticles (MNs). The HYBIT may be used for the regulatory assessment of MNs with slight modifications (Nano-HYBIT). After completion of ongoing validation studies, a guidance document on testing MNs with *H. azteca* as a supplement to the HYBIT TG is planned. The development and implementation of the HYBIT as novel approach methodology is described.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Development of a defined foetal calf serum-free medium for differentiated HepaRG[®] cell culture

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HepaRG[®] differentiated human liver cells, also known as HPR116, provide a state-of-the-art, ready-to-use *in vitro* model for studies of human hepatocyte metabolism and toxicity. Foetal calf serum (FCS) is present in most HepaRG[®] cell culture supplements. HPR116 can be maintained in culture for up to one month using medium containing 10% FCS. Our aim was to design a FCS-free maintenance medium for HPR116 culture, as FCS collection is unethical, and its composition is unknown and variable from batch to batch, leading to time-consuming and costly cell culture qualification. Following a literature review, fractional factorial design, using

a statistical software, were made leading to screen 32 FCS-free defined medium formulations with a variation of 22 factors. HPR116 cells were seeding for 14 days in these media. Plan responses were HPR116 morphology and functionality. From then, a response surface design was performed to test the best FCS-free medium concentration upon the selected factors giving the best predictive FCS-free medium. Two FCS-free medium compositions were selected from this design of experiment. In both 2D and 3D cultures, HPR116 cells exhibited similar cell morphology and cytochrome P450 enzymatic activities, when cultured in one of the FCS-free media in comparison to the control medium with FCS. Monolayer HPR116 cells cultured in both FCS-free media demonstrated good transporter activities leading 2D culture model particularly relevant for cholestasis studies. This new FCS-free medium supports the morphological and functional integrity of HPR116 cells and provide a reliable and ethical alternative to traditional FCS-containing maintenance media.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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Designing new fluorescent probes for efficient monitoring of drug-induced liver injury effects on bile canaliculi motility and albumin expression

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DILI, or Drug-induced liver injury, is still a significant reason for withdrawing drugs from the market. New tools need to be set up to improve DILI characterisation upstream of market release. This study aims to characterise two fluorescent probes: Fluobile™ and Fluoalb™ for bile canaliculi and albumin labelling respectively on HepaRG® hepatic cell line, in presence of known reference DILI. These probes are easy to use, 2 step staining tools, and can be used in 3D model, which aim to reduce number of hepatocytes used in response to cells source shortage.

HepaRG® cells were exposed to Chlorpromazine, Fasudil, APAP and Rifampicin for 2 hours prior to the incubation of cells then for one hour with fluorescent probes. Drug effects on bile canaliculi and albumin expression were evaluated by fluorescence microscopy and fluorimetry using respectively Fluobile™ and Fluoalb™ probes in 2D and in 3D models.

The results showed that Fluobile™ and Fluoalb™ were able to specifically label bile canaliculi and albumin in the different hepatic assay systems. Additionally, these fluorescent probes were able to detect changes in hepatocyte functions, as well as identify DILI in the cells. As expected, Fasudil and Rifampicin induced an increase of surface of bile canaliculi, whereas a decrease was quantified by image analysis with Chlorpromazine.

Overall, these specific fluorescent probes have the potential to be valuable tools for improving DILI characterisation in drug development and monitoring. They can provide researchers an easy-to-use and reliable method for assessing hepatocyte functions and identifying potential liver toxicity.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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Animal methods bias and the COLAAB-orative effort to overcome it

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There is a growing consensus among researchers, policymakers, and regulators that advancing the development and use of innovative nonanimal research methods is needed to improve biomedical translation and reduce and replace the use of animals in science. Despite the availability of such methods in many applications, confidence is still being established and uptake has been slow due to a

variety of barriers. Preliminary evidence suggests that peer reviewers of animal-free manuscripts and grant applications may sometimes prefer animal-based methods (as an unconscious bias) or may sometimes lack adequate expertise to properly evaluate nonanimal research, resulting in unfair assessments and potentially serious career consequences [1]. This presentation will provide an overview of this concept of animal methods bias as a barrier to the broader dissemination and uptake of nonanimal methods. It will include early anecdotal and survey evidence of animal methods bias [1] and findings from a Workshop to Address Animal Methods Bias in Scientific Publishing [2]. It will also discuss the formation and ongoing efforts of the Coalition to Illuminate and Address Animal Methods Bias (COLAAB): an international collaboration of researchers and advocates aimed at building concrete evidence of the characteristics and consequences of animal methods bias, as well as developing and implementing solutions for overcoming it.

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Presentation: Oral

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Exploring nanoparticle-tissue interactions in *in vitro* models of the intestinal mucosa in health and disease

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The significance of *in vitro* models of the human intestinal mucosa for assessing nanoparticle-tissue interactions is widely acknowledged across various disciplines. However, discrepancies in complexity and culture conditions among studies pose challenges to comparability and reproducibility, impacting research outcomes in toxicology, permeation, and therapeutic efficacy. In a systematic study, we investigated the effects of varying cell ratios (enterocytes to mucus-producing goblet cells) and culture conditions (static vs. dynamic) to discern their implications for *in vitro* tissue develop-

ment. Adaptation of cell ratios and culture conditions resulted in morphological variations in the resulting tissue models, including the formation of protrusions, and increased mucus secretion. Tight junction formation and barrier integrity were contingent upon cell types and culture conditions, with dynamic models exhibiting reduced epithelial barrier integrity. We evaluated two nanoparticle formulations – with and without polyethylene glycol coating – for cytotoxicity, uptake, and transport across the different *in vitro* models. Notably, the mucus layer primarily influenced the permeation of uncoated particles, whereas for coated nanoparticles, tissue morphology emerged as the rate-limiting factor for permeation. In inflamed *in vitro* models, a significant reduction in barrier integrity was observed. However, nanoparticle permeation was attenuated in these models due to changes in the viscosity of the mucus layer. This systematic investigation into alterations in tissue properties and their implications for nanoparticle interactions lays a foundation for making more informed decisions when exploring particle-tissue interactions, enhancing the reliability and relevance of future studies.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Mission impossible accomplished? On the incoherent implementation of the harm-benefit analysis as a requirement of Directive 2010/63/EU

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The use of animals for research purposes is regulated by designated laws in many countries. In the European Union (EU), the most influential legal framework for using laboratory animals is Directive 2010/63/EU (Directive) [1]. One of the Directive's intentions was to harmonize the legislation among EU member states (MS) whenever animals are used for scientific purposes. However, certain provisions within the Directive give MS room to maneuver. Therefore, it allows for some flexibility in the interpretation of its content. This may result in deviations in MS' national legislation and differences in the overall implementation, particularly in the project evaluation.

An integral part of the project evaluation is the harm-benefit analysis (HBA), which aims to facilitate the decision-making processes around justifying the use of and harm inflicted on animals. The HBA's coherent implementation has been debated at great length [2,3], and its operationalization remains challenging [4]. In

a literature study [5], we examined the differences and similarities of the HBA implementation across European countries, drawing from national legislation and available guidance documents. We analyzed the transposition of the Directive's HBA requirement into national legislation, identified relevant national/regional guidance documents, and performed a cross-national, comparative analysis of the available guidance.

Our results show deficits in the HBA requirement's transposition into national laws, discrepancies in available guidance documents relating to the HBA, and insufficient consistency in the HBA's implementation. These findings underscore the need for a more coherent approach to the HBA across European countries.

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Presentation: Oral

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The introduction of alternative *in vitro* methods in laboratory practicals

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The objective of the revision of the laboratory practicals at the University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Pharmacy in the course “Immunology of the skin” was the inclusion of the 3Rs concept (replacement, reduction, and refinement) into the curricula. The aim was to enhance cosmetology students’ knowledge of alternative methods in scientific research as well as for the regulatory purposes.

The content of the laboratory practicals was also adjusted for better relevance to the Cosmetology study program. As part of the newly introduced laboratory practical, students learned how to handle reconstructed human skin models and evaluated the irritation potential of selected creams and cosmetically active substances by

performing simulation of OECD Test No. 439: *In vitro* Skin Irritation. The wound healing potential was evaluated on reconstructed human skin equivalents in another new laboratory practical. Students also performed scratch assay using human keratinocytes and later monitored keratinocytes migration by the camera in the cell incubator by AxionBio technology. Furthermore, students gained hands-on experience in performing isolation of peripheral blood mononuclear cells utilized in The *In vitro* Pyrogen Test. The theoretical knowledge about 3R concept was shared through the recorded and live seminars.

The aim is to introduce alternative methods into the laboratory practicals also in other study programs at the faculty of pharmacy. We believe that such updates to the curricula by providing opportunities for hands-on experience in alternative methods in laboratory practicals will increase students’ interest in 3R concept and possibly better prepare them to utilize alternative methods in the future.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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Animal methods bias in education

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New approach methods (NAMs) in education are underrepresented in German universities, yet professionals in this field are needed in many biotech and pharmaceutical companies. Animal methods bias in teaching should be investigated and discussed. In undergrad courses animal experiments and “models” are still taught as standard research tools in life science. In order to help prevent animal methods bias in publishing and funding students need a more diverse course catalog with NAMs as subjects. Different approaches are necessary to tackle this issue. NAM education especially organ on a chip, bioprinting, organoid technologies and *in silico* meth-

ods must be taught in a hands-on manner. Teaching labs must be equipped with the latest tools, appliances and analyzers to educate students. Every curriculum should be revised and NAM lectures incorporated. Course instructors need time and compensation for developing new syllabuses and researchers in the field of NAMs invited as guest lecturers. Students must have the opportunity to choose their specialization in NAMs on an undergrad level. Universities should be encouraged to advertise their focus in NAMs to attract students interested in the field. Currently it is challenging to find a degree program with focus on different aspects of NAMs. Students are the work force of tomorrow and NAMs are on the rise in pharmaceutical and biomedical companies. It is necessary to change education programs not just for ethical and economic reasons but also for the acceleration of innovation.

Conflict of interest

none

Presentation: Oral

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Utilization of human lymphoblasted cell lines as an *in vitro* test system to unveil immunotoxicity of bisphenol A analogues and their mixtures

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Human lymphoblastoid cell lines (LCLs) encompass extensive variations in human genomic and epigenomic profiles and are emerging as a valuable *in vitro* tool for predicting drug responses, adverse reactions and inter-individual variability. They have been validated as a reliable and reproducible *in vitro* model for predicting immunotoxicity. The utilization of LCLs enables accurate discrimination between compounds with immunomodulatory effects and those that are immune-inert, facilitated by assessments of cell viability and alterations in cytokine release [1,2].

Recent studies have extensively investigated the endocrine disrupting properties of bisphenol A (BPA) and its analogues, yet their impact on immune system function remains poorly understood. To address this gap, we evaluated the immunomodulatory effects of nine BPA analogues in three LCLs cells. Significant variability in

cytotoxicity among BPA analogues was detected with some exhibiting higher toxicity than BPA. The logP values of BPA analogues as determined by the Molinspiration program were inversely proportional ($p < 0.001$) to the IC₅₀ values, indicating a correlation between lipophilicity and cytotoxic effects.

Subsequent evaluation of cytokine (IL-2, IL-6, IL-10, IL-17, TNF α and IFN γ) release in LCLs exposed to varying concentrations of the analogues unveiled a complex non-monotonic dose-response relationship. While high 10 μ M concentrations demonstrated immunosuppressive effects, lower 100 nM concentrations mimicking real-world exposures induced pro-inflammatory responses, indicating a nuanced impact on immune function. This was further corroborated using NF- κ B/AP-1 reporter Ramos-Blue cells.

In conclusion, *in vitro* alternative method utilizing LCL cells enabled identification of several BPA analogues as immunotoxic compounds, which was further confirmed in Ramos-Blue cells.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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Production of fibroblast-coated sutures and examination of their applicability – Preliminary study

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Fibroblasts play key role in wound healing, and in case of its insufficient functioning or low numbers wound healing disorders, chronic wound may develop.

Our aim was to promote wound healing by replacing fibroblast, with cells grown extracorporeally on suture materials. By combining *in vivo* and *in vitro* models, we searched for the answer to whether we can produce suitable conditions and surface for the fibroblasts.

All steps of the preliminary experiments were performed under *in vitro* conditions. Our aim was to determine which surgical suture material is more suitable for cell transport. We used two cell lines and investigated whether alginate coating is more effective in promoting cell attachment to the surface. The threads were left in cell cultures for 3 and 7 days and subsequently examined by epifluorescence and confocal microscopy. We tried to place the cells onto the surfaces of the threads by pipetting the cells directly into the medium and 3D bioprinting.

Hoechst-Phalloidin staining was adequate for cell detection by confocal microscopy. We concluded that multifilament thread without coating after 7 days immersion is more suitable. Once the cells are inserted between the fibers, they remain stable until they are sutured into the tissue. 3D bioprinting method did not change the result significantly.

We tested several options *in vitro* system before the thread was stitched into living tissue.

As the next step C57BL6 GFP fibroblast cells separated from one mouse will be used to follow-up the cells *in vivo*.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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A comprehensive approach to cardiotoxicity assessment using adverse outcome pathways

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Cardiovascular disease, the leading cause of mortality worldwide, is exacerbated by environmental chemicals. However, current regulatory guidelines inadequately address cardiotoxicity, relying heavily on animal testing and apical endpoints. Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) offer a transformative approach by systematically elucidating the underlying mechanisms between chemical exposures and adverse health effects. Within the EU-H2020 Project ALTERNATIVE (www.alternative-project.eu), we aim to rethink regulatory assessment of cardiotoxicity by developing a new basis for testing.

We integrated multiple lines of evidence for heart damage caused by environmental chemicals using the AOP framework, employing an evidence-based approach by systematically retrieving epide-

miological and toxicological data. In the toxicological systematic review, data was extracted from 362 *in vivo* and *in vitro* studies, resulting in over 1100 key event (KE) and over 2500 key event relationship (KER) entries, encompassing 138 unique KEs and 207 unique KERs reported at least three times. Epidemiological evidence was utilized in the identification of relevant adverse outcomes (AO). We focused on the most frequently observed KERs to integrate this evidence into an AOP network covering various aspects of cardiotoxicity, including electrophysiological, contractile, and structural effects. Central to the network are pathways describing mitochondrial dysfunction leading to left ventricular impairment. Based on the established AOP network, we developed an Integrated Approach to Testing and Assessment (IATA) for cardiotoxicity, aligned with the Next Generation Risk Assessment approach. This framework combines existing non-animal methods with those developed by the ALTERNATIVE project to guide the assessment of the cardiotoxic potential of chemicals, reducing the need for animal testing.

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Presentation: Oral

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Innovative animal-free approaches in regulatory toxicology: The OECD advisory group on emerging science in chemicals assessment – ESCA

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The landscape of toxicology is evolving rapidly with the emergence of innovative scientific methodologies aimed at enhancing chemical safety assessments. Traditional animal-based testing approaches are increasingly being supplemented or replaced by advanced technologies that offer more efficient, ethical, and accurate assessments of chemical hazards.

At the forefront of this transformation is the Advisory Group on Emerging Science in Chemicals Assessment (ESCA), operating under the Working Party on Hazard Assessment (WPHA) and the *Working Party* of the National Coordinators to the Test Guidelines Programme (WNT) within the Organisation for Economic Co-op-

eration and Development (OECD). ESCA's primary purpose is to advise on cutting-edge scientific developments to support next-generation chemical assessments. This encompasses the application of new approach methodologies (NAMs), including high throughput screening, omics technologies, computational models, and standardized methods for data collection, curation, and dissemination to support regulatory decision-making. Additionally, ESCA develops guidance and recommendations on the integration of emerging science into regulatory frameworks and oversees the essential elements of the Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) Programme.

ESCA collaborates with various OECD Working Parties on projects related to emerging science and submits project proposals to the most relevant bodies, serving as an incubator for innovative ideas and scientific advancements. We present ongoing projects within ESCA, including the implementation of omics technologies in chemical testing through the development of reporting frameworks for FAIR omics data, guidance on best practices and standardization of omics samples, and the application of omics for chemical grouping. Furthermore, ESCA explores the advancement of the AOP framework.

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Presentation: Oral

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Measuring metabolism in whole-brain organoids

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Cerebral organoids represent a promising technology in neurosciences, thanks to their ability of recapitulate salient human brain structural and functional features *in vitro*. Despite those advanced models are employed successfully in different research fields, different drawbacks need to be addressed for their fully characterization [1]. As an example, the main technologies for monitoring metabolism *in vitro*, i.e., Seahorse Analyzer, are only able to measure nutrient consumption of the whole construct, not considering local changes in concentration [2]. However, their metabolism is highly dependent on spatial chemical gradients occurring between their inner core and their surface [3].

To properly characterize brain organoids peculiar metabolism, our aim was to set up a novel pipeline, consisting in recording oxygen concentration over time on the surface and in the inner core of the model until it reaches a stationary state. To this end, commercial oxygen sensors are employed, whose functioning is based on oxygen quenching. At this point, an *ad hoc* algorithm is exploited

to obtain the metabolic rate, processing the recorded oxygen concentration. Our procedure has been tested on brain organoids, obtained from induced pluripotent stem cells derived from healthy volunteers.

Since the link between several neuropathies, such as Parkinson Disease, and metabolic alterations is known, the final goal would be exploiting the developed pipeline on brain organoids derived from patients affected by neuropathies associated with metabolic dysfunctions [4], in order to gain knowledges on disease pathogenesis and progression.

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Presentation: Poster

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Key elements for transitioning to non-animal science in the pharmaceutical sector

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This presentation explores some key elements of an action plan that individual pharmaceutical companies can implement to further accelerate the transition to non-animal science. It draws on a NGO-pharma collaborative effort to develop ideas to help pharmaceutical companies to effectively review internal practices and progress.

Many companies are required to provide toxicity data on their products to demonstrate their safety for humans, animals and the environment. Traditionally, this has been done using animal-based approaches, but this raises ethical, scientific and economic concerns. Recent scientific and regulatory developments now increasingly enable companies to embrace advanced non-animal technologies expected to deliver societal benefits as they have the potential to better predict the effects of pharmaceutical compounds [1]. They can also offer other future advantages such as reduced costs and development time [2], and the ability to provide mechanistic insights

not possible with animal-based models [3]. Consequently, a growing number of companies are showing dedicated interest in adopting these reliable biologically relevant and mechanistically driven methods to replace animal-based approaches.

Over the past decades, the development of non-animal methods has been a major focus of innovation in the pharmaceutical industry, and some companies have made promising progress in moving away from animal testing [4]. However, this has not been accompanied by the expected reduction in the use of animals for scientific purposes. A successful transition to non-animal science requires a cohesive plan across the sector, involving coordinated action, strategic planning, targeted investment and dedicated support for animal and non-animal method users and developers.

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Presentation: Oral

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Better science through more transparency – A mixed-methods case study of the Dutch research landscape

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The replication crisis in biomedical science has underscored the need for more transparency, yet implementing it practically presents complex challenges requiring multiple stakeholders with coordinated strategies. In response, the Dutch Ministry of Education, Culture, and Science commissioned ZonMw (a major Dutch research funder) to evaluate methods that enhance transparency and reproducibility in animal research. This study investigates the perceptions, challenges, and feasibility of implementing transparency methods among researchers and stakeholders in the Dutch research landscape.

Using online questionnaires and semi-structured interviews, we gathered insights from participants, including researchers, data stewards, animal welfare bodies, journal editors, deans, and

fundors. The study focused on six transparency methods promoted by ZonMw: preregistration, data management plans, FAIR data, ARRIVE guidelines, open-access publishing, and systematic reviews.

While participants recognise the benefit of the transparency methods, their implementation is hindered by insufficient training, support, and awareness. Additionally, these methods often introduce extra bureaucracy or costs, which are difficult for researchers to handle under social pressures and competitive environments. To encourage implementation, we developed twelve recommendations. A key point among them is integrating these methods into education, research assessment, and recognition systems by funders, journals, and institutions. Moreover, stakeholders should strive to align their requirements and processes to reduce administrative burdens and allocate sufficient resources to monitor compliance. Before this can be fully implemented, rewarding researchers' voluntary efforts would be more effective than imposing sanctions for non-compliance. The recommendations give practical direction for various stakeholders on stimulating these improvements nationally and hope to inspire other European stakeholders.

Conflict of interest

Julia ML Menon became involved with Preclinicaltrials.eu (a pre-registration platform) after the start of this study, while preregistration is one of the evaluated methods. Martijn Nolte and Bas de Waard declare no conflict of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Mucoadhesive magnetic nanoparticles for restoration of intestinal function in childhood visceral myopathy

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Childhood visceral myopathy is one of the most severe and life-threatening pathologies affecting intestinal tone and motility. There is currently no cure [1]. The aim of this study is to engineer chitosan-coated magnetic nanoparticles (CS-MNPs) capable of binding to the intestinal mucosal layer [2] allowing controlled deformation of the bowel wall with external magnets.

Iron-oxide nanoparticles coated with chitosan were prepared in 1M acetic acid solution. Their size distribution, surface charge, pH stability, and cytotoxicity were evaluated using various cell lines mimicking the intestinal wall: Caco-2 and HT29-MTX cells (epithelial layer), HIMEC cells (endothelial layer), and HIF cells (extracellular matrix) via a resazurin assay. Additionally, a complex *in*

vitro model including the different cell types and mimicking the intestinal wall was used to assess nanoparticles translocation.

CS-MNPs were found to be stable at room temperature for a week and across a range of pH values, mimicking the intestinal environment. They were also non-cytotoxic for all the cell types due to the presence of chitosan. Additionally, they were unable to cross the intestinal barrier, highlighting their ability to interact with intestinal mucosa without systemic toxicity.

This study suggests that CS-MNPs are a promising strategy for intestinal applications. Future work will assess their effectiveness in replicating intestinal tone and motility in the presence of external magnets using physical and digital intestinal phantoms replicating gut anatomy and mechanics. Using advanced *in-vitro* models and phantoms, this study is in-line with 3R principles contributing to the reduction of animal use in the development of therapeutic approaches.

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Presentation: Poster

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3D cardiac tissue model for pollutant toxicity testing

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Humans are continuously exposed to toxic substances. Therefore, there is a growing demand for standardised devices to assess the toxicity of chemicals and support procedures to develop reliable risk assessment approaches. Among the different target tissues of toxicity, the myocardium is still poorly investigated, although several chemicals have shown cardiotoxic effect [1,2]. In this scenario, the H2020 ALTERNATIVE project is developing 3D bioengineered human myocardial tissue models for cardiotoxicity assessment. To mimic the cardiac tissue, models were obtained by micro-fabricating an elastomeric poly(ester urethane) from the melt into a scaffold that was then impregnated with methacryloyl gelatin (GelMA) hydrogel, embedding human-induced pluripotent stem cell-derived cardiomyocytes (hiPSC-CMs) and human coronary artery

endothelial cells (hCAECs). GelMA hydrogels were prepared at 5 and 10% w/v concentration to simulate cardiac tissue stiffening in elderly people, and evaluate the effect of chemicals on this population. hiPSC-CMs and HCAECs were co-cultured in the 3D system and compared to the gold-standard 2D monoculture of hiPSC-CMs, showing that the 3D microenvironment supported the survival and maturation of cells and reduced oxidative stress in association with a significantly lower release of LDH enzyme and cTnI, indicating a less critical condition for cell survival and function with respect to the 2D one.

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The content of this abstract reflects only the author's view, and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

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Presentation: Oral

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Proliferation and differentiation capacity of an *in vitro* cell line model for myelopoiesis adopted to chemically-defined media

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The human promyelocytic cell line HL-60 is an important and frequently used *in vitro* model for myeloid leukemias and myeloid differentiation. Factors like *all-trans* retinoic acid (ATRA), 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D (vitamin D3) or 12-O-tetradecanoylphorbol-13-acetate (TPA) can be applied to differentiate HL-60 promyelocytes *in vitro* to granulocytes, or monocytes and macrophages. In the commonly applied protocols, the cells are cultivated in presence of fetal

bovine serum (FBS). In order to replace FBS and to foster harmonization of culture conditions and differentiation protocols, we have adopted HL-60 to two different xeno-free chemically-defined media (CDM-A and CDM-B) which are both commercially available. While HL-60 was successfully transferred to CDM-A, the cell line stopped growing in CDM-B after some time. Both, immunophenotyping by flow cytometry and morphological analyses of the cells applying Pappenheim's staining indicated that in contrast to CDM-A, CDM-B triggered already myeloid differentiation of the cells. This resulted in growth arrest and caused the failure to propagate HL-60 in CDM-B. Furthermore, proliferation and differentiation capacity of HL-60 was systematically compared between cells cultivated in presence of FBS or in CDM-A, highlighting some differences. In summary, our study points out how important the right choice of FBS replacements is for maintaining the differentiation capacity of *in vitro* cell line models such as HL-60.

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Presentation: Poster

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First ever animal-free, cell line-derived human S9 fraction for *in vitro* drug metabolism

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In novel approach methodologies (NAMs), animal-derived *in vitro* metabolism agents are still used. To increase the sustainability, animal-free, cell line-derived alternatives need to be established.

In a process to replace the animal liver-derived S9 fraction for *in vitro* metabolising agents, we have established proprietary hepatoma suspension cell lines grown in an optimised chemically defined media system to produce the first animal-free human S9 fraction. The current process is efficiently able to produce animal-free alternatives on a large scale to replace the usage of animal-derived or donated human livers.

The process combines the advantages of suspension cell culture (high cell density, easy handling, high productivity) with efficient and flexible reprogramming of liver-specific properties. As a result, customised enzyme activities can be achieved. The current weekly production of the cell line-derived human S9 fraction results equivalent to about one third of an average human liver. A 100-liter bioreactor is sufficient to replace a commercial batch consisting of the livers of four individuals. This process would increase the interest and likelihood of the product being included in the OECD/DIN guidelines, where the rat liver-derived S9 fraction is still standard (e.g., OECD TG471: bacterial reverse mutation test).

An improved and up-scaled production process for animal-free S9 alternatives would reduce the risk of potential ethical implications due to increased sourcing of human livers, as well as meet the parallel increasing demand for human liver S9 fraction for *in vitro* metabolism in toxicology studies.

Conflict of interest

The author is managing director of Scinora GmbH.

Presentation: Oral

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DNT-RAP₄: Pioneering non-animal methods-based DNT risk assessment of pesticides engaging EFSA's AOP based IATA approach via four new case studies

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The concept of Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP)-based Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) was developed by the Organization of Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) and the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) [1]. This abstract outlines its evolution through four new case studies on assessing pesticides for developmental neurotoxicity (DNT) within the EFSA project DNT-RAP4. The stepwise approach includes:

1. Defining the regulatory problem formulation.
2. Conducting systematic literature searches on pesticide-specific toxicity and modes of action, and critically appraising the evidence for risk of bias.
3. Organizing low-risk data into lines of evidence for Molecular Initiating Events (MIEs), Key Events (KEs), or Adverse Outcomes (AOs), and assessing data consistency within each line.
4. Mapping the consistency of chemical-specific lines of evidence with relevant, available AOPs, and amending AOPs with new chemical-specific data if needed.

5. Utilizing Quantitative *In vitro* to *In vivo* Extrapolation (QI-VIVE) with Physiologically Based Kinetic (PBK) modelling simulations to assess consistency within and between lines of evidence [2].
6. Characterizing uncertainty in AOP-organized data concerning biological plausibility and empirical evidence for key event relationships (KERs) [3].
7. Systematically reporting the AOP-informed IATA and drawing conclusions.
8. Considering uncertainties equally within and between all lines of evidence, from *in vitro* to *in vivo* rodent and human studies, for AOP-based regulatory decision-making.

This approach aims to enhance the regulatory use of non-animal methods (NAMs) in complex fields like developmental neurotoxicity (DNT) in regulatory toxicology [4].

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Presentation: Poster

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Evolvoid: A biophysical-inspired genetic algorithm for optimal cellular construct design towards lab-on-a-laptop

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Cell arrangement in biological organisms is subject to a broad spectrum of chemical [1] and thermo-mechanical [2] phenomena, constraining the possible morphological configurations that the organism can adopt. In this work we present Evolvoid, an *in-silico* pipeline based on *Genetic Algorithms (GAs)* for identifying the optimal macroscale morphologies of cell-laden *in vitro* constructs. GAs are a class of optimization algorithm mimicking natural selection criteria [3].

Briefly, the oxygen consumption and surface energy of a random population of constructs laden with cells with different morphologies is generated. The environmental oxygen is varied and the oxygen dynamics of each construct is simulated via Fick’s law with Michaelis-Menten kinetics, returning information about cell viability, robustness to perturbations and surface tension. The outputs are used to calculate a fitness function (FF), defined *ad hoc*. Then, individuals are scored, and those yielding optimal morpholo-

gies – and thus maximizing the FF – are selected. At this point, a new generation is obtained randomly combining their geometrical features. The process is iterated until the FF value stabilizes within a threshold of tolerance over consecutive generations or the predefined maximum number of generations is reached [4].

The optimal constructs identified with the Evolvoid have sizes close to constructs obtained in laboratory experiments [5]. An *in silico* pipeline predicting the optimal morphology of 3D construct (evaluated by universally-observed biophysical parameters) enables the development of high-fidelity and cost-effective *lab on a laptop*, which could augment or even replace costly *in vitro* models.

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Presentation: Poster

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The German animal welfare federation's "Guide to animal-free science" – A comprehensive overview of scientific and ethical progress

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The German Animal Welfare Federation (GAWF) envisions a society that regards all animals as fellow creatures, meets them with compassion and respect, and protects them from suffering, harm and fear. To this end, we are committed to promoting and improving animal welfare, both nationally and internationally. Facilitating a transition to animal-free science thus is the central focus of the Department for Animal-free science at the Animal Welfare Academy, the GAWF's scientific institution. We engage in dialogue with political decision-makers, regulators, industry and academia and place great emphasis on informing and educating future scientists, stakeholders and the public.

As a means of informing those parties, we created the "Guide to animal-free science". This comprehensive publication provides an easy-to-understand introduction to this topic, that is often deemed too complex by those not actively involved. It includes an overview of the current data on animal-free research and animal experiments, and sheds light on the relevant legal frameworks in Germany and the EU.

We compare sixteen animal-free methods from the fields of basic research, translational research, regulatory testing, environmental protection and education with the corresponding animal experiment. The process, background, advantages and disadvantages, as well as existing challenges are highlighted. Interviews with scientists who have developed or use these animal-free methods complement the presentations.

The Guide concludes with a presentation of the GAWF's impactful work, highlighting our engagement in political and scientific committees and our advocacy for stronger animal protection in research. The publication will be available both digitally and in print.

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Presentation: Oral

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Daphnids as early warning systems for pharmaceutical contamination: A metabolomic approach

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The continuous global increase in an ageing population together with the over consumption of pharmaceuticals and resources has increased the detection and presence of pollutants in surface waters. In relation to water monitoring practices, analytical techniques provide means for the detection of pollutants, however, these approaches are weak and fail to provide means of the early prediction or any mechanistic insight of the action of pharmaceutical pollutants. Therefore, now even more than ever, they are supported by effect-based methods which employ responses of key species to compounds of interest.

Among the key freshwater organisms used in the context of New Approach Methodologies, daphnids provide new diagnostic molecular indices mainly because they provide alternative to higher evolved organisms (in the alignment with the 3R principles) while they share many responses to toxicity with them (in the context of phytotoxicology). Our research revolves around commonly encountered pharmaceutical pollutants and their impact on the physiology of daphnids. Combining phenotypic endpoints and metabolic fingerprints we provide mechanistic insight of the actions of pollutants and novel metrics for pollution assessment. Examples include the presence of a pharmaceutical mixture which was evaluated with key enzyme activities and a reconstruction of metabolic pathways in both laboratory exposures as well as water samples collected from the environment. Thus, metabolic perturbations can ultimately provide more sensitive metrics for pollution assessment and capture more accurately the mechanism of action of pollutants which allows the timely prediction of pollution hot spots before the damage becomes irreversible.

Conflict of interest

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Presentation: Poster

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Between Heisenberg and Schrodinger: A novel approach to quantify measurement-induced perturbations in cell cultures

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Probing cell function often requires using assays which alter the very behaviour under investigation, the so-called “Schrodinger’s cat quandary in cell biology” [1-3]. On the other hand, live imaging unavoidably implies the application of a disturbance introduced by the specific measurement instrumentation (e.g., microscopes), which may influence the actual state of the system. This is referred to as the uncertainty principle of biology [4].

Here, we aimed at quantifying the impact of optical stimulation while imaging cell cultures on human neuroblastoma cell dynamics. We used a lensless imaging device (CellWatcher M, PHIO Scientific GmbH [5]) enabling real-time observations of cell cultures within the incubator under different imaging protocols, which involve continuous or alternate exposure to the light source. The images were processed to extract relevant single-cell metrics. Cross-culture comparisons were then performed to assess the potential correlation of the estimated parameters with the different protocols of optical stimulation.

We found that characteristics of single-cell trajectories (e.g., motion speed and circularity) significantly correlate with the applied imaging protocol, suggesting that optical stimuli delivered through microscopy might affect cell motility, with potential implications on, e.g., cancer invasion studies. Ongoing experiments involving the administration of differentiation factors (e.g., retinoic acid) are further highlighting the impact of measurement-related stimulation on cellular responsivity to environmental changes.

Our results pave the way to discriminate artefacts due to measurement disturbances. This might improve the reliability of *in vitro* investigations and help in the development of more predictive and translational cell-based models as consistent alternatives to animal-based methods.

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Conflict of interest

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Presentation: Oral

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Digitoids: A novel computational platform to assess the metabolic-electrophysiological behaviour of neurons cultured in monolayers

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In the last decades, computational model-based solutions have been developed to support a better characterization of neural network behavior *in vitro*. However, current *in silico* models do not consider oxygen concentration, a crucial parameter *in vitro* since they lack vascularization.

Here we present a computational platform where an oxygen-dependent model of neuron firing is implemented. It allows modelling *in vitro* monolayers of neurons reproducing their spatial arrangement and connections. Oxygen diffuses through the medium over

the monolayer and is consumed by the cells, for sustaining both neuron firing and cell functions not directly related to electrophysiological activities. Input conditions are cell density, medium height, spatial arrangement of neurons and boundary oxygen concentration. The outputs of the simulations are the neuron membrane potential and the oxygen concentration at the cell level over time.

To validate the platform, we implemented *in silico* networks reproducing those *in vitro*, whole electrophysiological activity is recorded via commercial micro electrode arrays.

We then simulated their firing: the same networks were also simulated without considering oxygen dynamics to emphasize the role of oxygen. The outputs of both the models were compared with the experimental data, highlighting statistically significant differences with the oxygen-independent model. On the other hand, the outcomes of the experimental data and the oxygen-dependent model are similar. These results suggest that taking into account oxygen dynamics results in a more accurate modelling of the electrophysiological behavior *in vitro*. The computational platform represents a powerful tool useful to optimize – or even replace- *in vitro* experiments.

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Presentation: Oral

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Machine learning-based prediction of fish acute mortality

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In silico models (including machine learning) are New Approach Methods with high potential to reduce, if not replace, animal testing for ecotoxicology. However, comparing the performance of models across studies that predict toxicity is difficult because model performance is highly dependent on the data set and the applied train-test-split. To motivate machine-learning experts without a strong biological background to work on ecotoxicological challenges we provide our clean and well-characterized data set as a potential benchmark [1]. The data set is comprised of effect values (EC50/LC50) for acute mortality (≤ 96 h), chemical properties and molecular representations, species-specific (taxonomic, ecological, life history), and experimental features in three taxonomic groups: fish, crustaceans, and algae. Additionally, we propose prediction challenges that could help answer pressing questions from our field. These range from predictions on single dominant species, inside

and across taxonomic groups, to on the whole data set. We describe our modeling approach focused on fish (both single species and across 140 species) that combines four different models with six different molecular representations, respectively. The tested models are the linear LASSO, decision-tree-based random forest and XGBoost, and Gaussian process [2]. The tree-based ones, random forest and XGBoost, performed best. On average, they were able to predict the LC50 within an order of magnitude with an RMSE of 0.9. Investigating predictions on a local level, the models show higher variability in predicting the toxicity on individual chemicals. The chemical properties molecular weight, logP, and water solubility were the most important features.

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Presentation: Oral

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Engineered fiber-based anisotropic microenvironments for 2D and 3D *in vitro* models of skeletal muscle tissues

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The functionality of skeletal muscle tissue (SMT) hinges on its hierarchical anisotropic microstructure. Conventional 2D cell cultures are unable to closely replicate SMT *in vitro*, driving the research towards more reliable and predictive *in vitro* models [1]. Biomimetic fiber-based scaffolds may provide additional topographical cues supporting SMT *in vitro* engineering, however so far optimal biomaterials and methods for easy control of 3D fiber organization are missing. This work addressed such limitations by designing 2D and 3D *in vitro* models of SMT using natural polymers and advanced fabrication techniques.

2D longitudinally-aligned gelatin nanofibers were prepared by electrospinning (A-Gel). A-Gel topographical cues triggered the

formation of aligned elongated C2C12 myotubes, showing myosin-positive myofibers, sarcomere-like organization and high fusion index and myotube lengths.

To reproduce more complex 3D SMTs, innovative fiber-reinforced C2C12 cell-laden bioinks were designed by embedding fragmented A-Gel into an interpenetrating network of Alginate and Gelatin. Multi-scale aligned 3D bioprinted fibrous constructs, fabricated by micro-extrusion printing, supported C2C12 differentiation into muscle fibres arranged anisotropically in mature bundles.

In conclusion, the formation of highly organized, densely packed myofibers on 2D and within 3D anisotropic scaffolds was triggered by their tissue-like chemical, topographic and mechanical cues. Modelling robustness will be improved by culturing human induced pluripotent stem cell-derived myogenic cells. Upon further validation, *in vitro* models of SMT could be exploited to support drug preclinical testing, in agreement with the 3R principle.

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Presentation: Oral

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Monkeys and moonshots: Exploring mission-oriented policies for animal-free research

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Humans sent animals into space before going up themselves. But might the policy approach that got us to the moon also be used to the animals' benefit? This talk explores what a "mission-oriented" approach to research policy can contribute to decreasing animal experimentation and creating animal-free hubs for cutting-edge research. Despite commitments to "full replacement," as in article 10 of Directive 2010/63/EU, traditional innovation initiatives have failed to significantly decrease overall reliance on animal experimentation [1]. Thus, new policy approaches need to be explored. A mission-oriented policy approach treats the state as a proactive shaper of markets, not just a reactive fixer of market failures [2]. It approaches big problems by adopting bold missions and encouraging bottom-up innovation across a range of sectors. It purposely tilts the landscape of innovation in a socially desired direction. Although scientific research is not literally a market [3], it resembles a

market in that it is a system of mutual adjustment [4] that provides agents with an incentive structure, and so the idea of applying a mission-oriented framework to it is straightforward. The talk will explore what a state-led, but science-driven mission to reduce overall animal experimentation in a given research hub could look like. Besides making a helpful connection between literatures on mission-oriented policy, innovation and animal experimentation, the talk also contributes to fleshing out what the often-demanded political project of phase-out planning for animal research [5] might entail.

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Presentation: Oral

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New paving stones for the road towards an animal-free regulatory system: INSIGHT and CHIASMA

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The replacement of animal testing finally receives strong policy support from the European Commission's roadmap towards an animal-free regulatory system [1]. Many important paving stones have already been laid down through the development of various experimental and computational non-animal methods (NAMs) as well as adverse outcome pathways (AOPs) explaining the NAMs specific mechanistic relevance [2] and, finally, case studies for the regulatory use of NAMs within Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) [3]. Next generation risk assessment (NGRA), using exclusively NAMs [4], is currently the “golden trophy” aimed by various research projects. Two of these projects are broadening the road towards different replacement options: INSIGHT [6] leverages the AOP concept to a Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) framework [5] that consists of a data-graph, a model-graph and an impact outcome pathway (IOP) graph for

health, ecology, societal and economic aspects. A decision map shall guide its regulatory use. CHIASMA [7] is co-designing this SSbD assessment framework by advancing the technical readiness level of a broad set of NAMs, including barrier models for skin, lung, intestine, placenta and brain and the primary organs of toxicity: liver, kidney, brain and reproductive system. Within an integrated SSbD evaluation, detailed (eco)toxicological assessments may sometimes become less important. Such European Green Deal founded assessment options may lead to a regulation, in which there is always an alternative to animal testing. We will visualize the INSIGHT and CHIASMA project goals, concepts and paving stones for the European Commission roadmap.

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The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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Combining education and research: Replacement of fetal calf serum for routine cell culture purposes

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While it is good news that researchers use *in vitro* technology to reduce experimental animal use, the widespread use of fetal calf serum (FCS) for cell culture purposes in biomedical research brings about both ethical and scientific concerns. More and more animal-free cell culture supplements are being developed that can be used as an alternative for FCS, and it is one of the focus points of the 3Rs Centre Utrecht (3RCU) to stimulate their uptake. For that reason,

the 3RCU has developed the free, public FCS-free database (www.FCS-free.org) and is organizing a working group to facilitate researchers in their efforts.

Recently, a collaboration between the University of Applied Sciences Utrecht and the 3RCU has gained financial support from the Ministry of Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality, under the Transition towards Animal-free Innovations program. This will allow us to maintain and expand an initiative in which we integrate the testing of alternative serum culture supplements both into the Life Sciences education curriculum and within the research of the Innovative Testing Lectorate. In this way, we will achieve two goals at once. We will educate students (future researchers!) on the feasibility of serum-free culture, and at the same time collect research results for more routine-like cell culture purposes.

We will present the set-up of the initiative, both conceptually as well as experimentally, and present some preliminary results. We expect that this initiative will increase awareness on this topic and that it will help us to reduce serum use in education and in research.

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Presentation: Poster

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An integral approach to replace animal-derived products for cell culture

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One of the focus points of the 3Rs Centre Utrecht (3RCU) is to reduce/replace the use of animal-derived products (ADP) for cell culture purposes. ADP such as enzymes and proteins are often derived from slaughterhouse material, but for the production of antibodies, fetal calf serum (FCS) and basement membrane extracts (BME, such as Matrigel) animals are being deployed with associated suffering.

To reduce the use of animal-produced antibodies, we are collaborating with companies that produce recombinant antibodies, to provide researchers with free test samples. To reduce the use of FCS

and BME, we are organizing a working group that meets regularly (once every 6-8 weeks). Members exchange information, have access to a shared IT environment containing relevant information, and discuss funding opportunities. Furthermore, we are hosting a searchable, public database of available products, strategies and information to replace FCS, and are developing a similar database for BME. For FCS, we coordinate central storage and free supply of replacement products to facilitate researchers. In addition, we have teamed up with the GreenLabs movement of which the sustainability goals align with reducing/replacing ADP, and we actively use social media like LinkedIn for targeted campaigns to create attention, awareness and adherence.

We will present a detailed plan of this strategy as well as share results. Overall, our philosophy is that “generating data in addition to having ideas” is the best way to facilitate researchers, also cell biologists, to fully implement the 3Rs in their workflow.

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Presentation: Oral

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Nebuloid: A novel *in silico* agent-based cell model

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Traditional *in silico* models implement a continuum approach to predict cell proliferation and resource consumption [1,2]. For instance, in a 3D cell-laden spheroid consuming oxygen, the construct is represented as a unique domain, and oxygen dynamics is governed by the diffusion and consumption equation [3]. Although this approach is widely used for several applications [4], it has some limitations. As a matter of fact, encapsulated cells in 3D structures are composed of discrete consuming units, e.g., cells, within an extracellular non consuming space. Thus, *in silico* models assume consumption in all the nodes of the mesh (i.e., the domain where the physics applies) using a pre-set cell density, thus neglecting any regions occupied by extracellular matrix. Moreover, such models do not take into account the real arrangement of the cells within the construct and their own metabolic parameters, which may change, e.g., with the phenotype [5].

Here, we propose an *in silico* model developed with the COM-SOL Livelink environment for Matlab, where cells within the construct were modelled as a point cloud, whose arrangement reflect what is observed *in vitro* [5]. The metabolic rate (B) was calculated as the inward flux at spheroid surface for spheres with different radius and same cell density (5.14×10^{12} [cell/m³]). Preliminary results show discrepancies in the values of B extracted from the bulk continuum model and the Nebuloid.

Nebuloid allows control of the spatial position and the metabolic parameters for each cell: this is crucial for developing more reliable computational models serving 3Rs.

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Presentation: Poster

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The NeuroDeRisk 3R *in silico* toolbox: De-risking neurotoxicity and 3D-pharmacophores

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Early assessment of risk for neurotoxicity benefits human volunteers and patients through safer chemicals, clinical candidates and approved pharmaceuticals. Current preclinical studies, performed during drug discovery research, poorly predict the adverse effects of pharmaceuticals on the nervous system and do not integrate sufficient time to mitigate risk by influencing chemical structure design [1].

To address this, we developed the NeuroDeRisk *In silico* Toolbox as one of the innovative results of the NeuroDeRisk Project (821528) [2,3]. NeuroDeRisk is a collaborative effort between pharmaceutical industry, SMEs and academia to improve the performance of *in vitro* models and minimize the use of animal models. The NeuroDeRisk Toolbox incorporates LigandScout 3D-pharmacophore technology developed to successfully enable key decisions in drug discovery research and address critical issues including, toxicity, speed, scaffold diversity and accuracy [4,5].

It fulfils an unmet need by identifying chemicals with potential risk for adverse events at an early stage using industry validated models covering risk for seizures/convulsions, psychological/psy-

chiatric effects, and peripheral neuropathies and algorithms that provide the ability to: 1) profile and rank chemical structures for risk of neurotoxic adverse events and neuropharmacology; 2) increase productivity and efficiency by supporting early stage decisions on development and commercialization of safer pharmaceuticals and chemicals and 3) advance research on molecular initiating events (MIEs), multi-target neurotoxicity related outcomes, and nomination of drugs and compounds for experimental studies to investigate complex mechanisms involved in neurotoxic adverse events.

It strengthens the 3Rs approach (Replace, Reduce, Refine) and increases productivity towards development of safer pharmaceuticals.

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Presentation: Oral

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The “fish invitrome” as an animal-free alternative for the assessment of organ-specific toxicity in fish – A focus on environmental neurotoxicity

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The extensive use of chemicals and their release into water bodies pose a major environmental problem. Currently, environmental risk assessment largely depends on resource-intensive and ethically questionable fish experiments. Hence, the demand for the development of alternative methods such as those based on fish cell lines is high. However, the detection of tissue-specific toxicity (e.g., neurotoxicity) still pose a challenge to these alternative methods, slowing their regulatory uptake.

The “fish invitrome” as a conceptualized modular framework combines different fish cell lines for a more holistic toxicity assess-

ment of chemicals. The aim of our project is (i) the characterization of toxicologically relevant fish cell lines originating from different organs of the rainbow trout (RT) (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) and (ii) the creation of a new approach for screening neuroactive chemicals based on neurotoxicity pathways identified in RTbrain cells. The cell line characterization follows a multi-omics approach. Furthermore, RTbrain cells are more thoroughly investigated by immunostaining and electrophysiological studies. This will allow to select candidate targets for neurotoxicity assessment, ultimately resulting in an *in vitro* test battery. Through chemical testing, we will assess the robustness and the ability to predict molecular mechanisms of neurotoxicity of the RTbrain *in vitro* battery. With the expansion of the “Fish invitrome” with organ-specific modules and markers, we expect to strengthen the case of *in vitro* approaches in environmental risk assessment and facilitate adoption by regulators.

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Presentation: Poster

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Latest advancements in the use of *in silico* methods for the qualification of non-genotoxic impurities

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Control of non-genotoxic impurities (NGIs) present in the drug substance (DS) or drug product (DP) is addressed in the ICH Q3A and Q3B guidelines, which establish that NGIs exceeding the qualification threshold should be examined with the aim of determining whether they add relevant toxicological concern with respect to the DS or DP. These impurities frequently possess novel structures, and typically, there is no existing toxicity data available to establish safety limits, i.e., Permitted Daily Exposure (PDE) values. For NGIs with limited data, *in silico* methods including (Q)SAR and read-across can assist a weight-of-evidence integrated assessment. However, the use of such methodologies in this context has

not been well defined by regulatory bodies. This work incorporates the latest scientific research, particularly on *in silico* methods and NGIs, to illustrate a framework for applying *in silico* techniques to support the NGI qualification process. *In silico* profilers can prove valuable for identifying alerting features of unusually-toxic NGIs, which would require special consideration to determine appropriate qualification thresholds [1]. Read-across approach aids the analysis of the similarity of the target impurity with the corresponding API to determine whether the impurity contributes additional toxicity with respect to the API. Importantly, best practice principles for applying *in silico* methods to the qualification of NGIs are essential for a robust use of these methodologies, and these principles are pragmatically illustrated and discussed through case studies.

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Presentation: Poster

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In vitro models of human cardiac fibrosis on biomimetic nanofibrous scaffolds: A novel preclinical testing platform for precision nanomedicine

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Myocardial infarction is one of the leading causes of death worldwide leading to cardiac fibrosis and impairment of heart functionality. Cardiac fibrotic extracellular matrix (ECM) is hallmarked by a loss of anisotropic fibrous organization, collagen I accumulation and stiffening [1]. Due to the absence of regenerative treatments, reliable *in vitro* scar-models are demanded for developing new therapies. Tissue-engineered models replicating human scar can advance their design.

In this work, in order to reproduce cardiac fibrotic tissue ECM architecture, composition, and *in vivo*-like stiffness, electrospun scaffolds with biomimetic topographical and biochemical properties and surface stiffness were prepared based on randomly-oriented poly(ϵ -caprolactone) PCL nanofiber mats, surface grafted with

human type I collagen (C1) and fibronectin (F). Human cardiac fibroblasts (CFs) were activated into myofibroblasts upon 7 days culture on biomimetic scaffolds, with no need for TGF- β stimulus. Model reliability and predictivity was validated upon antifibrotic drug treatment [2], leading to a downregulation of fibrotic markers (α -SMA expression, and cell-produced C1 and F). The model was then exploited to study the safety and efficacy of novel polymer-lipid hybrid nanoparticles, loaded with four therapeutic miRNAs (miRcombo: miR-1, miR-133, miR-208, miR-499) and functionalized with a selective ligand for direct reprogramming of CFs into cardiomyocytes. Design of co-cultured models is ongoing. In conclusion, reliable human cardiac fibrotic tissue models were engineered exploiting scaffold biomimetic cues and validated for testing nanomedicine approaches.

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Presentation: Oral

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Developing a global education hub for animal-free methods

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To accelerate the transition towards animal-free innovations in research, testing, and training, education of stakeholders of all generations in life sciences research in its broadest sense, including veterinary science, biomedical research and pharmacology, is key. An extensive array of animal-free methods is evolving, from advancements in cell culturing, such as organ-on-chip and organoid technologies, to sophisticated computer simulations, data mining and artificial intelligence. These novel methodologies will only be developed further and used more broadly if relevant students and professionals learn how to use, apply and evaluate them.

Therefore, we advocate a thorough integration of these methods into educational curricula and courses, from high school to continuous professional development for professionals, in order to promote a paradigm shift from animal research to animal-free research. It is within this context that we describe our initiative to establish the Global Education Hub for non-animal methods (NAMs), dedicated to co-creating, sharing, and spreading animal-free tools for, e.g., veterinary and medical education, as well as educational methods and materials for teaching about NAMs for life sciences research and regulatory testing.

This initiative aims not only to address the ethical concerns and the translational failures associated with the use of animals for research, testing and training, but also to foster scientific excellence, collaboration, and global impact in the use of non-animal methods in the life sciences. We will show the needed efforts that the community has identified and the short and long-term goals, with the final aim to connect with important ongoing initiatives.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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What would Miffy do? Applying informed consent by proxy to all sentient animals

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If we want to take sentient non-human animals and their interests seriously, we can try to ask for their consent before using them for human purposes, like experimenting and testing. With mentally competent humans, we speak of informed consent: for them to participate in scientific studies, for example, it is required that they consent explicitly, in full understanding of the risks and benefits.

This full understanding cannot be expected from non-human animals. We must therefore look for ways to know what they want and to estimate what they would do if they would have a deep understanding of their options, and the consequences of these options for themselves and others.

We will lead the audience through the steps we followed to evaluate different approaches that uphold and respect the agency of animals. The most promising method is to gain informed consent by proxy from thoroughly informed competent humans, in combination with seeking assent of the animals where possible and being alert to their dissent.

This approach offers a transformative perspective on the ethical evaluation of animal experiments and testing as an alternative to the harm-benefit-analysis.

Conflict of interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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***In vitro* assays for the assessment of thyroid hormone disruption – Comparison of different models and detection methods**

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Interference with thyroid hormone (TH) regulation can result in health issues in both children and adults, including neurodevelopmental and thyroid disorders and cardiovascular risks. Thyroid hormone disruptors can disrupt the TH system affecting TH synthesis, transport, actions on target tissues, or metabolism. We have established a battery of *in vitro* assays targeting crucial molecular initiating events that have been linked by adverse outcome pathways network to harmful effects in various species. This talk will introduce the battery and focus on the comparison of different assays targeting thyroid hormone synthesis, namely the inhibition of

thyroperoxidase (TPO). We conducted an in-depth characterization of existing *in vitro* human and rat cell-based models and rat microsomes together with newly developed human TPO-overexpressing cell model. Selected models were coupled with high-throughput peroxidase activity assays (Luminol and Amplex UltraRed (AUR) assays), along with a novel sensitive and selective method using HPLC-ICP-MS detection. The suitability and specificity of these methods for assessing TPO inhibition was determined using a set of 21 model chemicals relevant to human exposure. The Luminol assay was non-specific, detecting peroxidation activity even in cell lines with very low or undetectable TPO expression. The AUR assay was specific for the oxidation step of TPO action. The HPLC-ICP-MS assay was the most sensitive, reflecting both the TPO-mediated oxidation and iodination, but with lower throughput. The successful creation of a human TPO-transfected cell line allows for high-throughput screening, avoiding the need for *ex vivo* material.

The project received funding from the EU H2020 ERGO project (No.825753).

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Presentation: Oral

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Multilayered nano-hydroxyapatite (nHA)/collagen (Coll) coated-PLGA scaffolds as *in vitro* tools to model metastatic prostate cancer in the bone and evaluate drug performance

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Background: Three-dimensional (3D) *in vitro* models offer exciting opportunities to recapitulate the native tissue environment and provide a better understanding of diseases, e.g., cancer. Little research has been conducted using fused deposition modelling (FDM), an advanced 3D printing technique, to produce 3D artificial niches of metastatic prostate cancer (mPC) in the bone. This research uses FDM to print biorelevant, 3D multilayer scaffolds as *in vitro* niches of the bone.

Methods: PLGA-based scaffolds were printed with FDM. Coated scaffolds was prepared by immersion of the scaffolds in collagen

and 10% w/v nano-hydroxyapatite, followed by lyophilization and crosslinking. Physico-chemical characterization of the scaffolds (porosity, mechanical properties) in addition to evaluation of hFOB 1.19 osteoblast and PC-3 cell viability (Quant-iT Picogreen) and cell behaviour (ALP, MMP-2 and OCN) were undertaken. An assessment of docetaxel toxicity on cells cultured in 3D was also conducted.

Results: Coating decreased porosity and water permeability but increased the mechanical properties of the scaffolds. Coating positively influenced the infiltration of hFOB 1.19 and PC-3, and particularly enhanced the proliferation of PC-3 in mono- and co-culture. hFOB 1.19 cells cultured on uncoated scaffolds produced more ALP. MMP-2 activity was evident at day 14 on coated scaffolds only. The drug toxicity was reduced on cells cultured on coated scaffolds ($\geq 50\%$).

Conclusions: FDM-printed scaffolds can be biomimetic and realistic *in vitro* niches of mPC. Physico-chemical structure and scaffold coating can impact on cell viability, differentiation of hFOB 1.19 cells, and the proliferation and aggressiveness of PC-3 cells.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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Water-soluble propolis Greit 120 and HuIFN- N3 shows anti-influenza virus activity *in vitro*

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The influenza viruses affect the respiratory tract in humans, causing a range of distinct manifestations including fever, nasal secretions, cough, headaches, muscle pain and pneumonia, which could become violent and severe [1]. Influenza A viruses remain resistant to Amantadine and Rimantadin with high level of Oseltamvir [2] Therefore, there is a need for constant improvement of drugs active against resistant Influenza viruses [3] Propolis has anti-Influenza activity both *in vitro* and *in vivo* [4]. Human leukocyte interferon (HuIFN- α N3) is a multi-subtype protein that displays an activity against Influenza A and B viruses.

In this study authors elucidated the anti – influenza activity of the mixes of Greit 120 and HuIFN- α N3 at different ratios: 1:1,1:2 and 2:1. Greit's 120 polyphenols and HuIFN- α N3 were characterized by RP-HPLC. Influenza A and B viruses were separately added to

the LLC-MK2 cells treated with Greit 120 and HuIFN- α N3 alone or in ratios 1:1, 1:2 and 2:1. Plates were incubated and cytopathic effects were determined. The best results of ID₅₀ were obtained with the mix of 10% Greit 120 and HuIFN- α N3 1:2, showing ID₅₀ at 12 ± 0.2 μ g/mL for Influenza A and 19 ± 0.6 μ g/mL for Influenza B viruses. When comparing the anti-Influenza activity of Greit 120/HuIFN- α N3 with that of Ribavirin, it was found that 1:2 was the optimal ratio for Greit 120/HuIFN- α N3 (0.5 and 0.6 for Influenza A and B). This new formulation of WSP (Greit 120) and HuIFN- α N3, showing better anti-influenza activity, will definitely improve its application in flu infections *in vivo*.

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Presentation: Poster

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Assessing male reprotoxicity of real-life mixtures using novel approach methodologies

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One in six adults worldwide experience fertility problems, with approximately 50% attributed to male factors. Additionally, we are witnessing an increase in testicular cancers.

Our research aims to gain deeper insights into chemical mixture-induced male reproductive issues. Two types of testicular cells are key chemical targets: Leydig cells produce hormones, while Sertoli cells play essential roles in supporting spermatogenic cells.

In our study, we developed an *in vitro* battery of assays to assess male reprotoxicity caused by real-life mixtures of prioritised endocrine disruptors and reprotoxins. Selected assays addressed specific molecular initiation/key events (MIE/KE) that were identified based on established adverse outcome pathways (AOPs) or scientific literature.

The studied mixtures mirrored real-life pollutant composition, including phthalates, organochlorines, and perfluorinated compounds.

At the molecular level, we investigated interactions with nuclear receptors, including those for estrogen, glucocorticoids, and androgens. Subsequently, we assessed the direct impact on Leydig or Sertoli cell viability and functionality, considering factors such as oxidative stress, cholesterol levels, blood-testis-barrier functionality, and hormone production.

Our experimental models span a range of approaches, from high-throughput reporter gene assays to two-dimensional *in vitro* cultures of testicular cells, ensuring that we do not miss any critical targets relevant to male reproductive health *in vivo*. We meticulously summarised all key events and adverse outcomes where Leydig or Sertoli cells play pivotal roles.

Our comprehensive approach aims to identify the drivers of male reprotoxicity in mixtures by combining their potency, efficacy, and concentrations.

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Presentation: Poster

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Novel pull-down assay for efficient separation and identification of endocrine disruptors in complex environmental samples

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Endocrine disruption caused by various pollutants in the environment poses a significant threat to both wildlife and human health. Most drivers of adverse effects on the endocrine system are yet unknown since only a negligible fraction of marketed chemicals is well characterized with respect to endocrine endpoints. Identification of bioactive compounds in the environmental samples is challenging due to their diverse properties, occurrence in low concentrations, and potential interactions within highly complex mixtures.

In order to facilitate the separation and identification of bioactive micropollutants from surface and wastewater samples, a novel pull-down assay method was optimized and established.

The pull-down assay approach is based on highly specific protein-ligand interaction, where a tagged target protein of interest, e.g., nuclear receptor or transport protein, is used as “bait” for ligands. In our study, human transthyretin (TTR – plasma transporter of thyroid hormone thyroxine) was engineered, expressed in *E. coli*, purified, and its quantity and quality were assessed. The protein was then mixed with environmental extracts of surface and wastewater, eliciting a high TTR binding inhibition effect in a bioassay. Protein-ligand complexes were separated through affinity of inserted His-tags to nickel magnetic beads, followed by elution with imidazole solution. Eluted ligands were then subjected to non-target screening. Identification of 1 known and 11 novel TTR ligands was achieved using the principle of differential analysis of sample-treated and protein-less pull-down assay system using a two-stage LC-HRMS non-target analysis workflow.

The project has received funding from the Czech Science Foundation (GACR) under grant agreement GX20-04676X.

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Presentation: Poster

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3Rs in focus – How to make researchers more aware?

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Experimental animals – animal experiments course is compulsory for all those who assist or carry out procedures on laboratory animals. Following the international trends, we focus on introducing the 3Rs and promoting their responsible application.

We have lectures that explain the 3Rs, another lecture presents only alternative options, one lecture is about the *in vitro* methods, and we talk about the inferior species and organisms to which the 2010/63 EU Directive should not be applied.

It is well known, that theoretical education alone is never sufficient. Practical sessions are used to raise awareness of the importance of proper handling the experimental animals and present op-

tions for ensuring animal welfare. In addition, during our course, participants get a homework assignment to create a presentation on the applicability of the 3Rs in their work/research. Thus, everyone should consider his/her options. Animal caretakers tend to focus on how they can apply 3Rs to the day-to-day welfare of animals, while the PhD students, researchers could associate 1) how they could apply 3Rs methods in their research 2) how they apply 3Rs 3) summarize what 3Rs means or, 4) if they do not have their research, apply it through a topic picked up from the literature. As the course participants come to us from very different research fields, we can see interesting examples from farm livestock, through industrial applications, to classical basic research.

This method brings a sense of responsibility closer and allows the participants to plan their research reflecting on animal welfare.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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Challenges and insights of investigating small extracellular vesicle internalisation and permeation across the blood-brain barrier *in vitro*

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Small extracellular vesicles (sEVs) released by cells are found in the bloodstream, putatively interacting with the blood-brain barrier (BBB) [1,2]. The presence of peripheral sEV cargo in the brain, fluorescence signals of labelled sEVs detected in blood, and *vice versa*, suggest that sEVs traverse the BBB [3,4]. However, direct proof for single sEV-particle permeation across the BBB has not yet been reported. Our study addresses whether sEVs can permeate through the BBB.

Uptake and transport of sEVs across the BBB were assessed by evaluating the permeation and recovery of fluorescently labelled sEVs using a human Transwell® BBB model. sEVs were applied to hiPSC-derived brain capillary endothelial cells (BCECs) and the immortalised BCEC line hCMEC/D3 to measure uptake and permeation rates. A novel co-culture model of hCMEC/D3 and astrocytoma cells was used for cerebral ischemia studies by applying

oxygen/glucose deprivation (OGD), addressing the hypothesis of increased (EV) transcytosis at the BBB under pathological conditions.

Technical challenges posed by standard 0.4 µm porous membranes were improved by using inserts with 1.0 µm pores and the addition of 1% BSA, which increased permeation (6.67-fold) and recovery (1.67-fold). Under OGD conditions, co-culture with astrocytes caused higher barrier damage and increased release of sEVs. Initial experiments did not reveal differences in sEV uptake under normoxia compared to OGD conditions, nor did OGD lead to detectable sEV permeation.

Our findings highlight the importance of model selection and optimisation in sEV research, challenging the hypothesis of single sEVs BBB permeation even under pathological conditions.

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Presentation: Oral

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Framework for identifying the origin of premature ventricular contractions using patient-specific electrocardiographic imaging

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The inverse problem of electrocardiography, i.e., Electrocardiographic Imaging (ECGI), offers a promising non-invasive approach to studying cardiac electrical activity. This method allows to reconstruct the spread of electrical activity through the heart's myocardium under various conditions [1]. Often, ECGI relies on animal models to validate the accuracy of used computational methods.

We conducted a series of studies using a patient-specific ECGI framework to identify the origin of premature ventricular contractions (PVCs) in 10 patients. Patient-specific models of the torso, heart, and internal inhomogeneities (lung lobes and blood pools) were created from CT scans. The PVC origin, identified as the earliest activated site by the inverse solution, was compared with the PVC origin derived from invasive cardiac mapping, a procedure each patient underwent as part of their ablation procedure. Localization error (LE) between these two positions, determined by Euclidean distance, indicated the accuracy of inverse solutions.

The findings from our series of studies demonstrate that the patient-specific ECGI framework achieves a median LE of less than 30 mm, with fluctuations between patients and methods [2,3]. This LE is higher than the LE reported with animal data from controlled experiments [4,5]. However, the patient-specific framework offers significant benefits, including improved relevance to human physiology and the ability to account for individual anatomical variability. Additionally, while animal models typically consider the heart and torso, patient-specific data allow for the inclusion of additional organs.

This methodological approach underscores the potential for enhancing the clinical relevance and applicability of ECGI in personalized medicine.

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Presentation: Oral

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From the meaning of words to the power of actions: What changed for animals in laboratories in the last EU political term and what can we expect from the new term?

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In 2019 Eurogroup for Animals shared concerns about the high number of animals that are still being used in science in the EU, despite the well-known scientific and ethical concerns associated with animal experiments. Although support to replace the use of animals in science was growing, non-animal methods were struggling to thrive. In that same year, we held a joint event with the Finnish Presidency, “Strategies for Innovation in Life Sciences”, to bring together innovators from academia, industry and organisations, politicians and policy makers to discuss possible targets and concrete steps that both Commission and national governments could support during the legislative term and beyond to promote innovation in life sciences [1,2].

Four years later, Virginijus Sinkevičius, Commissioner for Environment, Oceans, and Fisheries, issued the following statement in light of the successful ECI Save Cruelty Free Cosmetics – Commit to a Europe without Animal Testing: “The EU is committed to animal welfare, to improving public health and protecting the environment. Animal testing should be phased out in Europe, and we are working towards this goal, by finding alternatives to it and by making sure they can be used for regulatory purposes” [3]. Together with that statement, important commitments were made by the

European Commission that can bring about the first steps to start transitioning to non-animal science [4,5].

This presentation will analyse the advances and setbacks faced in the last five years, and the political environment in which the commitments made by von der Leyen’s Commission will have to materialise.

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Presentation: Oral

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A composite bioink derived from lacrimal gland extracellular matrix and alginate

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With dry eye disease (DED) exhibiting a high global prevalence and approximately 17% attributed to aqueous deficient dry eye (ADDE), there is a pressing need for therapeutic treatments targeting lacrimal gland (LG) insufficiency [1]. Advancements in *in vitro* analysis of the LG are crucial for developing new therapies, enabling efficient, ethically sound, and comprehensive evaluation of cell-based therapeutics and pharmaceuticals. Given the rapid emergence of 3D bioprinting in tissue engineering, this study focuses on developing a composite hydrogel derived from decellularized porcine LG combined with alginate, harnessing the advantages of both materials in a single bioink. Decellularized extracellular matrix (dECM) has demonstrated excellent support for *in vitro* cell culture

[2], while alginate offers favorable biomechanical properties [3]. The biomechanical and rheological properties of the bioink were analyzed for evaluation. Additionally, 3D structures containing LG-derived cell types were printed and cultured, and cell viability was assessed. The developed LG-based bioink exhibits shear-thinning behavior, reduced cell sedimentation, and resistance to shear stresses similar to pure alginate hydrogel. Furthermore, excellent viability of LG epithelial cells and mesenchymal stromal cells was demonstrated throughout the printing process and for 7 days thereafter. Enhancing the dECM hydrogel of the LG with alginate introduces favorable biomechanical properties while maintaining biofunctionality. This study represents a significant step forward in the development of bioinks for LG tissue engineering, offering a promising platform to advance complex *in vitro* research into therapeutic interventions for LG-related conditions, including ADDE.

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Presentation: Poster

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Towards the validation of an *in vitro* assay for gap junctional intercellular communication to identify non-genotoxic carcinogens

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Non-genotoxic carcinogens (NGTxC) cause cancer through diverse non-DNA damaging mechanisms. Due to the lack of fully validated alternative test methods, NGTxC are primarily identified through the conventional rodent cancer bioassay. Gap junctional intercellular communication (GJIC) is a key mechanism for maintaining tissue homeostasis, and its dysregulation has long been recognized as a hallmark of NGTxC [1]. GJIC has the potential to be a functional *in vitro* biomarker in identifying NGTxC and their health hazards [2].

Scrape loading-dye transfer (SLDT) assay is a commonly used method for *in vitro* assessment of GJIC [3]. Our team recently improved this method by evaluating additional parameters (cell density and viability) along GJIC (i.e., multiparametric SLDT, mSLDT) and increased its throughput and adaptability for high-content analysis/screening [4]. The readiness level of this method has been currently evaluated as “B” by an OECD expert group, i.e., being optimized with validation steps needed [5].

We focus on mSLDT method for assessing GJIC *in vitro* using rat liver epithelial cells (WB-F344) and experimentally evaluate the method relevance, specifically its predictive capacity (sensitivity, specificity, accuracy) to distinguish between known NGTxC and non-carcinogens. We plan to test up to 40 reference chemicals (including at least 30% of non-carcinogens). Our data obtained for a set of 12 chemicals (six positive and six negative) show accurate identification of NGTxC and non-carcinogens by the mSLDT in WB-F344 cells. Further results and next steps of the study will be discussed.

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Presentation: Oral

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The COST-ACTION networking activity IMPROVE 3Rs concepts to improve the quality of biomedical science

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COST Actions are European projects that promote the formation of networks. A range of resources are available for this purpose, such as the organisation of events, meetings, workshops and training schools, as well as the awarding of Virtual Mobility Grants, Dissemination Grants, ITC (inclusiveness target countries) grants and short-term scientific missions.

The COST Action IMPROVE was developed from a bottom-up approach initiated by members of European 3Rs centres and its network platform EU3Rnet [1]. This activity will be presented in detail with its possibilities, plans and instruments. The working groups focus on Quality and Translatability of Science, Implementation, Dissemination and Education, whereby ethics will be an integral part in the work of the single working groups. Currently, over 200 participants reflecting several stakeholder groups take part in the activities of this project.

Cooperation and active involvement in the COST Action will be invited within the framework of this open bottom-up network approach. Further information can be found via following link: <https://cost-improve.eu/>

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Presentation: Oral

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Dealing with surplus animals – What to do instead of killing millions of animals annually in Europe

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Every year, millions of animals are bred for scientific purposes at animal research facilities in the European Union (EU) [1]. A large share of these animals features traits, such as different sex or genotype, which make them – from the researcher’s point of view – unsuitable for the originally intended experiments [2]. Even with the most meticulous breeding plans, this would still be the case, especially due to Mendel’s laws of heredity. Thus, while the general occurrence of surplus animals seems inevitable, as long as animals are still used for scientific purposes, simply killing these animals because they are considered to be of no further use should and can be prevented. From an animal welfare perspective, no reasonable cause subsists for killing them.

Since the creation of surplus animals is a result of human activity, it is our responsibility to find solutions on how to deal with them in a humane way and in accordance with animal welfare. Killing them should not be considered as an option. Instead, we will discuss animal-friendly strategies and elaborate on why economic reasons are no justification to end the lives of those animals [3]. Furthermore, we will discuss whether alternative uses of the animals are suitable options to handle this issue [3].

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Norecopa: PREPARE for better science

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Preclinical research needs to be of high quality, reproducible and translatable. If animals are used, their welfare must be maximised and they should be replaced with alternatives wherever possible.

Scientists are usually aware of reporting guidelines, since these are used by many journals, but since a burnt cake can't be improved by a better description it's essential that they work on all three Rs of Replacement, Reduction and Refinement from day 1 of planning. This should begin with a detailed literature search to evaluate the necessity, legality, feasibility, ethical acceptance of the project, and all the practical issues involved.

Norecopa's staff have been collecting global resources to help scientists implement the 3Rs since the 1990's. Links to these are available on the Norecopa website (<https://norecopa.no>), which currently consists of over 10,000 webpages and an intelligent search engine. The site includes the PREPARE guidelines for planning studies which appear to involve the use of animals. The PREPARE checklist is available in 35 languages.

Norecopa contains links to resources for all planning stages, and the website aims to be a global one-stop-shop for these. In addition, Norecopa issues detailed newsletters with the latest 3Rs news from around the world, and its staff frequently hold presentations on how to conduct high-quality research.

Conflict of interest

The author declares no conflict of interest but is the Secretary of Norecopa.

Presentation: Poster

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Development and characterization of reconstructed tracheo-bronchial tissue models from multiple species

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Highly differentiated *in vitro* models of the respiratory tract have been commercially available for a long time and are widely used for variety of studies including toxicological, respiratory infection, tobacco safety, and inhaled drug delivery. Despite these useful applications, there are large databases of animal toxicity data which are not directly translatable to data obtained from the human *in vitro* airway tissue models due to the species differences. To close this translational gap, cells harvested from both rat and non-human primate (rhesus monkey) tissues were utilized to develop models similar to existing human reconstructed tracheobronchial tissue model offered by MatTek.

Acute exposure to 4 chemical toxicants (CT) showed species-specific changes in the tissue viability and membrane integrity. The effective dose concentration that reduces tissue viability by 50% (ED-50) for vinyl acetate (VA) and chloroacetaldehyde (CA) were both < 2 mg/tissue and the ED-50 for propylene glycol (PG) was > 20 mg/tissue for all species. However, the ED-50 values for toluene (T) showed differences between the species: human > 20 mg, primate 16.2 ± 1.7 mg, and rat 13.8 ± 0.1 mg. TEER values from standardized QC tests averaged 1094 ± 325 (n = 141 lots) in the US vs. 913 ± 238 (n = 64 lots) in Europe.

Conclusions: Although more chemicals need to be tested, the multispecies 3D airway tissue models may become useful translational tools to predict airway inhalation toxicity and to bridge the *in vitro-in vivo* knowledge gap to reliably predict human responses, while providing a worldwide alternative approach to animal experimentation.

Conflict of interest

MatTek is a producer of commercially available models used in this study.

Presentation: Oral

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EpiOcular™ time-to-toxicity – A test method for subcategorization of eye irritants

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In 2015, an OECD TG 492 was accepted and validated for the use of *in vitro* ocular tissue models. Initially, this TG only allowed for distinguishing between substances and mixtures not requiring classification and those that must be labeled for eye irritation or serious eye damage. Further specification of eye irritation severity was not included in the TG. More recently an OECD TG 492B was accepted, which allows for distinguishing between chemicals that: a) do not require labeling for serious eye damage or eye irritancy (No Cat), b) cause serious eye damage (Cat 1), and c) are eye irritants (Cat 2) according to the UN GHS ocular hazard categories. A new

testing strategy was developed based on the results from 2 studies, CON4EI and ALT4EI projects. A robust final set of 144 reference chemicals – 78 liquids and 66 solids, was obtained and the results provided confirmation of the new testing strategy. The performance criteria, established by the OECD expert group overseeing OECD TG 492B, were met for all 144 chemicals. Using this data set we developed the EpiOcular™ time-to-toxicity test method for eye hazard identification of liquid and solid chemicals according to UN GHS. Overall, the new test method correctly predicted 76.8% of Cat 1 (N = 55), 61.9% of Cat 2 (N = 42), and 81.2% of No Cat (N = 47) test articles. The EpiOcular™ time-to-toxicity test method is a novel approach for subcategorizing of both liquid and solid compounds. The prediction models for liquids and solids are capable of distinguishing substances and mixtures into: No Cat, Cat 2, and Cat 1.

Conflict of interest

MatTek is a producer of commercially available models used in this study. MatTek is a producer of commercially available models used in this study.

Presentation: Poster

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In vitro reconstructed model of human epidermis containing melanocytes for studying skin pigmentation and lightening

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Products that modulate natural skin pigmentation are used to protect skin from UV irradiation (by increasing melanin content of the skin), or to treat skin pigmentation disorders, such as melasma, dark spots, solar lentigo, and other hyperpigmentation lesions. Clinical studies of such products are often lengthy (more than 3 months). We have developed the 3D reconstructed tissue culture model of human skin, which contains normal human melanocytes (NHM). Epidermal tissues can contain NHM of varying skin phototypes which follow the pigmentation level of the donor tissue. We have utilized this

model to develop the protocol for studying skin whitening products *in vitro*. The tissues were treated topically three times a week over a two-to-three-week period to mimic consumer application. Several skin lightening products were evaluated in cultures containing NHM. Over the treatment period, negative control cultures became increasingly pigmented with retention of normal epithelial morphology. In contrast, tissues treated with cosmetic skin lightening agents remained lighter than the control cultures. The skin lightening effect on treated tissues was quantitatively evaluated for melanin content using a Solvable melanin assay and for skin brightness (L* value) using a hand-held spectrometer. Treated tissues showed significant changes in overall melanin content and brightness compared to control tissues. These results suggest that this model can provide valuable *in vitro* data for screening raw materials prior to the commencement of costly clinical trials and that it will be useful to study melanogenesis, skin lightening, and other pigmentation phenomena of the skin.

Conflict of interest

MatTek is a producer of commercially available models used in this study.

Presentation: Poster

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Translation of an established *in vitro* blood-brain barrier differentiation protocol to CRISPR/Cas9 gene-edited, patient-derived hiPSC lines: Highlighting challenges

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The use of patient-derived human induced pluripotent stem cells (hiPSCs) for disease modeling has the advantage of overcoming the problem of interspecies differences originating from animal models. Here we aim to emphasize the challenges of adapting a well-established differentiation protocol to create a patient-derived hiPSC-based blood-brain barrier (BBB) model of the SYNGAP1 disorder. Brain capillary endothelial-like cells (BCELCs) were differentiated from a patient-derived hiPSC line (L), two CRISPR/Cas9-edited isogenic controls (F1, D1), and a CRISPR/Cas9 mock patient line (C/Cmock). BBB models' properties were assessed by

transendothelial electrical resistance (TEER), paracellular marker permeability, and immunofluorescence (IF) staining of pluripotency (SSEA4, Nanog) and junctional (Claudin-5, CDH5, ZO-1, Occludin) markers. RNAseq confirmed the correction of the patient's mutation in the isogenic control lines. One major challenge was that the four hiPSC lines showed dissimilarity in growth rates (Population doubling time = PDT_L : $22.4 \text{ h} \pm 1.8 \text{ h}$; $PDT_{C/Cmock}$: $23.1 \text{ h} \pm 1.2 \text{ h}$; PDT_{F1} : $27.5 \text{ h} \pm 5.1 \text{ h}$; PDT_{D1} : $30.2 \text{ h} \pm 5.4 \text{ h}$) which required optimization of the differentiation protocol for each single cell line. Additionally, IF staining of Nanog and CDH5 indicated heterogeneous cell populations of the differentiated cell lines presumably originating from distinct responses to the differentiation process. To obtain more homogenous cell monolayers, an extracellular matrix-based pre-enrichment step before seeding onto transwell inserts was optimized and implemented. Ultimately, with these protocol adjustments, we were able to establish BBB models from all four cell lines forming tight barriers ($TEER > 1000 \text{ Ohms} \cdot \text{cm}^2$) with continuous networks of BBB-relevant junctional markers.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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***In vitro* 3D reconstructed models of human duodenum, jejunum and ileum**

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The study of gastrointestinal (GI) toxicity is limited due to the lack of physiologically relevant *in vitro* models that recapitulate the role of specific parts of the GI tract. To mimic the physiology and functionality of the human gut, we established the small intestinal model from primary human cells. The only pitfall of this model is that it only consists of cells derived from jejunum. Here we present development of 3 new models of small intestine utilizing primary cells from different intestine regions in order to provide further physiological relevance and expand ability to pinpoint differences between different regions of small intestine mucosa (duodenum, je-

junum, and ileum). Gene expression analyses revealed differences in the expression of genes encoding transporter proteins (ABC family, peptide transporters) and drug metabolizing enzymes in various regions. On the other hand, expressions of some drug metabolizing enzymes such as CYP3A4, CYP2C9, UDP glucuronosyltransferase 1 family, polypeptide A1 (UGT1A1), and Carboxylesterase 1 (CES-1) were maintained in each segment at a comparative level. Our preliminary experiments aimed at drug absorption and metabolism revealed that the permeation of Vinblastine was affected by inhibition of MRP and/or P-gP transporters. These results suggest that the reconstructed tissues from the three segments of the small intestine may serve as useful tools to predict both investigational and traditional GI drug safety and absorption in the GI tract. In addition, use of these models will reduce animal use and improve the pre-clinical drug development process.

Conflict of interest

MatTek is a producer of commercially available models used in this study. MatTek is a producer of commercially available models used in this study.

Presentation: Poster

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Development of an *in vitro* test method for irritation of medical devices used in the oral cavity

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The irritation of any medical device (MD) contacting oral tissues needs to be evaluated. The objective of this project is to develop and validate *in vitro* assay to assess the oral irritation of MDs. This assay is intended to replace historical *in vivo* assay performed on Syrian hamsters. The ISO 10993-23 standard requires that MDs be evaluated using an *in vitro* irritation test based on reconstructed human epidermis (RhE) prior to animal or human patch testing is performed. However, RhE models are not appropriate for MDs designed for use in oral cavity, therefore ISO recommends use of other *in vitro* models with relevant cells or tissues. The EpiOral tis-

sue model consists of normal, human-derived oral epithelial cells cultured to form multilayered, highly differentiated model of the human buccal tissue. To assess the feasibility of an *in vitro* method, initial experiments tested solutions of irritant chemicals contained in MDs used in oral cavity. Increasing concentrations of ethanol, lactic acid, methyl methacrylate, sodium dodecyl sulfate, phosphoric acid, sodium hypochlorite, hydrogen peroxide, and chlorhexidine digluconate in NaCl or sesame oil were applied to the EpiOral model. The time required to reduce tissue viability by 50% (ET-50), was determined. The results showed a clear relationship between tissue viability and exposure time and between ET-50 and concentration of the irritant chemical. Compared to historical *in vivo* data, the *in vitro* method classified the samples containing an irritant at the expected concentration. In addition, the ET-50s allowed differentiation between strong and mild irritants.

Conflict of interest

MatTek is a producer of commercially available models used in this study.

Presentation: Poster

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A microphysiological system for simultaneous neural and oxygen measurement in brain tissues using an integrated opto-electrical sensor system

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The complexity of *in vivo* systems limits the study of neural activity and metabolism. Here we present the development of integrated opto-electrical sensors enabling real-time, simultaneous measurement of neural activity and oxygen levels in brain tissues. Multi-electrode arrays (MEAs) were fabricated using lift-off lithography and incorporated PDMS micro scaffolds for tissue support, facilitating high-resolution electrophysiological recordings from quail brain tissues.

Ex vivo validation with quail brain microsections confirmed the integration of oxygen sensors and preservation of neuronal mor-

phology. Field potential recordings displayed distinct frequency bands, providing insights into neural dynamics.

Pharmacological interventions with TTX, Bicuculline, and PTZ demonstrated the system's sensitivity to changes in neural and metabolic activity. TTX, a voltage-dependent Na⁺ channel inhibitor, reduced neural activity and oxygen oscillation, indicating electro-mitochondrial uncoupling. Bicuculline, a GABA_A receptor inhibitor, enhanced neural activity and oxygen levels, demonstrating electro-mitochondrial coupling. PTZ, a GABA receptor antagonist, significantly elevated neural excitation and metabolic response.

Fast Fourier Transformation (FFT) analysis of field potential and interstitial oxygen data elucidated the dynamic interplay between electrical activity, calcium channel function, and mitochondrial metabolism. These findings underscore the potential of integrated opto-electrical sensors to advance our understanding of neural activity and metabolic processes in brain tissues, providing a powerful tool for neurophysiological investigations and therapeutic development.

Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Toxicological aspects of *in vitro* oral mucosa wound healing models

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The objective of this project is to develop new *in vitro* oral wound healing models and determine their toxicological profile using common dentifrice materials. Two tissue models were used in this study EpiOral (ORL-200), which consists of normal, human-derived oral epithelial cells cultured to form a highly differentiated model of human (non-cornified) buccal tissue, and EpiGingival (GIN-100), a cornified model of the gingival mucosa. On Day 0, tissues were wounded using a 3 mm biopsy punch and wound closure was monitored using brightfield microscopy, histological cross sections, and transepithelial electrical resistance (TEER) measurements. The

toxicological profile of the tissues was probed using sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS), at 1%. Within 2 days postwounding (PW) for the ORL-200 tissue and 4 days PW for the GIN-100 tissue basal cells migrate into the wound to reestablish a continuous monolayer. Immediately following wounding, TEER for WT decreases to < 20% of the NWT controls, but TEER increases as wound healing proceeds. Wounding also changes the toxicological profile of the tissues. For the ORL-200 model, the ET-50s for the WT and NWT were 27.8 and 49.1 min, respectively, which represents a 76% increase in ET-50 for the NWT vs WT. By contrast, in the cornified GIN-100 model, the ET-50s were 54.5 and 124.5 min, respectively, which is 128% increase in ET-50 for NWT vs WT. These results demonstrate successful development of wound models for tissues of the oral cavity. Wound healing can be monitored with brightfield microscopy, TEER, histology, and sensitivity to a common dentifrice additive.

Conflict of interest

MatTek is a producer of commercially available models used in this study.

Presentation: Poster

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Performance evaluation: Incorporating GARD[®]skin assay into the OECD TG 497 defined approaches as a KE3 component

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Recent regulatory developments in skin sensitization assessment led to the acceptance of Defined Approaches (DA) and Integrated Testing Strategies (ITS) in OECD TG 497. Currently, Data Interpretation Procedures (DIPs) only apply to specific assays. Efforts are underway to include equivalent validated assays.

GARDskin OECD TG 442E is an *in vitro* skin sensitization assay relevant for potential incorporation into DIPs as monitor for Key Event (KE) 3. Minor adaptations are needed to fit it into DA and ITS, including defining a Borderline Range (BR) for binary classifications and a procedure for deriving a potency score.

The readout of GARDskin is a Decision Value (DV). The BR, determined from the ring trial data variability, is defined to be between DVs of -0.450 and +0.450. Applying the BR slightly increased performance among conclusive classifications. Incorporating GARDskin as the KE3 component in the DA maintained overall performance, with improved outcomes in specific chemical domains, e.g., hydrophobic compounds.

A procedure for deriving a potency score compatible with ITSs in TG 497 was also defined. Based on binary hazard classification and exposure concentration, non-sensitizers receive a score of 0, while skin sensitizers receive scores between 1 and 3, with thresholds at 56.44 µg/mL and 13.03 µg/mL. Using this scoring system, an ITS containing GARDskin achieved classification performances in line with current ITS.

In conclusion, GARDskin, adapted for compatibility with DA and ITS in OECD TG 497, produced performances comparable to current versions, with improvements in certain chemical domains, suggesting its relevance in either DIP.

Conflict of interest

All authors are currently employed by SenzaGen AB that markets, sells and performs the GARD assay.

Presentation: Poster

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What have we achieved? – Retrospective assessment of 3Rs projects funded by the set Foundation

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The Foundation for the promotion of alternatives to animal testing (*Stiftung zur Förderung von Ersatz- und Ergänzungsmethoden zur Einschränkung von Tierversuchen*, set Foundation) was founded in 1986. It was intended as a joint effort from the German Federal Ministry for Food, Agriculture and Forestry and German industry Associations to unite industry, animal welfare organisations, research

bodies and government in coordinating their efforts and work together towards a common goal: The refinement, reduction, and replacement of animal experiments through the active development of 3Rs methods.

To assess the outcome and benefits for the promotion and improvement of the 3Rs, we did an analysis of a selection of the most recent projects that were funded. We evaluated project documentation, project reports and surveyed project leads. Projects were categorized according to project type, type of methods that were used or developed, target organ or product, field of application and outcome.

Here, we present the results of our analysis and show how the set Foundation helped promising 3Rs projects on their way to become successful methods, paved the way for follow-up projects, and even led to OECD Test Guidelines. We discuss possible learnings for 3Rs funding bodies and give an outlook on future plans of the set Foundation.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Advancing cell-based assay reproducibility through lensfree imaging and AI integration

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The 3R (replacement, reduction, refinement) principle is fundamental in minimizing animal use in life science research. However, achieving Replacement and Reduction is challenging due to the lack of viable alternatives. Traditional cell-based assays often lack temporal information and depend heavily on cell quality, impairing reproducibility. To address these issues, we present a novel, incubator-compatible approach for cell-based assays aligned with the 3R principle.

Our method utilizes lensfree imaging to exploit cells' inherent optical properties for non-invasive, label-free monitoring within a CO₂ incubator. Additionally, our system integrates artificial intelligence (AI) for real-time analysis of key cell culture parameters, such as confluency, proliferation, and motility [1]. This integration allows for automated, objective data acquisition, enhancing assay standardization and result reproducibility.

In this study, two colon carcinoma cell lines with varying growth homogeneity were cultured and monitored using a lensless microscope setup under arsenic trioxide treatment. Results indicated that memory effects of prior subculturing influenced cell growth and multi-omics profiles, with higher homogeneity in earlier passages increasing the number of differentially expressed markers by up to 80% [2].

By providing continuous, label-free monitoring during incubation, our system offers a powerful tool for deeper insights into cell behavior. This method can quantify organoid growth dynamics and interactions in 3D cell models. Our approach not only adheres to the 3R principle by reducing reliance on animal models but also significantly improves data quality, control, and processing speed in cell-based research. This technology holds potential to address the reproducibility crisis and standardize future cell-based assays.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Unveiling the dynamics of scratch assays: Continuous, label-free monitoring of cell migration using lensfree imaging and AI

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Scratch assays are essential for studying cell migration and wound healing in cellular biology. Traditional methods, relying on intermittent measurements and labeling, can disrupt cellular behavior. This study introduces a novel approach utilizing continuous, automated, lensfree imaging and analysis within CO₂ incubators, providing detailed and accurate analysis of scratch assay dynamics.

We developed an advanced system for non-invasive, label-free imaging to continuously monitor the closure of scratch “wounds” in 2D cell cultures. This methodology enables real-time data acquisition, significantly enhancing the temporal resolution of cell move-

ment observations compared to manual acquisition (every 30 minutes vs. every 8-12 hours). By tracking closure speed and direct cell movements without external markers, we gain a comprehensive understanding of cell dynamics.

Our findings demonstrate that this continuous monitoring system not only accurately measures wound closure rates but also distinguishes between active directed migration and proliferation-driven movements. This distinction is critical, as it provides a reliable indicator for differentiating these mechanisms in a label-free environment. The ability to discern these processes opens new avenues for understanding cell behavior in various biological contexts, including cancer metastasis and tissue regeneration.

Overall, this study underscores the potential of automated, continuous lensfree imaging systems in CO₂ incubators to revolutionize cell migration assay analysis. By eliminating disruptive labeling and enhancing data resolution, our approach significantly advances cellular dynamics research, providing nuanced insights into cell behavior and movement mechanisms.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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Eye damage reversibility in an *in vitro* model of bovine cornea to replace the Draize test completely

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One of the requirements for the registration of chemicals is to provide evidence about their potential eye damage. The Draize test performed in rabbits allows the products to be classified into four categories, considering both the severity of the lesions produced in the animal's eye as well as its healing time [1]. The available alternative methods to this live animal test do not allow documenting the damage reversibility, nor the time necessary for such reversibility to occur, as required by the UN GHS classifications [2].

Our proposal is to complement the *in vitro* model that uses the bovine cornea as a substrate to predict whether a substance is irritating or non-irritating (BCOP) [3], with a strategy that allows predicting if the observed irritation is reversible and the time it takes to revert.

Limbal stem cells are known to play an important repairing role in corneal injury; therefore, we isolated these cells from bovine cornea and used them to evaluate the cell sensitivity to reference prod-

ucts. A wound healing assay was also performed to study whether these products differentially affect the replication and migration capacity of the cells. Furthermore, a tissue explant and an organotypic cornea culture model were implemented to study if the chemical exposure alters cell's replication, migration and overall wound healing differentially.

Our results provide evidence suggesting that a combination of the approaches used might be effective in detecting the different categories of UN GHS, which is necessary to finally replace the Draize test completely.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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Characterization of alternative methods for intestinal epithelial cell regeneration after infection

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Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) represents prevalent gastrointestinal condition characterized by chronic inflammation of the intestinal epithelial cells. The underlying pathophysiology of IBD remains a subject of unresolved investigation. Nevertheless, there has been a notable surge in research employing animal models to elucidate the pathogenesis. Despite ethical concerns and inherent complexities associated with animal testing, complete elimination of such procedure is currently not feasible. However, replace, reduce, or refine (3Rs) principle as articulated by Russell and Burch, serves as a guiding ethical framework. In pursuit of “replacement”

principle, we have introduced organoids and organ on chip system to create a gut-on-chip model. The aim of the project is to establish a system that replicates the morphological and functional aspects of the intestine, enabling the analysis of epithelial regeneration following infection and treatment.

As a simple disease model, organoids were stimulated by LPS or *E. coli* Nissle 1917 (*EcN*). Low dose of LPS increased the expression of *Ki67* and *Lgr5* after 12 h and *Slc5a1* and *Muc2* after 36 h. With *EcN* infection for 1 to 6 h, the proliferation and differentiation of the cells increased initially and the effect declined with time. To mimic the intestinal cells alignment, we established the chip system with murine epithelial, stromal, and endothelial cells. The cells co-cultured together show compatibility on the chip system. The cells will be subjected to bacterial exposure to model cell damage and regeneration. Upon successful establishment of the chip, a comprehensive characterization will be undertaken, focusing on both morphological and functional features of intestine.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Contribution of human organ models to COVID-19 research – A large-scale systematic review

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Organ models offer promising new avenues for studying human diseases and designing treatments. However, establishing the reliability and robustness of these models is crucial for their broad acceptance as alternatives to certain animal models and in preclinical research.

Systematic reviews aim to gather, evaluate, and synthesize existing evidence from various studies based on predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria. While common in clinical and preclinical animal research, this methodology is not yet widespread in *in vitro* research.

This study conducts a large-scale systematic review to provide a rigorous and unbiased summary of evidence generated by studies employing human organ models to investigate SARS-CoV-2. We are synthesizing data from 289 studies focusing on infection studies and host factor expression experiments. Our analysis examines various types of organ models, their respective organ compartments, conducted assays, outcomes, and the quality of reporting. With a team of 24 reviewers, primarily organ model experts, we systematically extracted information to assess the scientific outcomes and the overall quality of reporting in the included studies.

We are synthesizing a comprehensive dataset and will present preliminary findings, emphasizing various focus areas, the frequency of applied assays, virus strains, detected host factors, and identified gaps in information provided in scientific publications utilizing human organ models. This dataset can serve as an initial use case to offer evidence-based insights for improving reporting practices for human organ models. Our pilot work can provide practical insights to tailor systematic review methodologies to this emerging body of literature.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Introducing the HTCR Foundation: A non-profit biobank of human biospecimens for 3R-aligned biomedical research

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The HTCR (Human Tissue and Cell Research) Foundation is a non-profit organization dedicated to promoting ethical and innovative research practices, and advancing alternatives to animal testing in biomedical research. A bottleneck in replacing animal experiments is the accessibility of human tissue.

To overcome that HTCR established a comprehensive biobank in close collaboration with the Department of General, Visceral, and Transplant Surgery, Ludwig-Maximilians-University Munich [1,2]. It contains diseased and macroscopically normal tissue, isolated primary cells as well as matching blood samples from almost 7000 donors and covers lung, liver, intestines, skin, and other entities. This resource supplies researchers with high-quality biospecimen and clinical data and supports a wide range of research fields, including oncology, immunology, toxicology, and

regenerative medicine [3-5]. HTCR's efforts aim at reducing the dependence on animal models in research and enhancing the relevance and translational potential of scientific studies. Through the operations of HTCR Services, which is fully owned by the foundation, more than 3000 donated samples could be allocated to collaborating clinician scientists, academic institutions, and industry partners in 2023 to advance the preclinical research pipeline of innovative treatment options.

As a non-profit organization HTCR Foundation is committed to ethical research and accessibility. Therefore, HTCR adheres to strict ethical guidelines ensuring the respectful treatment of all donated bio-samples, prioritizing both scientific integrity and donor welfare.

Hereby, the HTCR Foundation exemplifies how non-profit biobank organizations can successfully drive innovative research through dedication to providing high-quality human tissues, and promoting ethical research practices that respect both human and animal life.

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The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Case studies of innovation and replacement to illustrate the trajectory of an ideal, fully humane veterinary degree

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A growing number of departments within veterinary colleges across the world use only non-animal tools within student practical classes. These tools may be developed at the college or may be purchased, and some are part of dedicated clinical and surgical skills labs. Most colleges also have diverse clinical rotations for students that provide patient care while presenting learning opportunities for students, and some have established body donation programs to source animal cadavers ethically, including from clinics. The pres-

entation will follow the trajectory of an ideal, fully humane veterinary degree by using case studies of innovation and replacement that feature in the InterNICHE documentary film series “DVM: Training the Animal Doctor”. The evolving film series explores knowledge and skills acquisition at diverse colleges from across the world, featuring interviews, demonstrations of “alternatives” of all types, and student labs and rotations. These ethical and effective methods have been implemented in classes from the pre-clinical years up to graduation and beyond, and are considered the norm in the departments featured. The presentation will address teaching objectives and present a bold definition of harm, and the case studies taken from all disciplines will demonstrate the feasibility of a fully humane veterinary education and the associated need for a full transition.

Conflict of interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Advancing validation methodologies and regulatory acceptance of microphysiological systems

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Microphysiological systems (MPS), as a category of New Approach Methods (NAMs), have increasingly gained attention for their application in drug development, toxicity assessment, and disease modeling. MPS potentially offer a more human physiologically relevant approach, promising lower costs and higher throughput compared to conventional animal models. However, the integration of MPS into current regulatory frameworks is still under development. Guidance on validation of MPS in different regulatory settings has the potential to accelerate their adoption and use.

This year, the Interagency Coordinating Committee on the Validation of Alternative Methods (ICCVAM) published a report titled “Validation, Qualification, and Regulatory Acceptance of New Approach Methodologies” that proposed a framework aimed at achieving regulatory acceptance for NAMs. Our analysis focuses

on the applicability of this framework to MPS, identifying key bottlenecks such as unclear allocation of responsibilities for regulatory acceptance and the limitations imposed by the current fit-for-purpose validation strategy, which may hinder broader adoption of MPS.

To overcome these challenges, we propose a two-phase framework: the validation phase, managed by collaborative entities like ICCVAM, should establish the human relevance and scientific robustness of the models; the qualification phase, undertaken by end-users (e.g., regulatory agencies, pharmaceutical companies), should be customized to meet specific needs. Implementing a scientifically robust validation process will provide MPS developers, end-users, and policymakers with a clear pathway to regulatory acceptance, thereby facilitating smoother integration of MPS into biomedical research and decision-making processes, ultimately benefiting technology development and public health.

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Conflict of interest

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Presentation: Oral

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Assessment of cytotoxicity, skin and oral irritation of medical devices with hygroscopic properties. Case study

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The study aimed to evaluate both the *in vitro* cytotoxicity and the skin and oral mucosa irritation potential of the medical device “hydro pastilky” in accordance with ISO 10993. A product of similar composition, referred to as the benchmark product, was used due to its comparable composition and mode of action.

For the cytotoxicity evaluation, the Neutral Red Uptake (NRU) cytotoxicity test (Annex A of ISO 10993-5) was chosen. Cell cultures treated with “hydro pastilky” showed viability above 50% up to 34.5% of the neat extract. Viability significantly decreased

at higher concentrations, judged by microscopic evaluation of cell density, morphology, and viability. For the benchmark product, the OD in the two highest concentrations unnaturally increased due to Neutral Red dye binding to the partially jellified extract. Cytotoxic results at higher concentrations can be attributed to the products’ water-binding ability, affecting cell osmolarity over prolonged exposure.

For assessment of irritation potential, the EpiDerm and EpiOral *in vitro* 3D tissue models were used following ISO 10993-23. Cultures treated with extracts (extraction ratio 0.2 g/mL) from “hydro pastilky” and the benchmark product consistently exhibited viabilities above 50% in all conditions, with most cases exceeding 75%, classifying them as non-irritating. The EpiDerm and EpiOral models’ responses to both products were consistently comparable.

We conclude that “hydro pastilky” and the benchmark product do not demonstrate significant skin or oral irritation effects. Under normal conditions of use, they can be considered as not causing skin or oral mucosa irritation.

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Presentation: Oral

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Novel protocol for *in vitro* biocompatibility evaluation of intraoral medical devices

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In the field of oral cavity healthcare, Medical Devices (MDs) are frequently used for various applications, including prosthetics, drug delivery, periodontal care, and overall maintenance of oral hygiene. Intraoral MDs may, however, interact with the surrounding tissues, potentially leading to adverse effects. The dynamic and complex environment, with influence of various factors like saliva, microbial flora, and fluctuating pH levels, poses a challenge for manufacturing safe MDs. MDs must undergo defined biological evaluation, to ensure safety of the end-users. Such evaluation follows strict guidelines, while many countries rely on ISO 10993. ISO 10993 describes various aspects of biocompatibility assessment and progressively implements *in vitro* methods. The most recent addition was an *in vitro* protocol for sub-cutaneous irritation testing of medical devices, leading to the creation of ISO 10993-23 [1-3].

Inspired by this, we designed protocol for testing of intraoral MDs *in vitro*. This protocol employs 3D reconstructed human tissue models, that can mimic the buccal mucosa tissues. In the initial

phase, we used EpiOcular tissues as a universal non-keratinized model. We tested various products, intended to be used in oral cavity, while the response of tissues to the tested materials met the predicted outcome. In further development, we employed EpiOral, to better mimic target tissues. Tissues manifested almost identical responses to given materials with only minor deviations between respective models. In the following phase of the development, we will aim to proceed to the validation of the protocol.

The research has been supported by grants VEGA 20/0153/20, DS-FR-19-0048, and APVV-19-0591.

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Conflict of interest

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Presentation: Poster

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Adverse outcome pathways to unravel drug-induced toxicity

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The skin is the organ most frequently affected by drug-induced toxicity. Cutaneous adverse drug reactions (CADRs) can be triggered by various drugs, including interleukin-2 (IL-2). Despite its promise in treating cancers and inflammatory disorders, side effects including skin rashes limit the therapeutic use of IL-2. Adverse outcome pathways (AOPs) describe toxicological cascades stepwise and are useful in chemical risk assessment. We aimed to develop an evidence-based immune-related AOP (irAOP) considering possible molecular and cellular key events (KEs) of IL-2-induced skin rashes to better understand CADRs.

We propose an irAOP for IL-2-induced skin rash as follows: In the molecular initiation event, IL-2 binds to cutaneous cells bearing the IL-2 receptor (IL-2R). This activates IL-2R+ cells (KE1), inducing a type 2-driven immune response by activating cutaneous type 2 lymphocytes including group 2 innate lymphoid cells (IL-C2s), leading to secretion of IL-5 and IL-13 (KE2). Subsequently, mast cells seem to be activated (KE3), possibly through ILC2-mast cell interaction. Secretion of signaling molecules by type 2 cells could contribute to infiltration of immune cells (KE4), including granulocytes. Increased ICAM-1 expression, possibly induced by histamine, may contribute to immune cell accumulation in the skin. Finally, cumulative secretion of tissue-damaging proteins could induce the tissue damage (KE5), leading to skin rash as an adverse outcome in patients treated with IL-2.

We identified a type 2-driven response driving IL-2-mediated skin rash. Overall, the irAOP is a valuable tool to develop mechanisms of drug-induced toxicities which could help to increase safety of drugs in the future.

Conflict of interest

Thierry Flandre is a full-time employee of Novartis. All other authors report no competing interests. Thierry Flandre is a full-time employee of Novartis. All other authors report no competing interests.

Presentation: Poster

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Biomechanically loaded three-dimensional tissue-mimetic lab-on-a-chip models for human inflammation and fibrosis modelling

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Biomechanical and biochemical cues are essential for joint tissue homeostasis, with gait-induced forces impacting knee joint health. Biomechanical loading can either promote tissue maintenance or accelerate osteoarthritis (OA) progression. We employ lab-on-a-chip technology to study the effects of cyclic fluid perfusion on cartilage/synovial tissue models and uniaxial stretching on tendon and ligament models.

Primary human and equine synovial fibroblasts and articular chondrocytes from OA and non-OA sources were encapsulated in TISSEEL fibrin hydrogel to create biochip models. Mono- and co-cultures of these models were subjected to cyclic flow perfusion at 1 Hz for up to a week, with or without 10 ng/mL TNF- α and IL-1 β as pro-inflammatory triggers. For tendon/ligament models, primary

ligamentocytes were embedded in Collagen I hydrogel and matured for at least 7 days before undergoing 29% cell straining at 0.25-0.5 Hz for up to 4 hours, with or without the same pro-inflammatory triggers. Gene expression analysis via qPCR was performed on key physiological markers (COL1A1, COL2A1, COL3, ACAN, TNC) and OA-related cytokines (IL6, CXCL8) and metalloproteases (MMP1, MMP3, MMP13).

Equine non-OA cartilage monocultures exhibited pro-inflammatory tendencies under cyclic flow, while synovial monocultures showed anti-inflammatory responses. In co-cultures, cartilage retained a stronger pro-inflammatory response. Ligament models exposed to a pro-inflammatory environment and cyclic straining showed increased IL6 and MMP1 expression, whereas high-passage cells did not respond to mechanical stimuli, indicating a loss of mechano-sensitivity. Our study shows how lab-on-a-chip technologies can effectively replicate the knee joint microenvironment.

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Conflict of interest

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Presentation: Oral

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Moral case deliberation (MCD) sessions within an animal facility

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Dealing with ethical questions and dilemmas is common in working with animals. Ethical dilemmas are characterized as choice between two mutually exclusive options, neither of which is satisfactory [1]. Approaches have been developed to address ethical dilemmas, one of them is Moral Case Deliberation (MCD). Within this method, participants reflect upon a specific moral question that derives from a concrete experience (case) following a structured method. Because professional medical recommendations cannot provide final answers, it is best if the whole team reflects upon the decision [2,3].

The aim of MCD sessions is to alleviate moral distress and at the same time increase moral competencies.

MCD sessions usually take 2-6 hours and consist of 4-15 participants. Participation is voluntary. The session is moderated by a neutral facilitator. One participant is the case presenter. Each session is divided into 8 steps: (1) Introduction, (2) Presentation of the case, formulation of the moral question and the dilemma, (3) Clarifica-

tion questions, (4) Case analysis – exploring values and norms, (5) Looking for alternatives, (6) Making an individual choice, (7) Dialogical inquiry of differences, (8) Conclusions. Topics ranged from dealing with surplus animals or single housed males to handling protocol deviations.

MCD sessions gain mutual understanding of different perspectives, and support in decision-making. A consensus upon a dilemma is not required. Actions resulting are the implementation of guidelines, specific training possibilities, or the “cage buddies program”.

The facility offers those sessions quarterly for all members. Current topics, which can be proposed by anyone, are discussed.

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Presentation: Poster

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Of mice and men: New tools to study respiratory tract infections

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Of mice: Tissue-resident macrophages are crucial for maintaining tissue homeostasis in mammalian organs. However, suitable cell culture models are limited. We introduced a novel culture model to study and expand murine lung alveolar macrophages (AMs) *in vitro* for several months [1]. Mouse *ex vivo* cultured AMs (mexAMs) retained typical morphology and surface markers, responded to microbial ligands, and exhibited AM-specific transcriptional profiles. When transferred into AM-deficient mice, mexAMs efficiently engrafted in the lung, reducing surfactant load. This model offers a simple, versatile tool to study AM behavior in homeostasis and disease settings as well as highly reducing mouse numbers needed for AM experiments.

And men: At G.ST Antivirals, our research is devoted to the development of innovative, broad-spectrum, host-directed antivirals that exploit the dependency of viruses on the metabolic processes of their host cells. Our pre-clinical research is centred on develop-

ing treatments targeting viral infections and excessive immune cell activation. To investigate this, we utilize airway models cultured at air-liquid interface, alongside an aerosolization chamber for administration of nebulized drugs. Our candidate drugs show strong antiviral activity against respiratory viruses such as rhinoviruses and human coronaviruses. Importantly, no cytotoxic effects were observed. Currently, we are advancing towards a Phase 2 clinical trial for a nasal spray, aimed at preventing and treating the common cold.

These examples demonstrate our progress in developing drugs for upper respiratory tract infections in relevant settings, increasing the likelihood of treatment success while significantly reducing the need for animal experiments.

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Conflict of interest

A.-D. Gorki is an employee of G.ST Antivirals, Vienna, Austria.

Presentation: Oral

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Evaluation and integration of blood-brain barrier *in vitro* models in a safety and sustainability assessment framework within the project CHIASMA

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The CHIASMA project aims to develop a new and improved Safety and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) framework to support the regulatory approval process for the next generation of hazard and risk assessment of chemicals and materials. This platform will integrate in-project validated *in silico* and *in vitro* methods along with New Approach Methodologies (NAMs), eliminating the need for animal testing. The target chemical test groups include perfluoroalkyl and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), two-dimensional materials for energy applications, and nano-pesticides. Our approach prioritizes the development of stable and easy-to-follow methodologies that align with key performance parameters such as repeatability, reproducibility, and transferability.

In this scope, we introduce our work on the development of blood-brain-barrier (BBB) models based on Transwell and spheroid systems. Multicellular systems including astrocytes, pericytes and/

or neurons were established to represent multifaceted cellular interactions with brain endothelial cells. To enhance the stability and robustness of the BBB model, we tested the synergistic effects of compounds such as pCPT-cAMP, Ro-20-1724, lithium chloride, A83-01 or hydrocortisone on brain endothelial cells, targeting the activation of cyclic AMP and Wnt/ β -catenin signaling and inhibition of TGF- β pathway [1]. After constructing different BBB models with robust barrier integrity, we will test the cytotoxic effects of the aforementioned chemicals based on barrier integrity, cell viability, and molecular markers. Furthermore, omics data from these models will be generated and used to establish biomarker panels on the Biomark[®] Fluidigm platform for high-throughput screening, and the transferability of the protocols will be evaluated with project partners.

CHIASMA has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme: Grant Agreement No. 101137613. Associated Partners from (a) Switzerland, (b) United Kingdom, and (c) Korea have received national funding from (a) the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI), (b) Innovate UK (UKRI), and (c) the National Research Foundation of Korea (NRF).

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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New approach methodologies (NAMs) for use in next generation risk assessment (NGRA) for systemic safety: A pragmatic approach to “validation” by establishing protectiveness and utility: NAMs and NGRA: It’s all going to end in tiers

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There is an increasing recognition that new frameworks and approaches are required for establishing scientific confidence in the use of NAMs to achieve regulatory acceptance. In the context of NGRA, which is an exposure-led and hypothesis-driven approach for conducting safety assessments using non-animal NAMs, we need to establish that the “toolboxes” are fit-for-purpose. This requires that the combination of NAMs employed are evaluated in

the context of their use (risk assessment) and that they can give the correct “call” that a given chemical and relevant exposure is safe or not. To address this, we recently proposed a NAM-based toolbox and workflow for conducting systemic safety assessments, together with an approach for evaluating how protective it is [1]. The approach is based on the principle of benchmarking safety decisions made using the NAM toolbox against historical safety decisions. The toolbox includes physiologically based kinetic (PBK) models and a broad range of different *in vitro* assays, from which points of departure (PODs) are estimated. The feasibility of the evaluation strategy was initially tested using 24 benchmark exposure scenarios from 10 different chemicals [1] and has since been expanded to include 69 additional benchmark exposure scenarios from 38 additional chemicals. The results of the extended evaluation will be presented.

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Conflict of interest

The author declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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Development of an alternative method to animal experiments using a physical stimulation model for osteoarthritis

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The number of patients with articular cartilage diseases, such as osteoarthritis, continues to increase with the aging of society. Cartilage has a very low regenerative ability, and once damaged, it progresses to osteoarthritis accompanied by chronic severe pain, and replacement with artificial joints is unavoidable, resulting in a significant decrease in quality of life. It is believed that sports injuries and tissue deterioration over time (fatigue) are deeply related to the onset of osteoarthritis, and this study aims to develop an alternative animal experiment model for these physical stimuli loading.

It is believed that chondrocytes are loaded with hydrostatic pressure of 0 to 30 MPa inside joints in the body, and it is presumed that there is a relationship between the onset of cartilage-related diseases and hydrostatic pressure loading, but there have been no concrete reports. In this proposed study, by developing a device that can load these hydrostatic pressures, we constructed a system that more accurately reproduces the physical environment in the body.

First, we developed a device that simulates the physical environment inside articular cartilage in the body. Next, from the perspective of replacing animal experiments, we used human articular chondrocytes surgically removed from polydactyly children as experimental subjects and loaded them with hydrostatic pressure, and found that the expression level of genes related to osteoarthritis in human chondrocytes increased. Therefore, it is suggested that the experimental system developed in this study may be useful in elucidating the mechanism of osteoarthritis and developing therapeutic drugs.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Poster

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Next generation risk assessment: Mechanistic insights and implementation of NAMs for toxicokinetics and toxicodynamics characterization

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Next generation risk assessment (NGRA) is an exposure-led and hypothesis-driven approach that integrates non-animal data derived from new approach methodologies (NAMs). Scientific reasons and ethical considerations led to a global shift toward assessing the safety of chemicals for humans without animal testing. The availability of toxicokinetics (TK) and toxicodynamics (TD) data significantly enhances confidence in risk assessment decisions by providing reliable estimates of internal exposure and potential modes of action (MoAs). Under the Cosmetics Europe Long Range Science Strategy, several case studies were performed to guide the implementations of NAMs and NGRA. The case studies considered different “EXITS” in the NGRA workflow, e.g., read across, iTTC, *ab initio*

[1]. This talk will discuss the implementation of iTTC and *ab initio* approaches, that are considered to evaluate the safety of certain ingredients, e.g., UV-filters and Benzyl salicylate [2,3]. The case studies highlight the importance of the internal exposure characterization of the parent and relevant metabolites. Internal exposure can be determined through methods such as PBPK modeling or clinical studies, and then compared to an iTTC limit of 1 µM, or used to conduct toxicodynamic bioassays, as *ab initio*. Identifying the toxicologically critical entity is essential for the toxicodynamic assays, where targeted and non-targeted toxicodynamic assays are performed to identify potential MoAs and *in vitro* points of departure (PoDs) for risk assessment. In conclusion, the case studies demonstrate the protectiveness and the applicability of various approaches in NGRA to ensure human safety, aligning with the first principle of 3Rs “replacement”.

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Conflict of interest

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Presentation: Oral

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Label-free functional analysis for the characterization of iPSC-derived neural organoid development and maturation

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Rapid advances in induced pluripotent stem cell (iPSC) technology have led to widespread adoption for the development of *in vitro* neuron electrophysiology models for drug discovery and safety screening [1]. Furthermore, spheroids or organoids are intensively studied with aims to establish mature human phenotypes *in vitro* [2,3]. The objective of this work is to develop and validate a live-cell analysis workflow for the characterization of iPSC-neural organoids *in vitro*. Whole-vessel live-cell imaging with the Omni was used to monitor iPSC colony growth in real-time and used to quantify iPSC colony size and coverage to ensure consistent iPSC passaging. Furthermore, iPSC stemness was confirmed by fluorescence staining of the pluripotency markers TRA-1-60 and SSEA4-1. Lastly, embryoid bodies (EBs) were differentiated towards neural organoids and real-time live-cell imaging was used to track the size and shape

of EB formation and the induction of neural differentiation. At day 50+, neural organoids were transferred to a multiwell microelectrode array (MEA) plate and impedance measurements were used to quantify the attachment of the organoids. Broadband (1-5000 Hz) electrophysiological data was acquired and then separately processed for action potential detection (200-5000 Hz) and low frequency oscillations (1-50 Hz). The emergence and maturation of neural organoid electrophysiological activity was tracked via these measurements of spiking activity and low frequency oscillations, coupled with the long-term monitoring of size via live-cell imaging. This new workflow combining live-cell imaging and MEA measurements supports the continued development of *in vitro* 3D models of neural function.

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Conflict of interest

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Evaluation of plate-to-plate reliability in a label-free cytotoxicity assay for dose response analysis

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High-throughput screening (HTS) cytotoxicity assays are a valuable tool for screening compounds for toxicity evaluation [1]. Most *in vitro* cytotoxicity assays rely on dyes, or labels, to measure cell death at a single timepoint after a predetermined exposure time. Here, we characterized a real-time, label-free cytotoxicity assay for HTS and dose response analysis. First, cancer cells (A549 and SKOV3) were seeded into 96-well microplates with microelectrode arrays (MEAs) embedded in the plate surface. Electrical impedance measurements in each well detected the attachment and proliferation of the cancer cells over time. Cytotoxic compounds were added 24 hours after the initial seeding of A549s, and cytolysis was moni-

tored for an additional 72 hours. A549s were treated with paclitaxel and doxorubicin at six concentrations and a dose response analysis was performed to determine EC50. The EC50 for paclitaxel (13.2, 13.9, 14.5, and 13.9 nM) and doxorubicin (1.02, 0.99, 1.01, and 1.09 μ M) was consistent across 4 separate plates with a COV of 3.9% and 4.2%, respectively. SKOV3s were treated with HER2-specific CAR T cells across four replicate plates at three effector-to-target (E:T) cell ratios (1:5, 1:2, 2:1). A two-way ANOVA analysis was performed and found the greatest source of variation to be different treatment groups as opposed to different plates. At the highest dose (E:T = 2:1), the KT50 was 10.4 hours, with a coefficient of variation of 9.8%. In summary, this work describes a reliable, label-free cytotoxicity assay for compound screening, demonstrating consistent toxicity assessment across replicates.

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P38 MAPK as a potential target to prevent IL-6/IL-22 induced leaky gut in Caco-2 cell model

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Acute-on-chronic-liver-failure (ACLF) is a severe liver condition marked by multi-organ failure and high mortality, often due to a leaky gut syndrome that allows bacteria into the bloodstream [1]. Inflammation in ACLF is driven by elevated levels of interleukins, particularly IL-6 and IL-22 [2,3], which activate the proinflammatory STAT1 pathway via the p38 mitogen-activated protein kinase (p38 MAPK) [4]. BIRB 796, an inhibitor of p38 MAPK, has shown anti-inflammatory effects through allosteric binding.

In this study we aimed to investigate the effects of BIRB 796 on IL-6 and IL-22 treatments in an *in vitro* leaky gut model using Caco-2 cells. These cells were grown on permeable membranes to form epithelial monolayers and were treated with IL-6, IL-22, and/or BIRB 796. The permeability was assessed using transepithelial electrical resistance (TEER) and fluoresceine isothiocyanate (FITC)-Dextran assays. Results showed that inhibiting p38 MAPK significantly reduced STAT1 phosphorylation. IL-6/IL-22 treatment disrupted barrier function, but adding BIRB 796 restored

TEER values and reduced FITC-Dextran permeability, indicating improved tight junction integrity. Immunofluorescence staining of Zonula Occludes ZO-1, a tight junction protein, revealed morphological changes and gaps in the Caco-2 monolayer, compromising barrier function. Electron microscopy confirmed these findings, showing barrier deterioration, which was reversed by BIRB 796.

In conclusion, it could be demonstrated that p38 MAPK is indirectly involved in the regulation of tight junctions, which contributes to a deterioration of barrier function under inflammatory conditions. Blocking this enzyme and achieving an improvement in inflammation-driven leaky gut syndrome could represent a potential therapy.

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A model to study human intestinal epithelium response to probiotics

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The benefits of probiotics on human health have been extensively demonstrated in the last two decades. Although many clinical studies linked specific strains with gut outcomes against inflammation, the mechanisms of action are difficult to resolve in human studies. Animal models or tumor-derived cell lines are typically used to demonstrate the effects on the intestine in a more precise mechanistic manner. However, both models present documented limitations: specie-specific characteristics and dampened innate immu-

nity responses or lack of cell heterogeneity, respectively. To study probiotic strain-specific effects on human innate immune response, we use patient-derived intestinal organoids, which maintain the region specificity of the gastrointestinal tract, including the innate immune components, and the cell heterogeneity, including the presence of enterocytes and secretory cell lineages. By growing human organoids on monolayer and applying previously reported media compositions, we obtained an apically accessible intestinal epithelium composed of differentiated enterocytes and secretory cells. We standardized the growth conditions by using commercially available and serum-free media and validated our results between two different laboratories. We built thus a reproducible *in vitro* model to mimic the environment where the first interaction of probiotics with human intestinal cells occurs. We anticipate that the innate immune response differs along the maturation state of enterocytes and highlight adult-stem cell organoids as useful model to study *in vitro* probiotic strain-specific effects on human innate immune response modulation and enhancement of the intestinal epithelial barrier function.

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Presentation: Oral

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Toward regulatory transformation in the biological and chemical sectors globally: Progress and challenges

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The transition towards non-animal methods (NAMs) in global biological and chemical regulations represents a significant milestone in the protection of human health, the environment, and animal welfare. Humane Society International (HSI), through its leadership in the Animal-Free Safety Assessment (AFSA) Collaboration, is at the forefront of this transitional effort. AFSA unites many diverse stakeholders to accelerate the global adoption of NAMs & Next Generation Risk Assessment (NGRA) approaches, challenge existing regulatory frameworks, and eliminate unnecessary *in vivo* animal tests.

AFSA's regulatory transformation strategy focuses on establishing regulatory precedents that replace redundant *in vivo* tests with appropriate NAMs, with the ultimate goal of removing animal testing references from regulations.

AFSA's strategy also includes educational initiatives like the AFSA Master Class, designed to upskill individuals responsible for making safety and regulatory decisions using toxicity testing data.

In addition, HSI is also working towards a paradigm shift in chemicals management [1,2].

One significant activity is HSI's involvement in the European Commission's commitment to developing a *Roadmap for phasing out animal testing for chemical safety assessments*. By supporting the Roadmap's shaping and defining specific actions and milestones, this effort not only sets the stage for regional transformation but also paves the way for global regulatory change.

Through these comprehensive efforts, HSI and AFSA are not only advancing scientific innovation but also challenging the regulatory status quo, working towards a non-animal-based safety assessment framework.

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A brief introduction to 3Rs education in China

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Background: There are gradually progress on harmonization of human development, nature and ecological international since the 3Rs rules published in 1959. And education plays an important role along its development.

Objective: To share experiences on 3Rs in education in China and explore its road to further global collaboration.

Method: We collect responses and feedbacks from those selected 3Rs courses for undergraduate students at Sichuan University in 2019-2024. A brief summary on students, teaching methods, publication and challenges was in a descriptive way.

Results: There are growing number of students selected the course on alternative animal research and frontiers in health technology assessment since 2019 to 2024. 107 students completed 24 teaching hours per year, respectively. Teachers team were mainly from Germany, Spain, China. They give wonderful lectures, practice guidance & discuss in the summer, either through on line or onsite in Chengdu, China. We also wrote and published a related a book to support learning in 2022. There still exist challenges for 3Rs sustainable development, including poor of continue funding to support degree courses, publications, etc.

Summary: 3Rs in education are welcome for students, but more courses choice and supports would be helpful in the future.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Presentation: Oral

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***In vitro* skeletal muscle model responsive to free fatty acids: A promising tool for testing toxins and metabolites**

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Skeletal muscle, characterized by its significant proportion in the body, abundant blood supply, and high metabolic rate, is susceptible to the adverse effects of accumulated toxins, drugs, and their metabolites. To address its inherent complexity, we have developed a novel *in vitro* tissue culture model. This model successfully sustains human muscle tissue blocks for up to 13 days, using agarose to maintain the tissue, thereby preserving its three-dimensional microenvironment. It facilitates interactions among cytokines, satellite cells, and resident macrophages while allowing for substance diffusion and enabling the tissue to respond as a system to external stimuli. This approach aims to overcome the limitations of animal studies in clinical translation.

Overall, the initial concentration of specific cytokines in the tissue can influence the number and phenotypic changes of macrophages and satellite cells during culture. Muscle tissues are stimulated with both saturated and unsaturated fatty acids. Pro-inflammatory macrophages (CD80, MARCO) and myogenic stem cells (PAX7, MyoD) are activated upon exposure to unsaturated fatty acids, while anti-inflammatory macrophages (CD163, CD206, PTGER3) respond to both types of fatty acids. There is a coordinated response among different macrophage phenotypes to fatty acid stimulation, with associated changes in cell numbers.

This model maintains the structural integrity of skeletal muscle tissue in a manner akin to natural conditions and properly reflects human tissue responses under stimulation. It also eliminates the replenishment of resident macrophages by circulating monocytes. This simple, easy-to-use model holds potential as a tool for testing other compounds, nutrients, or toxic substances in the future.

Conflict of interest

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